

Co-UDlabs
COLLABORATIVE URBAN DRAINAGE
RESEARCH LABS COMMUNITIES

Grant Agreement No. 101008626

Co-UDlabs

Building Collaborative
Urban Drainage research labs communities

D10.3 3rd Periodic Technical Report Part B

Period covered by this report:
M37 (01/05/2024) to M48 (30/04/2025)

Periodic report:
3rd (M48)

Document tracks details

Project acronym	Co-UDlabs
Project title	Building Collaborative Urban Drainage research labs communities
Starting date	01.05.2021
Duration	48 months
Call identifier	H2020-INFRAIA-2020-1
Grant Agreement No	101008626

Deliverable Information	
Deliverable number	D10.3
Work package number	WP10
Deliverable title	3 rd Periodic Report
Lead beneficiary	UDC
Author(s)	Jose Anta, Juan Naves, Alejandra Pimiento, Andrea Ciambra (UDC), Simon Tait, Alma Schellart, James Shucksmith (USFD), Antonio Moreno (Deltares), Jörg Rieckermann, João Leitão (EAWAG), Thomas Brüggemann, Marcel Goerke, Iain Naismith (IKT), Jean-Luc Bertrand-Krajewski, Frédéric Cherqui, Gislain Lipeme Kouyi (INSA-Lyon), Jesper Ellerbaek Nielsen (AAU), Elodie BreLOT (GRAIE), Laura De Nale (Euronovia)
Due date	30/06/2025
Actual submission date	30/06/2025
Type of deliverable	Report
Dissemination level	Public

Version Management

Revision history and quality check			
Version	Name	Date	Comment
V 0.0	Jose Anta, Andrea Ciambra (UDC)	02/05/2025	Report Template for circulation among WP leaders and TA providers
V 0.1	Laura De Nale (Euronovia), Jörg Rieckermann (EAWAG), Jesper E. Nielsen (AAU), Elodie BreLOT (GRAIE)	16/05/2025	Early contributions from WP leaders

V 0.2	Jean-Luc Bertrand-Krajewski (INSA)	23/05/2025	Technical contributions to the report
V 0.4	Thomas Brüggemann, Iain Naismith, Marcel Goerke (IKT), Antonio Moreno (DEL)	30/05/2025	First draft for additional contributions and revisions
V 0.5	Jose Anta, Andrea Ciambra, Alejandra Pimiento (UDC)	09/06/2025	First draft for additional contributions and revisions
V 0.6	Thomas Brüggemann, Iain Naismith, Marcel Goerke (IKT), Andrea Ciambra (UDC)	10/06/2024	Revisions to TA contents, draft consolidation
V 0.7	Jörg Rieckermann (EAWAG), Alejandra Pimiento (UDC), Simon Tait, James Shucksmith (USFD), Jean-Luc Bertrand-Krajewski, Frederic Cherqui, Gislain Lipeme (INSA), Antonio Moreno (DEL), Jesper E. Nielsen (AAU),	17/06/2024	Revision of main contents, draft consolidation
V 1.0	Jose Anta , Alejandra Pimiento and Andrea Ciambra (UDC)	23/06/2025	First consolidated version for final round of revision
V 1.1	Jose Anta, Andrea Ciambra, Alejandra Pimiento (UDC), Simon Tait (USFD), Antonio Moreno (DEL), Jörg Rieckermann (EAWAG), Thomas Brüggemann (IKT), Jean-Luc Bertrand-Krajewski (INSA), Elodie Brelot (GRAIE), Laura De Nale (Euronovia)	27/06/2024	Revision of consolidated version and adding last requests
V 2.0	Jose Anta, Andrea Ciambra, Alejandra Pimiento (UDC)	30/06/2025	Final version to submit for RP3
V 3.0	Jose Anta, Andrea Ciambra (UDC)	24/07/2025	Final version with revisions from Project Advisor Office
V 3.1	Jose Anta, Andrea Ciambra (UDC)	12/08/2025	Final version with revisions from Project Advisor Office

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List of acronyms

Acronym	Full definition
CCTV	Closed-circuit television
CEE	Central Eastern Europe
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
CFS	Certificate of Financial Statements
CNTs	Carbon nanotubes
COD	chemical oxygen demand
CSO	Combined sewer overflows
DAS	Distributed Acoustic Sensing
DIC	Digital Image Correlation
DMP	Data Management Plan
DO	Dissolved oxygen
DoA	Description of Action
DV	Data Validation
EDM	Event duration monitoring
EJSW	European Junior Scientists' Workshop
EU	European Union
EURO-SAM	European Sewer Asset Management JCUD Working Group
EWA	European Water Association
GA	Grant Agreement
GBGR	Green and blue-green roof
H ₂ S	Hydrogen sulphide
IAB	International Advisory Board
IAHR	International Association of Hydro-environmental Research
ICRA	Catalan Institute for Water Research
ICUD	International Conference on Urban Drainage
IFRs	Inline Flow Restrictors
IoT	Internet of Things
IWA	International Water Association
IWGM	IWA/IAHR Working Group on Data and Models
JCUD	Joint Committee on Urban Drainage
JRA	Joint Research Activity
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
LAI	Local Area Infiltration
LAZE	Local-Area-Zero-Emission
LJMU	Liverpool John Moores University
LSPIV	Large-Scale Particle Image Velocimetry
LTU	Luleå University of Technology
ML	Machine Learning
MOFs	Metal Organic Frameworks

MOH	mineral oil hydrocarbons
MS	Milestone
MST	Management and Support Team
NA	Networking Activity
NBS	Nature Based Solutions
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
PA	Project Advisor
PBPM	Polyurethane Bound Permeable Mixture
PEDR	Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of Project Results
PM	Person/Month
POPD	Protection of Personal Data
PR	Periodic Report
PTV	Particle tracking velocimetry
RI	Research Infrastructure
RP	Reporting Period
SIS	Swedish Institute for Standards
SME	Small-Medium Enterprise
SPH	Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics
SSS	Separate sewer systems
SuDS	Sustainable urban drainage systems
SWMM	Storm Water Management Model
TA	Transnational Access
TES	Toronto Exfiltration System
TMU	Toronto Metropolitan University
TRT	Thermal Response Tests
TSS	Total Suspended Solids
UA	Uncertainty Assessment
UD	Urban Drainage
UDMT	Urban Drainage Metrology Toolbox
UDS	Urban Drainage Systems
UFA	User Facility Agreement
UoB	University of Belgrade
UPP	User Project Plan
UWWTD	Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package
WWTW	Wastewater treatment works

List of project partners acronyms

Acronym	Institution
UDC	Universidade da Coruña
USFD	University of Sheffield
DEL	Stichting Deltares
EAWAG	Eidgenoessische Anstalt für Wasserversorgung Abwasserreinigung und Gewaesserschutz
IKT	IKT - Institut für Unterirdische Infrastruktur GmbH (Institute for Underground Infrastructure)
INSA	Institut national des sciences appliquées de Lyon
AAU	Aalborg Universitet
GRAIE	Groupe de recherche animation technique et information sur l'eau
EURO	Euronovia

1 Explanation of the work carried out by the beneficiaries and overview of the progress

Co-UDlabs is a four-year project designed to integrate research and innovation activities at the European level in the field of Urban Drainage Systems (UDS). The project brings together seven key Research Infrastructures, encompassing 17 facilities, into a unified and ambitious initiative that offers a comprehensive transnational access programme to the Urban Drainage community. By the end of Reporting Period 3 (RP3), which marks the conclusion of the project, the nine Co-UDlabs partners have actively engaged in the core activities outlined in the INFRAIA call: Networking Activities, Joint Research Activities, and the Transnational Access programme. This report presents evidence, figures, and results from the activities conducted between May 2024 and April 2025. As this is the final reporting period, it also includes a summary of the overall outcomes of the project.

Building on the significant progress made during the first two reporting periods, Co-UDlabs entered its final phase with a solid foundation of collaboration, impact, and consolidation within the European research infrastructure (RI) landscape for UDS. During RP3, the consortium focused on maximizing the impact of its activities, ensuring the sustainability of its outcomes, and laying the groundwork for the continuation of the network beyond the project's lifecycle. In this period, Co-UDlabs successfully completed the implementation of its ambitious Transnational Access (TA) programme, overseeing the finalization of selected projects across its facilities and supporting the generation of high-value scientific, technical, and applied results. The Joint Research Activities (JRAs) reached key milestones, with preliminary results published and further scientific contributions in preparation, reinforcing the project's role as a reference point for innovation and collaboration in UDS.

Through its Networking Activities (NAs), the project continued to expand and diversify its stakeholder community, strengthening connections with key actors from the public, private, and academic sectors. Training and dissemination efforts were sustained through new seminars, workshops, and educational materials aimed at a broad audience. Internally, coordination efforts intensified, particularly in data management, exploitation planning, and the development of a roadmap for the project's legacy. The remainder of this section outlines the key efforts, initiatives, and results for each Work Package (WP), providing a comprehensive overview of the final implementation of Co-UDlabs.

WP1: Sectorial Integration and Sustainability Strategy. WP1 focused on developing the knowledge base and methodologies necessary to promote the long-term sustainability and impact of Co-UDlabs. During RP3, the main tasks carried out included:

- **D1.2. Roadmap of Research Infrastructures (RIs) to Support Effective UDS Transition at the EU Level:** This deliverable aimed to gather insights from a broad range of stakeholders to identify which practices RIs should adopt, maintain, or improve to optimize urban drainage (UD) management. Sources included existing literature in the water and environmental sectors, input from academic researchers and scientists involved in Co-UDlabs, and contributions from other project partners.
- **Collaborative exchanges and meetings:** Numerous conversations and strategic discussions among WP1 partners helped consolidate proposals to enhance knowledge transfer at both

national and European levels. Monthly WP1 meetings, held from March to October 2024, were instrumental in refining the content of Deliverable D1.2.

- **D1.3. Strategy for RI Sustainability and Community Development:** This strategy was designed to ensure long-term viability and advancement of RIs. It emphasized increasing visibility and accessibility, fostering interdisciplinary collaboration, enhancing knowledge exchange, and identifying future funding opportunities. Key achievements included the establishment of the UDRAIN Working Group (supporting global coordination through shared standards), the creation of an RI atlas, and the launch of new training and funding initiatives. Engagement with EU and national bodies, industry stakeholders, and utilities was pursued, along with exploration of funding avenues such as ESFRI, ERIC, and Open Science initiatives.
- **Policy Briefs:** Two "Policy Brief" documents were prepared under WP1. One addressed the management of combined sewer overflows (CSOs), drawing on work from WP2 and WP6. The other highlighted Co-UDlabs' contributions to the European Research Infrastructures landscape.

WP2. Harmonisation and capacity building. WP2 aimed to enhance the interoperability, reproducibility, and overall quality of urban drainage research by standardizing data practices, facilitating staff exchanges, and addressing institutional barriers to smart governance. The work aligned closely with Co-UDlabs' objectives on open science, FAIR data, and evidence-based decision-making. Key activities and results during RP3 included:

- **Revised Data Management Plan (DMP):** A new DMP template was adopted consortium-wide to better support open science. It offered greater flexibility for researchers and clearer guidance on metadata, licensing (CC0), and long-term data accessibility.
- **Controlled Vocabulary Development:** WP2 created a standardized vocabulary for sensor and variable names related to rainfall, hydraulics, and water quality. These were mapped to standards such as INSPIRE, SSN/SOSA, and WaterML, and now inform ongoing ontology work by IWA/IWGDM.
- **SensorThings API Implementation:** This API was tested using the Urban Water Observatory dataset, replacing outdated protocols and improving compatibility with FAIR data principles and real-time applications. The Renku platform was piloted in three reproducibility use cases, demonstrating strong potential for workflow tracking and data lineage in urban drainage research.
- **Staff Mobility Exchanges:** WP2 organized and documented 15 staff exchanges (totalling 45 person-days), focusing on joint experimentation, model calibration, sensor testing, and data-sharing strategies.
- **Multilingual Stakeholder Survey:** A comprehensive survey was conducted across Co-UDlabs countries to assess how CSO monitoring data is managed and shared. A total of 147 responses were collected and analyzed.
- **Survey Insights:** Results showed that while CSO monitoring is widespread, the data is often underutilized for compliance or planning. Organizational and regulatory barriers—rather than technical limitations—were identified as the main obstacles to data transparency and public access.

- **Policy Relevance:** The survey findings directly support the implementation of the revised Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive (UWWTD), which mandates performance-based CSO monitoring and reporting.

WP3. Training activities. WP3 aimed to enhance collaboration among diverse UD stakeholders by promoting knowledge transfer and community building. Activities were designed to disseminate scientific and technical knowledge to practitioners and authorities, connect early-stage researchers across Europe, and facilitate broader knowledge exchange. The WP was structured into three main tasks: Task 3.1: Free, open training activities for junior and early-stage researchers from both the Co-UDlabs consortium and the wider Urban Drainage community; Task 3.2: Training activities targeted at industry professionals and practitioners; Task 3.3: Public webinars. Key results from these training activities (detailed in Section 1.2.3) include:

- **26th European Junior Scientist Workshop (EJSW)** on “Monitoring UDS and Rivers”: A highly regarded event in the UD research field, supporting both knowledge dissemination and community building for early-stage researchers (Task 3.1).
- **Course on Sewer Processes:** Focused on hydrogen sulfide modeling and management, aimed at disseminating advanced knowledge within the research community (Task 3.1).
- **Applied Course on Urban Drainage Metrology:** Designed for professionals in the water sector, including industry and public authorities (Task 3.2).
- **Workshop on FAIR Data Practices:** Promoted best practices in data management and sharing within the urban drainage field (Task 3.2).
- **Webinars and Online Workshops (Task 3.3)** on, among others, Routine Data Validation; Underground Infrastructure State Monitoring; Key Findings from Co-UDlabs and How to Access Them; and FAIR Data Practices in Urban Drainage.

WP4. Communication, dissemination, and exploitation of results. Co-UDlabs outcomes and activities were disseminated in a structured way within the framework of WP4, reaching a very good level of visibility among a variety of stakeholders of the urban drainage sector: researchers, industrials, students, policymakers, citizens. The communication and dissemination activities have been really satisfying, overstepping in some cases the project expectations, as demonstrated by the key performance indicators (KPIs) identified and monitored by the project (see Annex 1). These are the main activities we highlight for RP3:

- The project mailing list has significantly expanded (546 contacts), as well as the number of followers on social media, thanks to the active media strategy and online presence of the project.
- Several new dissemination materials were produced, including new scientific publications, a [policy brief](#), a [success story series](#) on the project website, 3 newsletters, a [final media press kit](#), a [final press release](#).
- Project partners have been very active, in the final months of the project. In addition to dissemination efforts, they worked to validate the list of Key Exploitable Results (KERs) and their related exploitation strategies (see D4.4).
- During RP3 project partners organized 12 events and participated in 12 external events where Co-UDlabs activities were presented, and results disseminated.

- Project partners organised a [public final event](#) to celebrate the conclusion of Co-UDlabs activities and its early and consolidated results (March 18, 2025 - Brussels, Belgium).
- Over the period, Co-UDlabs partners published 18 scientific publications (13 conference papers and 5 journal articles) and 2 technical articles.
- The final Data Management Plan was submitted at M48 as a new version of Deliverable 4.1.

WP5. Management of Transnational Access (TA). After the organization of the 1st, 2nd and 3rd TA call in RP1 and RP2, during RP3, withing WP5 the different partners and users organized the signature of the documents as the User Facility Agreement (UFA) or DMPs to ensure effective coordination between user groups and facility providers prior to star of access for the 18 TA provision resulting from the 2nd and 3rd calls. Comprehensive operational and logistical support was provided, including preparatory activities and administrative arrangements. On-site support included experimental setup, supervision, and data collection was also provided in the framework of each access in WP9. Each facility assigned scientific and technical staff to assist users, ensuring thorough pre visit preparation and support throughout the experimental phase.

WP6. JRA 1 – Smart sensing and monitoring in urban drainage. WP6 fosters a paradigm shift in UDS management: transitioning from current inefficient approaches towards a digitised, informed, shared, evidence-based decision process based on truly smart monitoring. During the reporting period M37-M48, WP6 work was mainly devoted to the following aspects:

- Task 6.1 on sensors testing: final writing and editing of Deliverable 6.2 on the outcomes of testing the 8 sensors / technologies selected in previous steps (see Deliverable 6.1).
- Task 6.2 on the Urban Drainage Metrology Toolbox (UDMT) software tool: i) revision of the entire code, final tests and debugging, creation of new examples of application, and update of Deliverable 6.3 with the new version UDMT 2025a, ii) continuation of webinars and training courses on UDMT for its dissemination.
- Task 6.3 on spatially distributed data: final writing and editing of Deliverable 6.4 on CSO data sets.

All deliverables, data set and source codes produced in WP6 are openly available, either on Zenodo or on institutional repositories.

WP7. JRA 2 – Evaluation of assets deterioration in urban drainage systems (UDS). WP7 has focussed on two aspects in the final reporting period. It has investigated the development of joint failures a very common occurrence observed in deteriorating pipes. This was carried out jointly by USFD and IKT and involved instrument development and joint experimental work and analysis. The experimental instrumentation has now been deployed to examine liner failure. The second focus was on the use of network models to simulate the impact of individual pipe defects at a network scale, this involved joint work between USFD and EAWAG.

- In Task 7.2 a limited number of laboratory tests were carried out at both USFD and IKT to examine the behaviour of pipe joint articulation and exfiltration from jointed pipes. The results indicated the exfiltration behaviour depended on the pipe material and the angle of articulation. The results were reported in Deliverable 7.4. Experimental measurement

equipment developed at USFD was deployed at IKT to investigate its feasibility to support full testing for an international innovation project.

- In Task 7.3 network models had been obtained from water utilities in the UK, Belgium and the Netherlands. These models were converted from their original model formats (e.g. MikeUrban, Infoworks) into SWMM models to make them suitable for the defect-impact modelling. MatSWMM code was developed that allowed multiple defect types to be inserted in large network models automatically, so that the performance of large complex sewer networks could be examined for multiple rainfall events. Both flooding and overflow performance was examined, and the results were reported in Deliverable 7.5.

WP8. JRA 3 - Improving resilience and sustainability in urban drainage solutions. WP8 has concentrated on comprehending the performance of hydraulic and pollutant retention of new forms of urban drainage infrastructure and assesses the sustainability of some sustainable urban drainage systems (SuDS) techniques. The primary tasks executed during RP3 included the following:

- Task 8.1 focused on consolidating experimental results from RP2 into scientific publications. These include studies on topographic survey methods, optical imaging applications, permeable pavement performance, and macro-plastic retention in gully pots.
- Task 8.2 provided new insights into UDS resilience. USFD demonstrated how sediments are mobilized during flood events and the role of manhole structures in sediment retention. EAWAG and UDC assessed how poor maintenance affects the hydrological performance of Blue-Green Infrastructure.
- Task 8.3 contributed to sustainability assessment methods. INSA developed and validated a dual-permeability infiltration model for designer soils, while AAU created a prototype tool (LAZE) to simulate water and chemical transport in SuDS, supporting optimized filter media design.

WP9. Transnational Access provision. WP9 oversaw the coordination and optimization of the TA program, ensuring the availability of the 17 facilities across the seven research infrastructures offered by Co-UDlabs. Under WP3, partners implemented and finalized the 18 technical assistance projects approved during the 2nd and 3rd Co-UDlabs calls. Table 1.1 below lists all TA projects that received access during this period. Further details on these accesses are provided in Deliverable D9.2 Final report on TA provision.

Table 1.1. Summary of work performed in Co-UDlabs facilities during RP3 per TA

Host Institution	Facility	Awarded Proposal Acronym	Project start date	Project end date	Days of access provided				
					RP1	RP2	RP3	Total	Expected
UDC	STREET	UDC-06-STREET-Linnemann	15/09/2024	08/11/2024	-	-	34	34	40
UDC	STREET	UDC-07-STREET-Lutze	01/04/2024	14/09/2024	-	26	52	78	60
UDC	BLOCK	UDC-04-BLOCK-Franca	01/07/2024	08/11/2024	-	-	70	70	60
UDC	BLOCK	UDC-05-BLOCK-Coupe	09/12/2024	24/03/2025	-	-	51	51	60
USFD	RTC RIG	USFD-07-RTC RIG-Vanderwerf	12/07/2024	17/09/2024	-	-	47	47	40
USFD	RTC RIG	USFD-08-RTC RIG-Gutierrez	05/06/2024	02/10/2024	-	-	26	26	20
USFD	BURIED INF.	USFD-06-BURIED-Joksimovic	21/07/2024	22/04/2025	-	-	35	35	35
USFD	A/B FLUME	USFD-05-ABFLUME-Martins	13/04/2024	10/07/2024	-	12	49	61	60
DEL	B-LOOP	DEL-01-BLOOP-Besharat	29/04/2024	07/06/2024	-	3	37	39	40
DEL	B-LOOP	DEL-02-BLOOP-Farhadiroushan	01/07/2024	16/09/2024	-	-	40	40	40
EAWAG	UWO	EAWAG-04-UWO-Dittmer	01/03/2024	28/02/2025	-	7	50	57	7
EAWAG	UWO	EAWAG-05-UWO-Abdelaal	01/03/2024	11/03/2025	-	10	1	11	15
IKT	IKT TEST	IKT-03-TEST-Carnacina	02/01/2024	24/01/2025	-	-	15	15	15
IKT	IKT TEST	IKT-04-TEST-Johansen	03/06/2024	30/08/2024	-	-	20	20	20
INSA	OTHU DRB	INSA-04-DRB-LE GAC	06/06/2024	06/11/2024	-	-	7	7	10
INSA	OTHU SuDS	INSA-03-OTHU-Prodanovic	18/06/2024	01/11/2024	-	-	17	17	10
INSA	GROOF	INSA-02-GROOF-Foerster	01/09/2024	31/03/2025	-	-	24	24	28
AAU	FREJLEV	AAU-01-FREJLEV-Laanearu	10/02/2025	03/03/2025	-	-	11	11	20

WP10. Project Management. WP10 is responsible for the day-to-day management of the project and for ensuring effective coordination among partners and WPs. During RP3, WP10's activities focused on three main areas: supporting the implementation of the TA programme, coordinating the project's governance bodies, and managing internal and external reporting. In this period, WP10 provided support for the development and execution of the TA programme, assisting the facility providers in the implementation of the selected access projects. It also coordinated the organisation of key project events, including the 4th General Assembly held in Gelsenkirchen in December 2024, and the Final General Assembly and the Final project InfoDay, which took place in Brussels in March 2025. WP10 ensured the timely delivery of project milestones and deliverables, was in charge of all internal communication, and has been the consortium's direct intermediary with the European Commission.

1.1 Objectives

The main objective of Co-UDlabs was to provide a transnational, multidisciplinary collaborative research infrastructure that brought together European stakeholders, academic researchers, and innovators in the urban drainage and water management sector. The Co-UDlabs framework enabled them to share ideas, co-develop project concepts, and access top-tier research infrastructures. The aim was to develop, enhance, and test innovative methods and technologies while fostering a collaborative European Urban Drainage innovation community.

The project also delivered a variety of activities that engaged the multidisciplinary urban drainage research community, water utilities and their supply chains, local authorities, and regulators. These

efforts ensured that institutions and organizations across the EU could contribute to the development of an efficient research and innovation environment centred around the Co-UDlabs Research Infrastructure. In relation with the main objective, Co-UDlabs addressed the following specific objectives:

O1: To foster a culture of co-operation between RIs and the urban drainage community through a set of coordinated Networking Activities - NA (WP1 to WP5), which help to develop a more inclusive, open and efficient research and innovation environment. A program of collaborative activities will engage the EU urban drainage sector to exchange knowledge, collaboratively generate and encourage innovation and enable multiple avenues of research, development of technology and innovation, thereby contributing to the delivery of a long-term, sustainable Research Infrastructure in the European water sector.

The main contributions of the different WPs towards this specific objective can be summed up as follows:

- **WP1** facilitated genuine collaborative work among project partners—particularly the operators of the research infrastructures—to review their functioning in relation to their core objective: advancing knowledge and practices in urban stormwater management at both international and, especially, European levels. Discussions on national practices and desired developments proved highly productive and informed the two roadmap reports. The launch and consolidation of the UDRAIN IWA/IAHR Working Group further strengthened long-term collaboration between research infrastructures across Europe and globally.
- **WP2** fostered stronger cooperation between research infrastructures by establishing common data standards and promoting interoperability. It championed the adoption of FAIR principles to ensure data could be shared and reused across facilities. The team introduced open science tools such as Renku to enhance reproducibility and transparency. Staff exchanges and regular meetings contributed to the development of shared skills and practices. WP2 also conducted a cross-country survey on smart governance and public access to data, beginning with a Swiss case study and promoting the initiative through the European Water Association (EWA). Additionally, an ongoing activity on FAIR urban drainage data was launched in collaboration with the IWA/IAHR Working Group on Data and Models (IWGM), actively engaging the UDS community in the development of open, harmonised data practices.
- **WP3** aimed to enhance knowledge transfer and skills development both among project partners and between the research community and practitioners. A key objective was to promote the use of Co-UDlabs Research Infrastructures through targeted actions designed to engage future users. Additionally, the project sought to build a pool of highly qualified professionals by offering tailored training activities for the broader urban drainage community, with particular emphasis on increasing participation from industry stakeholders and early-stage researchers. Actions under Task 3.1—such as the 26th European Junior Scientist Workshop (EJSW) and the PhD course on hydrogen sulphide—focused on disseminating technical knowledge to early-stage researchers and strengthening international scientific networks. These one-week, in-situ events enabled PhD researchers to collaborate closely, inspire one another, and acquire new analytical and technical skills. They also fostered the dissemination of a shared ethical culture within the community, allowing young researchers to learn from each other's experiences and better understand what is considered

standard practice beyond the cultural particularities of individual research groups. Task 3.2 activities—such as workshops on uncertainty in metrology and FAIR data—focused on sharing analytical techniques and measurement practices with stakeholders from the urban drainage water industry. Finally, during RP3, several webinars were organised under Task 3.3 to disseminate novel techniques and practices in water infrastructure monitoring and data management. These events included participation from non-Co-UDlabs partners, serving as a broader dissemination platform for the urban drainage community.

- **WP4** provided continuous support to all project partners in actively communicating project activities and disseminating results to a broad range of stakeholders within the urban drainage community, as well as to the general public. During RP3, efforts focused on promoting events and training sessions organised by project partners to attract new participants, supporting partners' involvement in external events to foster collaboration and knowledge exchange with other researchers, and coordinating the final Infoday held in March 2025 in Brussels. Additionally, WP4 was responsible for preparing dissemination materials that highlighted project outcomes, including the publication of success stories, a final media press kit, a concluding press release, and the final project newsletter.

O2: To facilitate free of charge Transnational Access – TA (WP5, 9) to 17 leading European facilities by two open calls. The calls and the project both focus on support to scientific communities and water utility and supply chain innovators in their access to highly relevant research facilities. Co-UDlabs will provide research infrastructure (physical and knowledge-based) to undertake breakthrough engineering and scientific research and innovation using multi-institutional and multi-sectorial teams to develop solutions that have the potential to transform the European urban drainage sector and provide credible evidence that these solutions work.

The main contribution of WP5 during RP3 was the organisation and management of access provision under the second and third calls. As part of WP9 activities, 18 projects from these calls were successfully completed. These Transnational Access (TA) projects had a significant impact across several key areas of urban drainage research and technological development. Many addressed challenges related to urbanisation and climate change, while others explored commercial applications of emerging technologies, instrumentation, and methodologies. Additionally, several projects contributed to the development of new protocols, standards, and datasets aimed at supporting policymakers, regulators, and urban water utilities in enhancing their decision-making processes.

O3: To enlarge and strengthen the quality and quantity of the services offered at European level by Co-UDlabs through a combination of interconnected Joint Research Activities - JRA (WP6, WP7, WP8). These activities will improve our understanding of asset deterioration and secure the long-term resilience and sustainability of urban drainage systems with the help of more robust, autonomous and interconnected smart monitoring techniques, and digital water data analysis tools.

The main contribution of the different WP towards this specific objective have been the following:

- **WP6** contributed to fostering a more open and efficient research and innovation environment, enhancing services at the EU level and beyond. It delivered results from novel sensor testing, introducing technologies capable of providing reliable new data. Dual-partner evaluations promoted collaboration among Co-UDlabs research infrastructures. WP6 also

improved services through the development and dissemination of the UDMT—a free software tool offering methods for sensor calibration, data correction, uncertainty assessment, and validation. Training sessions and webinars supported the uptake of UDMT among researchers and operators. The work package also highlighted the value of accessible, spatially distributed datasets through a detailed analysis of UK CSO data and a comparative study of CSO data use in regulation across Europe. All WP6 outputs—including deliverables, datasets, software, and source code—will be made openly available, for example via Zenodo, at the end of the project.

- **WP7** developed techniques and tools to better understand deterioration processes and quantify the impact of individual assets at the network level. This integration of system performance and asset deterioration supports operators in targeting maintenance and renewal investments to ensure the long-term resilience and sustainability of piped urban drainage systems. Notably, a new in-pipe camera inspection technology was developed to measure joint movement within pipes, enabling the measurement of joint displacement angles and sizes. This innovation allowed researchers to link exfiltration rates with joint condition for the first time. The same technique is now being used to assess defects in cured-in-place liners, enabling in-pipe measurements to be correlated with performance reductions. Network modelling clearly demonstrated the impact of various in-pipe defects (e.g. deposits, blockages, and pipe wall deterioration) on flood risk and overflow volumes. The influence of individual defects was analysed to provide actionable insights for water utilities in prioritising maintenance.
- **WP8** advanced the resilience and sustainability of urban drainage systems during RP3. While imaging techniques continued to support the characterisation of urban assets, the main impact of this period stemmed from experimental studies and modelling efforts focused on infrastructure performance and sustainability. Task 8.2 provided valuable insights into sediment transport during flood events and the role of maintenance in Blue-Green Infrastructure, informing risk assessment and operational strategies. In Task 8.3, new methodologies were developed to evaluate SuDS sustainability, including a dual-permeability infiltration model and the LAZE simulation tool. These tools support the design of filter media that balance hydraulic efficiency with pollutant retention. The outcomes offer practical tools and knowledge to enhance urban flood resilience and guide sustainable drainage planning.

1.2 Explanation of the work carried out per WP

1.2.1 Work Package 1 - Sectorial Integration and Sustainability Strategy

WP1 aimed to strengthen the role and long-term impact of RIs by exploring how they can evolve to better support the transition towards more sustainable and intelligent urban water systems. This effort was guided by a broad strategic vision for the future of urban drainage research in Europe, drawing on diverse sources of knowledge and input from a wide range of stakeholders. Task 1.1 was completed during the previous reporting period, although a paper derived from the work performed after the workshop “Tapping the Value of UDS Data” held in the IWA World Water Congress has been accepted at the moment of writing this deliverable. All the partners with the exception of Euronovia, are involved in this WP.

Task 1.2. Development of a roadmap to identify the role of RI to transition to more sustainable and smart urban drainage systems (Lead GRAIE)

The main aim of the task during RP3 was to develop a roadmap to identify the position of RIs within the landscape of UDS community actors and stakeholders, to foster the transition toward more sustainable and smarter UDS. The task focused on the key research topics described in the JRA of Co-UDlabs.

The Roadmap of RI required to support effective UDS transition at EU level was included in D1.2. The recommendations were drawn up based on interviews and surveys of Co-UDlabs members and partners, as well as a bibliography review to benchmark the mechanisms and initiatives implemented to optimise knowledge transfer in other domains.

The results indicated that specific national characteristics, particularly regulations, governance structures, and the distribution of responsibilities in urban stormwater management, made it difficult to adopt a unified approach at European level. However, the recommendations aligned on several key priorities: opening RIs to broader partnerships and networking opportunities, encouraging multidisciplinary training to foster openness and curiosity about the complex research-based solutions, and identifying local and national relays to overcome language barriers and the legitimacy of practitioners in accessing this type of knowledge and collaboration.

Task 1.3. Co-UDlabs Strategy for RI Sustainability and Community (Lead UDC)

The aim of this task was to support the long-term development and integration of RIs across Europe to address the ongoing research and dissemination needs of the EU water sector in relation to UDS. A strategy was developed for the long-term consolidation of a European Urban Drainage RI community, building on the experience and outcomes of Co-UDlabs.

A key achievement was the establishment of the UDRAIN Working Group, created to serve as a global platform for RI collaboration, technical coordination, and increased visibility. This initiative, supported by a growing number of international institutions, reflected the momentum and interest generated by Co-UDlabs and provided a foundation for consolidating its results and partnerships.

However, sustaining this momentum required navigating new funding landscapes. With fewer opportunities for Starting Communities under Horizon Europe, Co-UDlabs partners explored alternative paths, including cross-disciplinary initiatives, alignment with ESFRI and ERIC frameworks, and participation in digital and environmental research programs.

Equally important was the need to maintain strong connections with users, particularly utilities, SMEs, and policymakers. Ensuring the visibility, accessibility, and relevance of RIs depended on ongoing efforts to promote best practices, shared standards, and co-created solutions. Enhancing communication and reducing entry barriers, such as language or administrative complexity, were identified as critical steps to engage a broader and more diverse community.

Finally, under WP1, two Policy Briefs were prepared—one on managing combined sewer overflows (based on WP2 and WP6), and another on Co-UDlabs' role in European Research Infrastructures (more details are provided in section 4).

Summary of Deliverables

Deliverables completed:	D1.2 - The Roadmap of RI required to support effective UDS transition at EU level (M42) D1.3 – Strategy for RI Sustainability and Community Development (M48)
Deliverables submitted past due date:	None

Summary of Milestones

Milestones completed:	None
Milestones submitted past due date:	None

1.2.2 Work Package 2 – Harmonization and Capacity Building

WP2 promotes interoperability, collaboration, and capacity building across Co-UDlabs by standardising data, enabling staff exchange, and addressing barriers to open data in urban drainage. Task 2.1 improved data practices by updating the Data Management Plan, creating a shared vocabulary, adopting the SensorThings API, and testing reproducible workflows with Renku. Task 2.2 organised 15 staff exchanges to strengthen collaboration. Task 2.3 ran a multilingual survey on CSO monitoring, showing data is often collected but rarely used for compliance—findings that now inform UWWTD implementation. All the partners are involved in this WP.

Task 2.1. Ensuring interoperability by definition of common standards, protocols and methods (Lead EAWAG)

Task 2.1 aimed to standardise data and methods across Co-UDlabs and lay the foundation for interoperable urban drainage monitoring. The DMP template was revised based on partner feedback and a visit to the University of La Coruña, introducing open-text fields to improve flexibility. While the updated DMP supports open science and adopts the CC0 license, challenges remain around delayed completion, variable quality of inputs, and manual dataset updates.

Significant progress was made on harmonising variable names for rainfall, flow, and water quality monitoring (Figure 1.1). These were mapped to existing standards (INSPIRE, SSN/SOSA, WaterML), and a controlled vocabulary was curated from sources such as GWSW, GEMET, and EN standards. This vocabulary will support future ontology development. To advance this, WP2 launched an expert group under the International Working Group on Data and Models (IWGDM), with workshops planned to define a shared UDS ontology. External collaboration has begun with Water4all, the University of Lisbon, and the OGC.

To modernise data exchange, WP2 transitioned from the legacy SOS protocol to the SensorThings API (STA) using the FROST Server, tested on UWO data from Fehrltorf. This shift to JSON/REST improves usability, supports FAIR principles, and aligns with emerging EU regulations like the revised UWWTD.

Figure 1.1: Sankey chart representing the mapping from references to TA and JRA variables categories. An interactive version can be accessed online [link].

Reproducibility was a key focus, with three Renku-based use cases developed: validation of sediment data, reimplementing of a UDMT tool in Python, and sewer defect detection using deep learning. These highlighted Renku’s strengths in provenance tracking and workflow integration, as well as its limitations for heavy computation. Results were presented at ICUD 2024 (Figure 1.2) and EJSW, with further sessions and IWGDM-led workshops planned for 2025 to promote standardised, reproducible urban drainage research.

Figure 1.2: Presentation of Improving the reproducibility and provenance of urban drainage data and models in the ICUD conference 2024

Task 2.2. Development and mobility of personnel staff (Lead Euronovia)

The objective of Task 2.2 was to organise mobility for project partners to facilitate the exchange of best practices and know-how among the project staff and the participants working in Research Infrastructures. This activity was meant to build internal capacity, support the networking and trust

between all partners, stimulate exchange, development and inspire new ideas for improved quality and services.

During the period covered by this report (May 2024 to April 2025), project partners have participated in 15 mobility sessions, for a total of 45 person-days, corresponding to 9 weeks. USFD and IKT are the partners with the highest number of mobilities implemented (27,5 days and 14 person-days respectively) with only one visit from AaU and INSA in this reporting period (1 person-day and 2,5 days respectively). Details are available in Table 1.2.

Table 1.2. Overview of staff mobility activities within WP2 in RP3. SP: Sending partner, HP: Hosting Partner

SP	HP	Days	Staff #1	Staff #2	Purpose of the mission	WP	Start	End
USFD	IKT	4	Gavin Sailor		Coordination regarding the implementation of the tests of WP 7 (JRA2), Task 7.2, Instruction of IKT staff in the use of an inspection system developed by USFD	WP7	03/06/2024	06/06/2024
USFD	AaU	2,5	Isabel Douterelo		Visit the research facilities at AAU; Discuss a future EU Doctoral Network proposal with AAU participation.		16/06/2024	19/06/2024
IKT	EAWAG	4	Thomas Brüggemann	Bert Bosseler	Knowledge transfer SUDS / data harmonization	WP2	02/09/2024	03/09/2024
USFD	IKT	3	Simon Tait		WP7 task planning, webinar planning, support dissemination event	WP7	10/09/2024	12/09/2024
INSA	IKT	2,5	Jean-Luc Bertrand-Krajewski		Green roof experiments related to TA Indoor-Grasp (WP9) & Presentation of Co-UDlabs project (related to WP4) & Participation to the IKT 30th Anniversary conference	WP2	10/09/2024	12/09/2024
IKT	INSA	2	Marcel Goerke		Collaboration on SUDS: green roofs	WP8	16/09/2024	17/09/2024
IKT	USFD	4	Thomas Brüggemann	Yongxiang Qiao	Collaboration on deterioration assets	WP7	16/09/2024	18/09/2024
IKT	USFD	2	Ashwini Ausekar	Iain Naismith	Knowledge transfer "Deterioration Assets"	WP7	21/11/2024	21/11/2024
USFD	DELTARES	4	Alma Schellart	Yiqi Wu	Knowledge exchange on England and Wales Spatial Combined Sewer Overflow data, and spatial correlation analysis methods.	WP6	20/01/2025	21/01/2025
IKT	INSA	2	Marcel Goerke		Joining work of TA IndoorGRASP; Visit of INSA facility GROOF and the small JRA-research of 1x1 m; Discussion and analysing the data of the first measurements month; Planning next steps of common work.	WP8	25/02/2025	26/02/2025
AaU	UDC	1	Jesper Ellerbæk Nielsen		Learn about techniques for LSPIV measurement and IOT technology for SUDS performance	WP8	24/03/2025	25/03/2025
USFD	IKT	4	Gavin Sailor		Information exchange about DIC joint measurements, collaboration on asset deterioration	WP7	01/04/2025	04/04/2025
USFD	EAWAG	3	Yiqi Wu		Joint development and implementation of simulation models to assess the impact of pipe defects on the hydraulic performance of sewer networks. Working on joint publication.	WP7	02/04/2025	04/04/2025
USFD	IKT	3	Simon Tait		Information exchange about DIC pipe joint measurements, collaboration on asset deterioration	WP7	02/04/2025	04/04/2025
USFD	IKT	4	Gavin Sailor		Carrying out full scale DIC joint measurements in full-scale lined concrete pipe	WP7	22/04/2025	25/04/2025

The purpose of these missions varied from sharing experiences about specific techniques for UDS, to learning about experiment standardisation, knowledge exchange on measurement techniques for SuDS, collaborating on data or performing various experiments in the framework of JRA activities. A wide range of activities were carried out during the mobility visits, including laboratory and field site

visits, testing other partners novel monitoring equipment, models, and data sharing methods. A lot of discussion about ongoing and new challenges in urban drainage and discussion of ongoing as well as potential future research took place.

After completion of each mission, the assigned person wrote a report and sent it to Euronovia (task leader) detailing the scope and outcomes of his/her activities during the mission. These reports have been included in the Final report on staff development (D2.4) submitted at the end of the project (April 2025).

Task 2.3. Smart governance and public access to data (Lead EAWAG)

Task 2.3 aimed to strengthen evidence-based governance in urban drainage by identifying organisational and political barriers to effective use of monitoring data, particularly around CSOs, in the context of digitalisation and the revised UWWTD.

The central activity was a multilingual survey in seven countries (CH, DE, DK, ES, FR, NL, UK), adapted from a Swiss study, with 147 valid responses analysed. Results show that while CSO monitoring infrastructure is widely deployed, the data is mainly used for operational control and rarely for regulatory compliance or public transparency (Figure 1.3). Key barriers are institutional—such as unclear mandates and limited capacity—rather than technological.

Figure 1.3: Motivation for monitoring Combined Sewer Overflows

The study also examined attitudes toward public access to real-time data, as is showcased in <https://www.sewagemap.co.uk/> for the UK. While respondents were not uniformly opposed, they expressed concerns about misuse or political overreaction. Many utilities are hesitant to share data due to concerns about misinterpretation or political misuse, despite supporting real-time monitoring internally. The study highlights the need for clearer standards, capacity building, and co-designed platforms that align operational, regulatory, and civic interests.

Deliverable D2.5 (M32) provides actionable insights to support Co-UDlabs’ mission of fostering open, cooperative, and regulation-compliant urban drainage governance across Europe.

Summary of Deliverables

Deliverables completed:	<p>D2.2. - Final report on a framework for harmonization of Co-UDlabs sensors, technologies and data procedures. (M44) An extension of the deliverable deadline was accepted to M44 after the revision performed in RP2.</p> <p>D2.4. - Final report on staff development (M48)</p> <p>D2.5 - Report on smart governance and public access to data (M44). An extension of the deliverable deadline was accepted to M44 due to delay in adapting the survey to the reality in the countries of the partners.</p>
Deliverables submitted past due date:	None

Summary of Milestones

Milestones completed:	<p>MS04 - Adoption of common protocols for data acquisition, validation, management and sharing within RIs (M44) Technically fulfilled through D2.2. However, Milestone 4 proved more difficult than expected due to diverse setups across Co-UDlabs RIs and early leadership gaps, prompting a strategic shift from full harmonization of data acquisition to a focus on shared validation procedures and FAIR data standards that continue to develop beyond the project (see Task 2.1).</p>
Milestones submitted past due date:	<p>MS05 - Joint database on Co-UDlabs open data actions on Smart Governance is released (M41) Governance and data sensitivities prevented utility contributions to a joint database, but the recast UWWTD now mandates regular reporting on stormwater discharges, effectively fulfilling our original milestone.</p>

1.2.3 Work package 3 – Training Activities

The Co-UDlabs WP3 involves the organization and execution of training activities through the project duration. These training activities are strategically based in three main focal points:

Task 3.1. UD early-stage researcher activities and training events (Lead INSA)

This task aims at promoting training and networking activities for young researchers in the field. Activities organized in this task targets the strengthening of the European connectivity between future academic and highly specialized practitioners, disseminate techniques and improve research capacity. Two types of activities were planned in the Grant Agreement (GA) within this task:

1. **Co-UDlabs early-stage researcher seminars** targeting PhDs and early-stage researchers, aiming to enhance interaction between academics, sharing ideas and promote common experimental protocols. These seminars have a duration of 2 days and are targeting 20 participants.
2. **Open workshops and PhD courses** targeting the UD European junior research community.

In the RP3 period, CoUDlabs organized the following activities:

- The 26th EJSW – **European Junior Scientists Workshop on “Monitoring UDS and Rivers”** was held on May 26 – June 1, 2024, in St-Maurice-en-Valgaudemar, France. This workshop was

organized by INSA Lyon and Deltares (Co-UDlabs partners), in collaboration with the Sewer Systems & Processes Working Group of the IWA – IAHR Joint Committee on Urban Drainage. It focused on on-line monitoring of water quality and quantity in waste-, stormwater and rivers systems; Links between data validation and model calibration; Emerging monitoring concepts and data communication techniques; Ethics in research, publishing, presenting and sharing data. This event gathered 20 junior-scientist participants from institutions based in 10 countries (Figure 1.4). The 26th EJSW included:

- 20 oral presentations by the junior scientists (20 min presentation + 10 min for questions/answers).
- 6 lectures (45 min) by senior organisers on: i) River morphology, ii) Remote sensing and optical observations in hydraulic structures. iii) Data validation and sensor calibration, iv) 3D printing and design for manufacturing sensors, v) Transport processes and monitoring floating materials (Plastics and FOG). vi) FAIR data, publishing, and open data
- 1 workshop (1.5 h) on ethics in science and research
- 1 guided-field visit (4.5 h) to hydrogeology alpine formations by Dr. Marianna Jagercikova
- In total 8 sessions (2 in parallel) were organized (each participant could select 4 of them): (i) Geophone based riverine morphology measurements, ii) Uncertainty analysis for monitoring data, iii) Cameras/drones as a measuring tool, discharge estimates in open channel flows iv) data validation workshop, v) Sediment size distribution monitoring and structure from motion measurements, vi) sensor calibration workshop, vii) tracer experiments for discharge estimation, and viii) Stone tracking with RFID and Geophone data analysis. (<https://ejsw-2024.sciencesconf.org/>).

Figure 1.4: EJSW 2024 in St Maurice en Valgaudemar (photo: F. Clemens-Meyer)

- A **PhD course on Sewer Processes with focus on hydrogen sulfide modelling and management** was organized by AaU in Aalborg (Denmark) on October 7-11, 2024. It was worth 5 credits in the ECTS system and was open to PhD students from institutions from all over Europe. Attended by 9 students, the course focused on sewer process and sewer process modelling in relation to sulfide and methane formation and associated problems in terms of

odor sewer corrosion and greenhouse emissions. The objective of the course was to give the students insight and knowledge on the most recent advances of sewer process modelling and applications to real-world use. The course addressed the following topics:

- State-of-the-art of the sewer process modeling
- Aerobic and anaerobic organic matter transformation
- Air-water mass transfer of sewer gases
- Sewer odor and corrosion
- Mitigation methods

Figure 1.5: PhD course on sewer processes at AaU

Task 3.2. UD Industry professionals and practitioners training activities (Lead DEL)

This task concerns the organization of free training activities aimed specifically at urban drainage industry stakeholders, regulators, professionals, and other practitioners. During the reporting period there has been two additional activities carried out:

- **Applied course on Urban Drainage metrology (UDC – July 16-19, 2024).** This course targeted UD practitioners and water utilities interested in monitoring the main hydraulic and water quality parameters of sewers and drainage networks. The course was held at CITEEC -

Research & Innovation Centre on Civil Engineering laboratories, allowing the participants to join STREET and BLOCK TA infrastructures, as well as Campus-SUDS research infrastructure of UDC on pilot Sustainable Urban Drainage techniques (<https://campus-suds.udc.es/h>). With 21 participants, the course took place over 4 days:

- Day 1 – Measurement of hydraulic variables. Rainfall, flow rates, water depths and velocities were measured using different technologies (direct measurement, ultrasound, pressure, acoustic velocimetry, etc.).
- Day 2 – Measurement of pollution parameters. Automatic grab samplers and on-line probes were used to measure the most relevant variables and methods of analysis.
- Day 3 – Data collection and management. In this session different technologies to convert signals to data were presented. Additionally, the course presented how parametrize hydraulic and pollution parameters linked to dry and wet weather flows.
- Day 4 – Demo Day – Simulation of a field campaign in the infrastructure of CITEEC. A field work was simulated in the BLOCK model and SUDS pilot techniques. Measurements of all relevant parameters were made, online and by grab samples. The analyzed events were parameterized assuming that the control sections are part of a specific urban area.

The course was a great opportunity for partners and stakeholders from Spain's and Galicia's communities of academics, researchers, practitioners, utility managers, local UD and water management authorities to meet and share expertise, common issues, and innovative solutions and ideas on a very sensitive topic for public policy and sustainability action.

Figure 1.6: Applied course on Urban drainage metrology at UDC

- On the 28th of January 2025, EAWAG organized an **online workshop on FAIR monitoring data practices in urban drainage**. The event brought together researchers and industry representatives.

Alfredo Chavarría from Eawag, summarized the results from the Co-UDLabs project on aspects related to data harmonization and sharing, highlighting the valorization of data and the needs for common standards. This focused on OGC standards (Observations and Measurements, WaterML, SensorThings API) as robust frameworks for sharing hydrological and urban drainage data. The workshop was a call for expanding the Dutch GWSW ontology, —currently more focused on sharing wastewater infrastructure data —to include more elements on monitoring data. We presented here an English

translated version of the GWSW Dutch ontology. The Materials Cloud platform was also presented as a role model for domain-specific FAIR data repository.

This workshop was recorded and provided here:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0O9nm9t0FOI&feature=youtu.be>

Task 3.3. Public webinars and education activities (Lead IKT)

The aim of this task was to organize public webinars and education activities. The following webinars have been organized within RP 3:

- **Routine Data Validation (DV) in urban drainage** (January 10, 2025) organized by INSA Lyon and Graie <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=e8moNDVWQ6E>

Figure 1.7: Data Validation and UD Metrology toolbox Webinar

- **Underground infrastructure state monitoring techniques** (January 30, 2025), number of attendees: approx. 50, organized by Deltares, IKT and The University of Sheffield https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=N6RCaA_ahzQ

Techniques for monitoring underground infrastructure

Current developments

Webinar, 30 January 2025
10:00 – 14:00 CET

Figure 1.8: Monitoring techniques for underground infrastructure webinar

- **Key findings from Co-UDlabs research** and where to access them (March 11, 2025), number of attendees: 16, organized by IKT, INSA Lyon and The University of Sheffield <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=iLgXOiDsicc>

Figure 1.9: Webinar on Key findings from CoUdlabs

- **FAIR data practices** in urban drainage organized by EAWAG (May 15, 2025): <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=IPZE6Mtyo3Y>

Figure 1.10: Webinar of FAIR data practices in UD

Summary of Deliverables

Deliverables completed:	D3.3 – 3rd Report on training and educational activities (M44)
Deliverables submitted past due date:	None

Summary of Milestones

Milestones completed:	None
Milestones submitted past due date:	None

1.2.4 Work Package 4 - Communication, dissemination and exploitation of results

Work Package 4 (WP4) focused on coordinating communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities of the whole consortium. It also aimed to effectively interface with stakeholders and the urban drainage community. The objectives of WP4 were as follows:

- Create a network across Europe for urban drainage practice and research.
- Identify various routes for innovation and exploitation of project results to maximize the project's impact on a wide range of stakeholders.
- Share information about the project with stakeholders, the scientific community, and non-academic actors to engage the community with the project and facilitate knowledge transfer.
- Carry out tailored communication activities to ensure maximum visibility of the project to raise awareness about the potential of Co-UDlabs and demonstrate its impact and benefits to society.
- Ensure all data used within the project are available in accordance with the H2020 Open Access Data Policy to enhance the exploitation of results through direct access to project data.
- Implement actions to enhance coordination and synergies with relevant EU projects to exponentially widen the dissemination of project results.

WP4 was led by Euronovia, but all partners were involved in this work package and dedicated time to its activities throughout the project's lifetime.

Task 4.1. Plan for exploitation and dissemination of the project results - PEDR (Lead Euro)

During RP3, it was decided together with the coordinator and the Project Officer, that an update of the PEDR (D4.2) was not necessary since the final update on communication, dissemination and exploitation have been provided in the "Final report on the project exploitation initiatives and related impacts on innovation, including dissemination and communication activities" (D4.4, M48, April 2025). This deliverable is composed of 2 main parts:

- Communication and dissemination strategy including a description of communication tools and dissemination actions implemented during the project lifetime and a section on impact assessment and KPIs.
- Exploitation strategy including an overview of the list of Key Exploitable Results, the actions implemented to achieve the exploitation of the project results and increase the impact of the project, as well as a section on intellectual property.

All versions of the PEDR and the final report are available on Zenodo¹. The full list of KPIs and their assessment is available in Annex 1.

Task 4.2. Dissemination actions to engage the community behind the project (Lead Euro)

The third reporting period was particularly important for disseminating the Co-UDlabs results, and the consortium was very active and involved in several dissemination actions.

Events organised by Co-UDlabs project partners

Project partners organised **12 events** with different formats (including trainings, seminars, online courses, open doors) with the objectives of raising awareness of the main tools and methods developed thanks to the collaborative work of partners:

- A training on metrology with the UDMT software during the 104th ASTEE congress in Toulouse (France) on June 2-4, 2024 by INSA Lyon.

¹ Resource accessible online at: <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.7261592>.

- Two Open Days at the Centre for Technological Innovation in Construction and Civil Engineering (CITEEC) laboratories on June 19-20, 2024 by UDC, to show to early-stage researchers, school pupils, and youth how impactful research can be on water management, resilience, and sustainability in our cities and territories.
- A course for urban drainage practitioners, regulators, and utilities interested in monitoring the main hydraulic and water quality parameters of sewers and drainage networks on July 16-19, 2024 at the CITEEC laboratories of the University of A Coruña, (Spain) by UDC. Participants were able to access and discover CITEEC's STREET and BLOCK experimental facilities.
- An open-door day including guided tours, workshops and lectures to present Co-UDlabs project and the research facilities of Eawag to a large audience on September 14, 2024 in Dübendorf (Switzerland).
- The 9th edition of the EURO-SAM workshop was co-organised by the University of Sheffield and INSA Lyon and took place in Sheffield on September 17-18, 2024.
- A 2-day training course with a focus on post PhD options for urban drainage students, looking at both academic and industrial career routes, organised on September 19, 2024 by the University of Sheffield.
- An online workshop for PhD students interested in Sewer processes organised by Aalborg University on October 7-11, 2024 in Aalborg (Denmark).
- A professional training course on Uncertainty Assessment with UDMT was organised by INSA Lyon on December 2-3, 2024 at Puy en Velay (France).
- A webinar on the Routine data validation in urban drainage organised on January 10, 2025 by INSA Lyon and GRAIE.
- An online workshop on FAIR monitoring data practices in urban drainage was organised by Co-UDLabs partners and the International working group of data and models on January 28, 2025.
- A webinar on Techniques for Monitoring Underground Infrastructure was organised by University of Sheffield and IKT on January 30, 2025.
- An online workshop on the key finding from Co-UDlabs was organised on March 11, 2025 by IKT, INSA Lyon and University of Sheffield.

Co-UDlabs final Infoday

In addition to these events, a **final Infoday** was organised by the Co-UDlabs consortium **on March 18, 2025** in the premises of the Fundación Galicia-Europa in Brussels. This public event aimed at celebrating the conclusion of the project activities and its early and consolidated results. Open to the whole urban drainage and water management communities, it was attended by 37 participants (physical and online attendance). During the event, Co-UDlabs partners presented and discussed the main achievements and advances of four years of the project work. After a short overview of the project achievements, a round table was organised in which partners presented the key policy recommendations related with project research and technology transfer, as CSO monitoring in the framework of the new UWWTD or the role of Large Research Infrastructures networks for a smart and sustainable urban drainage management from the perspective of EU institutions, water utilities and administrations, industry and researchers. Lastly, further EU-wide collaborations for the consolidation

of an international network of Research Infrastructures in the field of Urban Drainage Systems were discussed. For more information: <https://co-udlabs.eu/evenements/co-udlabs-2025-infoday/>.

External events attended by Co-UDlabs project partners

The consortium participated in **12 external events** for scientific dissemination where partners presented the work done within the project with an oral or poster presentation. This included:

Four scientific conferences:

- An oral presentation by IKT at the **21st European Water Association Symposium at IFAT** on May 16, 2024 in Munich, Germany.
- Two oral presentations on “Understanding the influence of leaf litter on the water balance composition of blue-green infrastructure” (by EAWAG and UDC) and on “Improving the reproducibility and provenance of urban drainage data and models with RENKU, a platform for sustainable data science” (by EAWAG, University of Sheffield and INSA Lyon) at the **ICUD 2024** (June 9-14, 2024) in Delft, Netherlands,
- A presentation by EAWAG on “Die kontinuierliche Messung der Abwasserqualität mit Kameras – erste Erfahrungen aus Pilotversuchen” during the **Aqua Urbanica 2024** on September 22, 2024 in Graz, Austria.
- Poster presentation by UDC at the **EGU General Assembly** on April 28, 2025 in Vienna (Austria)

Three technical events:

- An oral presentation by IKT, USFD and INSA at the IKT 30th anniversary event on September 11-12, 2024 in Gelsenkirchen, Germany.
- An oral presentation by IKT, USFD at the AI, Drones, Sensors and Robots for Smart Sewers and Urban Drainage 2025 event on April 3, 2025 in Gelsenkirchen, Germany.
- A poster presentation by UDC at the redSUDS conference at the School of Civil Engineering of the University of Cantabria on April 7-8, 2025 - Santander, Spain. The presentation showcased the results of research conducted between the Universidade da Coruña and the institutes IKT (Germany) and EAWAG (Switzerland) to analyze the aging of certain sustainable drainage systems such as green roofs and porous pavements.

Two exhibition booths

- Co-UDlabs booth organized at ICUD 2024 on June 9-14, 2024 in Delft, Netherlands.
- Joint exhibition space with the European project D4runoff at the redSUDS conference at the School of Civil Engineering of the University of Cantabria on April 7-8, 2025 in Santander, Spain.

Three Open Science / popularization events:

- Participation of UDC in the EU Green Week 2024 on 19-20 June 2024 with a open-door event of its research infrastructures.
- Open Lab Day organized by EAWAG and Empa on 14 September 2024 in Dübendorf, Switzerland.

- Participation of UDC in the G-NIGHT 2024 – Noite Europea das Persoas Investigadoras 2024 taking place in A Coruña, Spain on 27 September 2024.

Scientific publications

During RP3, partners have published 18 scientific publications (5 journal articles and 13 conference papers), as well as 2 technical articles:

Five Journal articles:

- [“Flow rate influence on sediment depth estimation in sewers using temperature sensors”](#), Manuel Regueiro-Picallo, Alma Schellart, Henriette Jensen, Jeroen Langeveld, Maria Viklander and Lian Lundy, Water Science and Technology (May 2024)
- [“Measuring heat transfer processes in gully pots for real-time estimation of accumulated sediment depths”](#), M. Regueiro-Picallo, A. Moreno-Rodenas, F. Clemens-Meyer, Environmental Science Water Research & Technology (July 2024)
- [“Concepts and evolution of urban hydrology”](#), Tim D. Fletcher, Matthew J. Burns, Kathryn L. Russell, Perrine Hamel, Sophie Duchesne, Frédéric Cherqui & Allison H. Roy, Nature Reviews Earth & Environment (October 2024)
- [“Understanding sediment wash-off in road drainage systems under intense rainfall and high sediment masses: Insights from a large-scale modeling facility”](#), CA Zafra-Mejía, D Hernández-Medina, J Suárez, J Naves, J Anta, Science of the Total Environment (December 2024)
- [“Large-scale clogging experiments assessing the hydraulic performance of porous asphalt during their service life”](#), Angélica Vanessa Goya-Heredia, Juan Naves, Joaquín Suárez, Jose Anta, Blue-Green Systems (January 2025)

Thirteen conference papers:

- [“Co-UDlabs. Fomentando la innovación en los sistemas de drenaje urbano”](#), Anta, J; Puertas, J; Cea, L; Suárez, J; Naves, J; Regueiro-Picallo, M; Pimiento, M.A; Ciambra, A., Proceedings of the XXXVII CONGRESO. Asociación Española de Abastecimientos de Agua y Saneamiento (AEAS 2024)
- [“Understanding the influence of leaf litter on the water balance composition of blue-green infrastructure”](#), Prabhat Joshi & Joao Leitao & Jose Anta & Juan Naves, Proceedings of the ICUD conference 2024
- [“Laboratory-scale analysis of road-deposited sediment wash-off: Runoff scenarios under high sediment load”](#), Joaquín Suarez & Jose Anta & Juan Naves, Proceedings of the ICUD conference 2024
- [“Evaluation of new flow and water quality monitoring equipment in sewers under realistic flow conditions”](#), Daniel Carreres & Jose Anta & Juan Naves, Proceedings of the ICUD conference 2024
- [“Monitoring sediment build-up in gully pots using temperature-based systems”](#), M. Regueiro-Picallo, L. Fuchs, J. Rieckermann, A. Moreno-Rodenas, F. Clemens-Meyer, Proceedings of the ICUD conference 2024

- [“Flow rate influence on sediment depth estimation using temperature sensors”](#), M. Regueiro-Picallo, A. Schellart, H. Jensen, J. Langeveld, M. Viklander, L. Lundy, Proceedings of the ICUD conference 2024
- [“Improving the reproducibility and provenance of urban drainage data and models with RENKU, a platform for sustainable data science”](#), A. Chavarría, S. Tait, M. Lepot, J.-L. Bertrand-Krajewski, J. P. Leitão, J. Rieckermann, Proceedings of the ICUD conference 2024
- [“The role of open data in regulating Combined Sewer Overflows”](#), A. Schellart, L. Sharp, J.-L. Bertrand-Krajewski, J. Rieckermann, Jose Anta, Frank Blumensaat, Francois Clemens, Ulrich Dittmer, Isabel Douterelo, Günter Gruber, Henriette Jensen, James Shucksmith, Simon Tait, Boud Verbeiren, Luca Vezzaro, Proceedings of the ICUD conference 2024
- [“Spatial analysis of the combined sewer overflow durations in England and Wales”](#), C. S. de Vito, A. M. Moreno-Rodenas, A. Schellart, J. Shucksmith & Z. Kapelan, Proceedings of the ICUD conference 2024
- [“Building the urban drainage community: European stakeholders’ visions and needs for Urban Drainage Systems”](#), Tondera, K., Legge, A., Brelot, E., Proceedings of the ICUD conference 2024
- [“European stakeholders’ visions and needs for the role of Nature-based Solutions for stormwater treatment in future urban drainage systems”](#), Tondera, K., Legge, A., Brelot, E., Proceedings of the ICWS
- “Influence of grate geometry on hydraulic energy losses in a surcharged manhole under flood conditions”, Brazier, Shucksmith, Nichols, Proceedings of the ICUD conference 2024
- [“Análisis de la movilización de contaminación difusa de carreteras en la Plataforma Científica para Ensayos de Escorrentía Urbana del CITEEC-UDC”](#), Joaquín Suarez & Jose Anta & Juan Naves, Proceedings of XV Congreso Español De Tratamiento De Aguas

Two technical articles:

- [“Co-UDlabs: promoviendo la investigación e innovación en los sistemas de drenaje urbano”](#), Anta Álvarez, Jose; Puertas Agudo, Jerónimo; Cea Gómez, Luís; Suárez López, Joaquín; Naves García-Rendueles, Juan; Regueiro Picallo, Manuel; Pimiento Avella, María Alejandra; Ciambra, Andrea, TECNOAQUA (October 2024)
- [“Comment optimiser les infrastructures de recherche au niveau européen”](#), by GRAIE in Astee TSM, the leading technical journal for water and waste professionals in France (March 2025).

All open access Co-UDlabs scientific publications and deliverables are available for download in the dedicated pages of the Co-UDlabs website², as well as on the project community on Zenodo³.

In addition to the publications above, there are currently **several other publications which are either in preparation or under review** and which are planned to be published in the upcoming weeks/month (list available in D4.4).

² Online at this link: <https://co-udlabs.eu/dissemination/deliverables/>.

³ Available online at: <https://zenodo.org/communities/coudlabs/>.

Task 4.3. Exploitation plan of the project results (Lead Euronovia)

The exploitation strategy outlined in the Grant Agreement has been further developed in RP3 and outlined in the “Final report on the project exploitation initiatives and related impacts on innovation, including dissemination and communication activities” (D4.4) submitted at M48.

During RP3 partners continued the work started at the exploitation seminar organised within the Horizon Results Booster (HRB) in February 2024 (RP2) and developed Lean Canvas for each of the 10 KERs identified, following the recommendations of the experts of the HRB. The Lean Canvas is an adaptation of Business Model Canvas, and it is considered to be the most suited for R&D projects. Therefore, in the final year of the project Euronovia coordinated the work on exploitation by guiding partners to fill a Lean Canvas for each KER (including the 3 KERs analysed by the Booster) with the objective of further developing the characterization of their KERs, preparing the materials to be discussed at consortium meetings and fine-tuning and developing the exploitation strategy. After several interactions among partners and Euronovia, Lean Canvas have been developed for the 10 Co-UDlabs KERs. They are available in D4.4. Some of them will be selected to be uploaded on the Horizon Results Platform to maximize their visibility and valorise them among relevant stakeholders.

Task 4.4. Communication activities (Lead Euronovia)

Several communication actions have been realised by Co-UDlabs partners during this third reporting period:

- Co-UDlabs’ **LinkedIn and Twitter accounts**,⁴ as well as the project’s [website](#) are being constantly updated with news, events announcements and new documents. At M48, the project LinkedIn group hits 651 followers and the Twitter account has 217 followers. Concerning the website, during RP3 32 news have been published, and we have recorded 443 visits on average each month. More information on the impact of the website and social media channels can be found in Deliverable D4.4.
- **A press release** was published by UDC in their website to present the outputs of the final event of the project: udc.es/es/novas/A-Universidade-da-Coruna-presenta-en-Bruxelas-os-resultados-do-proxecto-europeo-Co-UDlabs-sobre-os-sistemas-de-drenaxe-urbana/. A **final press release** was published at the end of April 2025 to announce the end of the project, its main achievements and its legacy. It was distributed through the project website, social media, newsletter and by partners to their contact networks. It is available for download in the project website: <https://co-udlabs.eu/dissemination/communication-material/>.
- **A final media press kit** was prepared at M46 to showcase the main achievements of the project. The final media press kit is available on the project website (https://co-udlabs.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/03/CoUDlabs_PressKit_WEB.pdf) and has been distributed during the Co-UDlabs final event and on social media.
- **Three newsletters were designed** in June 2024, December 2024 and April 2025 and sent out to the project mailing list and disseminated through social media and the project partners network to maximise its dissemination⁵. Some additional mailing campaigns were sent out to

⁴ Co-UDlabs is on LinkedIn at this link: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/74284316/>, and on Twitter at this link: <https://twitter.com/CoUDlabs>.

⁵ All newsletters are available on the Co-UDlabs website: <https://coudlabs.eu/dissemination/newsletter/>.

the newsletter subscribers to promote specific activities (UDRAIN, final infoday). They have been sent to 546 contacts.

- **One article** about Co-UDlabs was **published in the newsletter of the IAHR/IWA joint committee on urban drainage (JCUD)** in March 2025 (https://jcu.org/wp-content/uploads/2025/03/2025_jcu_newsletter_final.pdf). An article on the end of Co-UDlabs was also published in the EWA newsletter in February 2025 ([EWA Newsletter April - Issue 02/2025](#)).
- A **Youtube channel** was established back in M12 as a dynamic repository of all project videos⁶. At M48 the YouTube channel contains 26 videos (including recordings of project webinars, Deltares' courses, the motion-design video, and several interviews with partners from the consortium), with more than 1,600 views (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KjgBKppROVk>).
- Several **news articles** were published by project partners on their institutional websites to give updates on the different activities taking place within the project (events, transnational access calls, etc.) and **four articles** were published in the Galician regional press (21Noticias and El Ideal Gallego) by the project coordinator.
- In terms of **synergies with other projects**, Co-UDlabs has interacted with a few different EU-funded projects (e.g., D4runoff, Water4All) and National projects (SATURNO, DigitalRain, SUDSlong) for example through joint exhibition spaces or by sharing content and reposting valuable information and activities.

Task 4.5. Data management plan (Lead: Euronovia)

During RP3, the DMP was updated at M48 (April 2025), thus including the latest project datasets. All versions of the DMP are available on the project's Zenodo repository⁷. By M48, 70 datasets have been produced by the Co-UDlabs project in the framework of the NA (40), JRA (15) and TA (15) activities.

Datasets related to Networking Activities include lists of participants in Co-UDlabs initiatives and other relevant participation and diffusion data, as well as the updated database of Co-UDlabs stakeholders. Accordingly, these are being considered as confidential, and access has been limited to the consortium. Datasets related to Joint Research Activities are openly available on Zenodo⁸. Regarding Co-UDlabs Transnational Access, all the 31 projects have been completed, and 15 open datasets have been uploaded to Zenodo (4 are restricted to an embargo which ends 2 years after the access ended as stated in the User Facility Agreement to allow scientific publications.). The datasets of other TNA projects are being processed (USFD 04-BURIED-Li, USFD06-BURIED-Joksimovic, USFD 07-RTCRIG-Vanderwerf, UDC-04-BLOCK-Franca, UDC-05-BLOCK-Coupe, UDC-06-STREET-Linnemann and UDC-07-STREET-Lutze) so more datasets will be produced after the end of the project.

⁶ The channel can be accessed online at: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KjgBKppROVk>.

⁷ Online at: <https://zenodo.org/records/11091173>.

⁸ See: <https://zenodo.org/communities/coudlabs>.

Summary of Deliverables

Deliverables completed:	D4.1 – Data Management Plan (M6) An updated version of this document was submitted at M48. D4.4 Final report on the project exploitation initiatives and related impacts on innovation, including dissemination and communication activities (M48)
Deliverables submitted past due date:	None

Summary of Milestones

Milestones completed:	None
Milestones submitted past due date:	None

1.2.5 Work Package 5 - Management of the TA

WP5 established the regulatory and administrative framework for transnational access, enabling external user groups to access Co-UDlabs' research infrastructure. During RP3, these tasks included organization and execution of 2nd and 3rd Calls for TA proposals. Tasks 1 and 2 were completed during the previous reporting periods, with only Task 3 being undertaken in the current period.

Task 5.3. Organisation of the TA access period (Lead UDC)

The facility provider and the user group had agreed to a User Facility Agreement (UFA) before the TA began. The UFA included the dates of the TA, the responsibilities and duties of both the user group and the facility provider, covered expenses, and applicable laws. Each UFA also included a User Project Plan (UPP), which detailed the agreed experimental setup, procedures, test program, access plan, visitor dates, and Data Management Plan (DMP).

Summary of Deliverables

Deliverables completed:	None
Deliverables submitted past due date:	None

Summary of Milestones

Milestones completed:	None
Milestones submitted past due date:	None

1.2.6 Work Package 6 - JRA 1. Smart sensing and monitoring in urban drainage

The Joint Research Activity "Smart sensing and monitoring in urban drainage" was developed in the framework of WP6. The objectives of this WP were to: i) foster a paradigm shift in UDS management, transitioning from current inefficient approaches towards a digitised, informed, shared, evidence-based decision process based on truly smart monitoring; ii) identify and evaluate new sensors and technologies for hydrological and hydraulic variables, pollutant load monitoring and UD underground asset inspection; iii) define and evaluate new methods and tools to improve evidence base for reliable and validated urban drainage monitoring data; and iv) define and evaluate new

methods to analyse and interpret urban drainage space and distributed data. WP6 is led by INSA and most of the TA facility providers are involved in their development (UDC, USFD, DEL, EAWAG).

Task 6.1. Evaluation of sensor and new data sources for hydraulics, pollutant load monitoring and asset inspection (Lead EAWAG)

Task 6.1 identified and tested emerging sensor technologies to address key monitoring challenges in UDS, such as pollutant detection, asset condition assessment, and operational robustness in harsh wastewater environments. Eight technologies were evaluated through a two-phase testing approach in lab, pilot, and full-scale UDS settings, emphasizing scientific novelty, readiness, and utility for wider adoption by utilities and research infrastructures (RIs).

Evaluation and Testing Approach

Technologies were assessed using a standardized strategy focusing on reproducibility and site-independent robustness. Target parameters included ammonium, PAHs, suspended solids, and flow. Data validation employed the UDMT, ensuring quality checks like range and uncertainty analysis. Operational metrics—calibration frequency, maintenance effort, and data completeness—were consistently documented. Of the eight selected sensors, six proceeded to full-scale testing, with four evaluated at multiple sites to assess transferability.

Technical Highlights

A standout result came from the **ISA UV-Vis spectrophotometric sensor** by Go-Systemelektronik. Though ammonium lacks direct UV-vis absorbance, multivariate regression on full spectra allowed accurate NH_4^+ predictions (RMSE < 5.5 mg/L) at Eawag and UDC (Figure 1.11). Separate calibrations for dry/wet weather improved performance, suggesting a promising low-maintenance alternative to traditional ammonium probes.

The **Low-Power Inductive Conductivity Monitor (LPICM)**, developed by Eawag and OST, reliably tracked wastewater dilution during wet weather in Swiss networks. While its ammonium predictions showed limited dry-weather accuracy ($R^2 \sim 0.5$), it excelled in detecting rain-induced dilution and resisted fouling due to a protective shield—ideal for remote or distributed applications.

A **hyperspectral imaging system (MV.X, Headwall)** showed strong turbidity prediction ($R^2 > 0.89$, RMSE \approx 13 NTU) across lab and flume setups. It demonstrated robustness under varied wastewater conditions and preliminary ability to track ammonium trends. Its non-contact nature holds promise for in-sewer deployment, supporting future low-cost variants like the PollutionKeeper prototype.

Figure 1.11: Results of the high-resolution ammonium monitoring with the ISA UV-Vis spectrophotometric sensor. a) Scatter plot for actual vs predicted NH4-N concentration at Eawag and b) at UDC, and c) NH4-N equivalents for 13/08/2023 show the expected daily trends and good agreement with lab measurements (crosses).

Other technologies included the **DischargeKeeper**, a video-based system for flow monitoring. It performed well under medium/high flows, providing level and surface velocity data within 10% of ultrasonic references. However, it struggled in low-light/low-flow conditions, limiting use cases. In contrast, a fluorescence-based **Trios EnviroFlu-HC sensor for PAHs** proved ineffective due to turbidity interference and overestimated concentrations, rendering it unsuitable for UDS applications.

Task 6.2. Smart methods and tools to improve the evidence base for reliable and validated monitoring data (Lead INSA)

During the reporting period M37-M48, the last updated version UDMT 2025a was produced and released, for both the webapp and the stand-alone exe versions, minor bugs and typos on the user interface were corrected, revision of and few changes in the entire Matlab codes were done. Based on feedback from all Co-UDlabs webinars and training courses held since M37, and from an additional final panel of five testers at INSA Lyon during M48, the user manual was also revised and updated, in parallel with the revision of the source code, with numerous comments, details and explanations added.

In M48, all the revised and updated material related to the UDMT was uploaded on Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/records/15195641>), including the .exe versions, all Matlab source codes, the user manual and all the .csv files of the detailed examples provided in the user manual allowing the user to use them for self-training.

Figure 1.12: Application of the UDMT Uncertainty Assessment functions for the evaluation of the uncertainty in a river discharge calculation based on 90 values of flow velocities measured with an ultrasonic velocimeter through the river wet section. Top: original raw data from INGE43; bottom: UDMT output.

In the period M37-M48, dissemination and communication about the UDMT continued: i) on June 27, 2024 during the H2O'Lyon Eco-Campus PhD students Summer School on Infiltration Processes, ii) on December 2-3, 2024 in Le Puy-en-Velay, France, during a professional training course for the INGE43 sewer and river monitoring teams (with new applications for flow measurements in rivers, see Figure 1.12), and iii) on January 10, 2025, during the Co-UDlabs webinar on data validation, with new examples of applications derived from T6.1 data sets. In addition, a UDMT training course session was held on June 4, 2025 during the ASTEE Annual Congress in Toulouse, France (16 participants). Finally, a paper on UDMT has been submitted on May 5, 2025 for publication in *Water Practice and Technology*.

Task 6.3. Space distributed monitoring and data interpretation (Lead USFD)

The aim of this task was to explore the information that can be gained from space-distributed monitoring data in both centralised and decentralised urban drainage systems, and the potential impact such datasets can have on regulatory policy and water utility behaviour.

A comparison of CSO related data collection and regulation between 10 European countries and regions has shown that this has led to a plethora of local regulations and guidelines around managing CSO performance. Assessing CSO compliance using monitored data does not happen in most countries/regions. The local regulations can be broadly divided into two types, emission based (limiting CSO spill frequency or spill pollutant load) and receiving water impact based (limiting concentration-duration-frequency of indicator pollutants in rivers). This, however, leads to a conundrum as data for simple versions of emission-based regulation such as spill frequency is relatively easy to collect but does not inform about the receiving water quality, whereas harm caused by CSO spills on the receiving water is so complex to monitor and simulate that this process is opaque and regulation becomes practically almost non-enforceable. This also means we lack oversight data concerning CSO compliance and impact on receiving waters.

The establishment of the open CSO spill event duration monitoring database in England and Wales highlighted larger than expected amounts of spills occurring, and the considerable investment needed to upgrade and future-proof decaying drainage systems. The recast UWWTD calls for more open performance data. Even simple but widespread (open) data can be very beneficial, for example warning about CSO spills occurring during dry weather.

Figure 1.13 Result from Self-Organising Map analysis of total annual CSO spill count and duration per wastewater catchment (both those that could be linked to a WWTW and those that could not), for details of the analysis and parameters included, please refer to Co-UDlabs Deliverable D6.4.

Detailed analysis of the open annual CSO spill frequency and duration database from England and Wales has indicated the difficulty of trying to derive relationships between physical and socio-economical parameters and CSO spill durations. Figure 1.13 shows a result from Self-Organising Map analysis of total annual CSO spill count and duration per wastewater catchment in England for 2022.

There is one panel per parameter investigated, and clusters of the same colour and location would indicate a positive correlation. There are no clearly pronounced correlations between CSO spill count/duration and potential explanatory parameters. This would indicate that there are likely to be other factors that considerably contribute to the amount of CSO spills, for example local network bottlenecks or blockages, or general lack of capacity in the sewer system, which could not be captured by this type of analysis.

The research from Task 6.3, together with results from Task 2.3, has fed into a Co-UDlabs response to the ECs consultation on the Water Resilience and Water Efficiency interlinked initiative: https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/better-regulation/have-your-say/initiatives/14490-Water-Efficiency-First-guiding-principles/F3524248_en as well as the Co-UDlabs policy brief on addressing CSO spills <https://zenodo.org/records/15081107>; a summary of findings will also be presented at the upcoming EWA/NWA spring conference <https://www.tekna.no/en/events/challenges-and-opportunities-with-the-new-eu-urban-wastewater-directive-48480/>.

A Manuscript on ‘The role of open data in regulating Combined Sewer Overflows’ has received minor corrections following review for the *Water Science and Technology* ICUD special issue and will be resubmitted end of June 2025. The spatial analysis of CSO EDM data from England and Wales is prepared for publication and aimed at submission in July 2025.

Summary of Deliverables

Deliverables completed:	D6.2. Report on emerging monitoring technologies for urban drainage systems Initially planned M36, delivered on M44 due to delays in sensors testing. An updated version has been made on M48 (correction of some typos, completion of section 3.8 which was not terminated in M44), available from Zenodo: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15699587
	D6.3 - UDMT – Urban Drainage Metrology Toolbox, for sensor calibration, data validation and uncertainty assessment. First version delivered on M24, revised version delivered on M32, available from Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/records/14160619 . Final version released as UDMT User Manual v 2025a on M48, available from Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/records/15195641 .
	D6.4. Report on space distributed monitoring and data interpretation (M41)
Deliverables submitted past due date:	None

Summary of Milestones

Milestones completed:	No milestone planned during this period
Milestones submitted past due date:	None

1.2.7 Work Package 7 - JRA 2. Evaluation of asset deterioration in urban drainage systems

The overall aim of WP7 was to develop techniques to both evaluate asset deterioration and also the impact of such deterioration on system performance such as flood risk, groundwater pollution and the operation of sewer overflows into receiving waters. In this reporting period work focussed on the final two tasks.

Task 7.2. Developing failure scenarios for defects (Lead IKT)

In RP3 one main focus was to complete a series of tests at both IKT and UFSD and then interpret and report on the results. In-pipe joint defects were identified in Task 7.1. as one of the most common defects found in sewer and stormwater drainage systems. And further literature revealed the large impact of leaking joints, e.g. studies in the UK have estimated that 40-50% of the flow entering wastewater treatment works (WWTW) in at least 25% of UK sewer catchments is from unintended infiltration via leaky joints. This indicated that defective pipe joints/connections can have a significant impact on the performance of many sewer and drainage systems. This information resulted in the IKT/UFSD team deciding to study the mechanics of infiltration/exfiltration caused by pipe joint movement.

USFD and IKT researchers decided to investigate the levels of infiltration/exfiltration possible from displaced joints (measured at full-scale) and if the level of joint displacement would be replicated in a buried pipe under realistic loading. As the investigation progressed, an instrumentation need was identified to measure the actual internal displacement and rotation within a joint that had been loaded so that the tests at both IKT and USFD could be compared. A low-cost, image-based system able to measure internal displacement and deformation within full-scale pipe sections, focusing on the articulation between pipe joints was developed. A custom system was built by UFSD using four synchronized 1MP monochrome cameras mounted on a frame placed on a wheeled trolley for insertion into 300 mm diameter pipes. The system included a Raspberry Pi 4B, synchronized global shutters, an illumination source, and wireless remote access. Python scripts were developed for calibration, image capture, and preprocessing. Proper lighting and calibration were critical to ensure measurement data quality.

Figure 1.14 Prototype of four camera low cost in-pipe measurement system, with central illumination system, placed in pipe with illumination in use for image capture

The complementary laboratory testing at IKT and at the University of Sheffield investigated the effects of pipe joint displacement and damage on exfiltration and infiltration in buried and non-buried sewer pipes. Large-scale tests at the USFD focused on concrete pipes (300 mm diameter) buried in compacted bedding material and subjected to dynamic surface loads simulating heavy traffic. The goal was to determine at what levels of joint damage or angular displacement measurable leakage (exfiltration) occurs, helping to define critical thresholds relevant for maintenance and standard compliance (e.g., BS EN 1610:2015-12).

Figure 1.15 Automated loading system applying 110 kN cyclic load above a buried pipe joint – exfiltration was measured using a volume-based method over the pipe length

Complementary tests were conducted at IKT, where several full-scale pipe systems made of PVC, concrete, and clay were examined without burial. The pipe joints were systematically damaged and articulated to analyse their leakage behaviour under varying conditions such as water level, joint displacement, and angle. These tests quantified how different pipe wall materials and sealing systems influenced the leakage rates. The Digital Image Correlation (DIC) system developed at USFD (Figure 1.14) was used at IKT to measure internal wall deformations at the pipe joints. This optical system helped to relate joint movement to observed leakage. It also ensured comparability between USFD and IKT tests. The IKT test rig consisted of two pipes—one fixed, one tiltable—allowing precise control of joint angles (Figure 1.16) - different pipe materials and levels of seal damage were used. The combined experimental program provides practical insights into how joint condition, pipe material, and articulation affect leakage, supporting better risk assessment and maintenance planning for sewer infrastructure.

Concrete and vitrified clay pipes showed comparable exfiltration behaviour, in contrast to the PVC pipes. The difference in behaviour can be explained by the collected DIC data. These clearly show a different mechanical behaviour. In the concrete and clay pipes, the articulation angle measured externally is close to the articulation angle measured internally. This shows that the stiff pipe sections continue to deform the joint seals as they are articulated to higher angles. This corresponds with higher exfiltration rates. The size of the rates is different for the concrete and clay pipes, but the trend and the mechanism are similar. It is clear from the PVC pipe DIC measurements that as the external articulation angle exceeded 2°, that the internal DIC measurements indicated that the pipe itself started to deform and the joint geometry remained similar. As the pipe deformed the exfiltration rate reduced to negligible values. The new low-cost DIC measurement system, developed in Co-UDLabs, has been able to measure joint and local pipe deformation, this explained the different pattern of observation in the stiff clay/clay pipes compared to the more flexible PVC pipes. A publication is in preparation to disseminate these findings.

Figure 1.16 Test setup and equipment at IKT used to measure the external angle of articulation

Furthermore, it should be noted that in the IKT tests exfiltration quantities in the experiments were always measured without the surrounding soil, so a “free” outflow” condition into the atmosphere was created. In Sheffield tests, exfiltration occurred with an additional influencing factor of the “bedding” material surrounding the with its potential sealing effect. The results indicated that the bedding material did not significantly impact the exfiltration from pipe joints. Demonstrating that in-air exfiltration tests could be used to estimate exfiltration rates from articulated pipes and also joints with damaged seals.

The most up-to-date version of the 4 camera DIC system was used at IKT to measure in detail the deformation of a liner installed within a 600 mm to assess the quality of the adherence between the liner and the pipe inner wall. This is the first time that such spatial measurements have been obtained at such scale.

Figure 1.17 Test setup for 600mm dia lined pipes, with the UFSD 4 camera DIC system being used to measure liner defects.

Task 7.3. Application of proposed defect deterioration models to real systems (Lead USFD)

Significant effort was expended in this task in Reporting Period 3. The aim of this task was to develop software able to simulate the impact of a range and number of defects within a sewer network. In RP2 a number of sewer network models had been obtained from different water utilities. These were assessed and two were converted into the SWMM model format as this allowed us to link

up the models to MATLAB to allow automated manipulation of the asset geometry within the models to assess the impact of different defects. First Matlab defect/deterioration code was written and verified so that a range of defects could be added anywhere within a network model and then the models run with different rainfall time series and the results could be automatically processed and then studied. This process is shown in the flow chart (Figure 1.1.18)

Figure 1.18 Flow chart outlining simulation process to test individual defects at a network scale

An initial case study was carried out using the smaller of the two models (~ 200 pipes). In the initial case study blockages formed on the invert of the pipe were examined. Several rainfall time series was used to estimate the impact on flood severity. This work clearly showed that in-pipe blockages had a significant impact on local flood severity. It also showed that for some locations an in-pipe blockage at that location could impact on system performance at remote locations, but these were small.

In the second case study both types of the defects described above were used – invert blockage and soffit blockage. The second case study area was a much larger network. Because of the computational load in the second case study the simulations were carried out using a single measured rainfall event. The rainfall intensity of this event was scaled to understand the impact of individual defects for events with different rainfall volumes and to understand the impact on system performance of differently sized defects. The measure of system performance used was the overall flood volume leaving the system through manholes.

The results showed that in-pipe defects do impact on the flood risk performance of networks. Different types of blockages create different impacts. There is some evidence that blockages can create flooding impacts remote from their location (see Figure 1.19).

Figure 1..19 Additional flooding caused by siltation that fills up 20% of the pipe diameter with rainfall event 3 (The darker the colour of the pipes (deeper orange) means higher flooded volumes are caused by a defect in the pipe)

By further analysis it is possible to identify the blockages in particular pipes that cause the highest increase in overall flood risk. It is also possible to link blockages with flood locations. These locations may not be close by. Some unexpected behaviour was observed, in which flow restrictions (blockages) in some parts of the network improved flooding performance in other locations. This tool can therefore be used by water utilities to better understand how the performance of their network changes as individual assets get block (degrade) and so help to better focus maintenance.

A similar analysis was also carried out for increases in overflow volume that could be linked to blockages in individual pipes. This indicated that increases and decreases of around 90% in overflow volume could be caused by in-pipe defects (Table 1.3). Again, the tool can help water utilities to identify those pipes in which maintenance can be most effective in reducing overflow volume. Reducing spill volume via effective maintenance can help with meeting the re-cast UWWTD, as it focusses on load emitted from overflows. These results are incorporated in a manuscript that is to be submitted to the Urban Water journal.

Table 1.3 Summary of proportion of pipes defect caused increase/decrease in overflow

	CSO 1			CSO 2			CSO 3			CSO 4		CSO 5	CSO 7		CSO 8		CSO 9
	Rainfall Event 1	Rainfall Event 2	Rainfall Event 3	Rainfall Event 1	Rainfall Event 2	Rainfall Event 3	Rainfall Event 1	Rainfall Event 2	Rainfall Event 3			Rainfall Event 1	Rainfall Event 2	Rainfall Event 3			
Decrease	58%	0%	0%	0%	44%	92%	24%	83%	26%	98%	63%	8%	36%	75%			
No Change	0%	100%	100%	100%	9%	0%	1%	0%	0%	0%	9%	0%	1%	0%			
Increase	42%	0%	0%	0%	47%	8%	75%	17%	74%	2%	27%	92%	63%	25%			

Summary of Deliverables

Deliverables completed:	<p>D7.4 - Report on the development of mechanistic models to simulate the temporal deterioration of drainage assets (M40).</p> <p>This deliverable was postponed to M40 from M36 with the approval of the Project Advisor</p> <p>D7.5- Report on Sewer System Hydraulic Performance in Networks with Defects and Deteriorating Assets (M44)</p>
Deliverables submitted past due date:	None

Summary of Milestones

Milestones completed:	None
Milestones submitted past due date:	None

1.2.8 Work Package 8 - JRA 3. Improving resilience and sustainability in urban drainage solutions

The Joint Research Activity titled “Improving Resilience and Sustainability in Urban Drainage Solutions” is carried out under the framework of Work Package 8 (WP8). This work package aims to (i) establish a consensus on methodologies required to generate high-resolution data for assessing the performance of urban drainage technologies; (ii) demonstrate how the resilience to urban flooding and the capacity for pollutant transport and retention of these technologies can be effectively evaluated; and (iii) propose and validate a methodology for assessing the sustainability of both existing and emerging urban drainage solutions.

WP8 is coordinated by the UDC, with active participation from all TA facility providers: USFD, Deltares, EAWAG, IKT, INSA Lyon, and AAU. The main activities developed during RP3 are as follows.

Task 8.1. Development of Consensus on Measurement of Hydraulic and Water Quality Performance of Urban Drainage technologies (Lead UDC)

Laboratory work and data analysis were completed during RP2, RP3 has focused on the preparation and submission of scientific publications based on those results. The UDC is leading a paper on the comparative analysis of topographic survey methods using imaging technologies, which is expected to be submitted after the summer. Deltares, with contributions from UDC, USFD, EAWAG, IKT, and INSA, is finalizing the review paper on optical imaging for process monitoring in urban drainage, scheduled for submission in July. In addition, UDC and IKT are collaborating on a joint publication addressing standard methods for evaluating the long-term performance of permeable pavements, also planned for submission later this year. In regards to the work of transport and retention of macroplastic elements in urban gully pot structures, another journal paper is in preparation based on the report and dataset available in Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/records/15308520>).

Task 8.2. Quantifying the resilience of urban drainage infrastructure (Lead USFD)

This task involved experimental studies of key components of UDS and their performance under pressure, specifically high flow/flooding events as well as understanding the impacts of varying

maintenance regimes. The first study conducted at USFD considered the transport of sediments through traditional UDS during urban flood events, specifically considering the transport of sewer sediments from pipe networks to surface flows during sewer surcharge events. This is of relevance to the understanding of the public health risks posed by urban floods, as sediments are highly likely to contain harmful pathogenetic or chemical substances. The work presented new experimental dataset of significant value for model validation and risk evaluation, as well as presenting new evidence concerning the significance of manhole lids/grates on retaining sewer sediments within pipe networks during flood/surcharge events (details of the experimental arrangement are provided in Figure 1.20).

Figure 1.20 *Experimental apparatus at USFD for the study of sediment exchange to urban surfaces in UDS during floods. a) injection system, b) accumulation pattern on model surface, c) manhole and turbidity sensors for monitoring concentration and sediment loads.*

Ultimately this information will assist UDS operators in post flood recovery operations via a better understanding of urban areas and under what flow conditions which there may be of higher risk of negative health outcomes from urban flood inundations.

The second study conducted at UDC by researchers from EAWAG considered the hydrological performance of poorly maintained Blue Green Infrastructure. The study provided specific performance changes relative to a reference case under varying degrees of accumulation of both sand and leaf litter, providing specific information on how reduced maintenance and cleaning of BGI can affect the hydrological performance and hence flood risk (see Figure 1.21).

Taken together these studies provide valuable new insights into the performance of UDS infrastructure under high flow events. This will enable us to provide increased confidence in modelling tools for risk evaluation and the targeting of public investment and post flood recovery resources, as well as provide more specific recommendations regarding UDS maintenance regimes to reduce societal risks of heavy rainfall events.

Figure 1.21. BGI Sand accumulation experiment conducted at EAWAG at four stages of accumulation (a-d)

Task 8.3. Improving the sustainability of urban drainage infrastructure (Lead INSA)

The goal of Task 8.3 was to demonstrate and propose a methodology for the evaluation of the sustainability of new and emerging urban drainage technologies. During PR3 Sub-Task 8.3.2 designer soils for Sustainable Urban Drainage Systems was completed with the deliverable D8.5.

The key findings gathered in the D8.5 include the evaluation of filtration and retention capacities of a new engineered soil developed by the German company HAURATON. The performance of Hauraton's substrate was compared to that of natural soil. Results showed that the new substrate demonstrated good retention capacity for certain trace metals such as cadmium, arsenic, and copper, along with effective DOC removal. However, its performance varied for other metals. These results were obtained under extreme and uncontrolled conditions—including stormwater derived from a settling basin heavily loaded with fine particles. In addition, the absence of vegetation in the Hauraton's reservoir, and a specific geometry differing from Hauraton's standard design likely limited performance and contributed to rapid clogging.

In Sub-Task 8.3.2, progress was also made in infiltration modeling through the development of a double permeability approach based on modified Green-Ampt equations. This method builds on previous work by Asry et al. (2023), who proposed three physically-based infiltration models. The improved model was tested under three initial saturation scenarios, dry, medium, and wet and validated against the Hydrus numerical model. Results showed that the approach accurately captured infiltration behavior, particularly under dry and medium initial moisture conditions. Further validation was conducted by inverting the model against data from six large-ring infiltration experiments. The calibrated model, which relies on just two parameters, hydraulic conductivity in the matrix and macropores proved effective in representing the infiltration process, including complex dynamics such as the position of the wetting front and the influence of preferential flow.

As part of the collaborative work in this sub-task, AAU developed a preliminary version of a one-dimensional, user-friendly tool called LAZE (Local-Area-Zero-Emission). Designed in MATLAB, LAZE simulates water and chemical transport in soils for applications in Local Area Infiltration (LAI) and SuDS. It combines a numerical Moving Mean Slope model with evapotranspiration and an analytical solution to the advection-convection-reaction equation. The model supports the design of filter media

by optimizing soil properties to meet two often conflicting criteria: ensuring sufficient water infiltration to prevent flooding and achieving adequate chemical retardation to protect water quality. Inputs to LAZE include soil physical and hydraulic properties, organic matter content (relevant for hydrophobic contaminants like PAHs), basin dimensions, and precipitation data. The model outputs hydrographs and chemical breakthrough times, and it iteratively adjusts design parameters if the initial setup fails to meet performance targets. Initial testing at a fine sandy site in St. Restrup Fælled, near Aalborg—where a SuDS system is being planned for a new residential area—demonstrated the model’s potential. By enhancing the existing subsoil with organic matter, LAZE was able to identify filter media configurations that satisfied both hydraulic and environmental requirements.

Summary of Deliverables

Deliverables completed:	Deliverables 8.5 Report on use of designer soils for Sustainable Urban Drainage Systems (M46). The deadline was extended from M44 to M46 with the approval of the Project Advisor
Deliverables submitted past due date:	None

Summary of Milestones

Milestones completed:	None
Milestones submitted past due date:	None

1.2.9 Work Package 9 – TA provision

The work of WP9 was essential for the viability and success of Co-UDlabs’ Transnational Access programme. The key goal of the WP was to provide coordinated, free-of-charge TA across the Co-UDlabs’ research infrastructure to as many researchers and institutions as possible, in a bid to make UD large-scale research more open, inclusive, transparent, and affordable.

WP9’s main achievement during RP3 was the successful arrangement and completion of 18 TA projects that had been accepted through the 2nd and 3rd TA calls in RP2. This represented a significant organizational, scientific, and administrative challenge that partners addressed collaboratively, with effective support from both Co-UDlabs and the hosted user groups. Full details on the provision of access were provided in Deliverable D9.2. A comprehensive overview of TA implementation is also available in Section 1.4 below, which is entirely dedicated to the TA program.

By the end of RP3, WP9 had overseen the administrative, practical and scientific execution of 31 TA projects (two more than originally expected) across all 17 research facilities within Co-UDlabs Ris. Additionally, collaborated on the Nas carried out by WP 1 to 4, to disseminate the initial results of what had proven to be an extremely successful TA program.

Summary of Deliverables

Deliverables completed:	D9.2. Final report on TA provision (M48)
Deliverables submitted past due date:	None

Summary of Milestones

Milestones completed:	MS22. Projects from 2nd call successfully finished (M48) Reported in D9.2.
Milestones submitted past due date:	None

1.2.10 Work Package 10 – Management and Co-ordination

WP10 oversees project coordination for Co-UDlabs, ensuring timely execution of the project's workplan and objectives while optimizing available resources. The key goals of this Work Package include: (i) coordinating participant actions and monitoring progress in workplan implementation; (ii) managing financial and administrative aspects for the entire consortium; (iii) facilitating effective collaboration and information exchange among partners; (iv) serving as the primary contact point with the European Commission; (v) maintaining high-quality project outcomes; (vi) addressing relevant gender considerations; and (vii) proactively managing project risks. WP 10, led by UDC, involves all partners in its development.

Task 10.1. Technical and administrative coordination (Lead UDC)

Since the project's launch in May 2021, UDC has continued to lead the day-to-day management of Co-UDlabs. During RP3, the Management and Support Team (MST), coordinated by UDC, ensured the smooth operation of the project and effective coordination across all Work Packages. The MST successfully responded to the growing demands of the project, particularly during the peak phase of the Transnational Access (TA) programme.

Throughout RP3, the MST maintained oversight of the project's implementation, ensuring the timely delivery of tasks and deliverables. In RP3, the MST assisted with the submission of 15 Deliverables. Per the regulations of the Grant Agreement, the MST also served as contact point with the European Commission and Co-UDlabs' Project Advisor to request deadline extensions whenever needed (ultimately, three Deliverables required an extension before submission). At the end of its implementation timeline, Co-UDlabs has delivered all Deliverables that had been initially scheduled for its whole duration — except D10.3, i.e., this Technical Periodic Report, which in agreement with the Project Advisor will routinely be submitted later than the original M48 deadline but before the end of the reporting process on June 30, 2025.

The MST also continued to manage the SharePoint platform and facilitate internal communication, in line with the requirements of the Grant and Consortium Agreements. The MST has also coordinated the safe storage of publications, dissemination materials, documentations, and other relevant information that was produced within the activities of the project and required to be easily accessible by all Co-UDlabs partners — as well as associated collaborators whenever necessary. WP10 also assisted partners with the maintenance and upkeep of the project's Zenodo community.

The MST monitored potential risks and deviations, providing guidance and mitigation strategies as needed. In terms of coordination and outreach, WP10 played a central role in supporting the execution of the TA programme, assisting facility providers with the development and implementation of access projects. WP10 maintained regular communication with the European Commission and the Project Advisor, ensuring compliance with reporting requirements and enabling strategic adjustments to the work plan whenever necessary.

Task 10.2. Organisation of consortium meetings (Lead UDC)

As project coordinator and leader of WP10, UDC has also been in charge of ensuring effective communication among members and organisational, logistical, and technical support when setting up the formal events at which Co-UDlabs partners and institutions have gathered.⁹

During RP3, WP10 has coordinated and supported the organisation of:

- Co-UDlabs' 4th General Assembly (Gelsenkirchen, December 2024) and an extraordinary final General Assembly (Brussels, March 2025);
- Co-UDlabs' Steering Committee meetings;
- Co-UDlabs' technical meetings, convened for task distribution and monitoring of the RP3 reporting process.

Co-UDlabs convened its 4th General Assembly in Gelsenkirchen, Germany, on December 2-3, 2024. The Assembly was hosted by partners at IKT, who had volunteered to arrange the event at the end of the 3rd GA celebrated in Zürich in January 2024. The 4th GA was organised by the end of 2024 because of its proximity to the conclusion of the project's Transnational Access programme, as most of its proceedings focused on identifying potential issues with any ongoing TA campaigns, ensuring that outcomes and results from performed TAs were adequately collected and analysed, and supporting partners whose final TAs were still ongoing or yet to begin. Additionally, the 4th GA also laid the groundwork for the project's final months — i.e., revising the status of implementation, raising awareness on financial and technical requirements at the end of RP3, and defining the project's final joint initiatives, such as the InfoDay and the beginning of final reporting work.

The Assembly in Gelsenkirchen agreed on the agenda and schedule of Co-UDlabs' InfoDay on March 18, 2025, in Brussels (a Grant Agreement requirement for the project's dissemination goals) and on the organisation of a back-to-back final and extraordinary General Assembly on the day before.

Most partners met again in Brussels for the final GA of the project. This later meeting allowed all facility providers to present the actual outcomes of all the 2nd and 3rd TA call campaigns and draw more general conclusions on the effectiveness and outreach of the TA programme as a whole. The GA was also a crucial meeting to distribute tasks for the final reporting process, agree on financial reporting figures, objectives, and procedure, and break down short-term requirements for the timely submission of all Deliverables. The InfoDay proved to be an extremely valuable event to showcase the achievements, results, and expertise of Co-UDlabs and its partners to a wider audience from a key community — i.e., individuals and institutions from the closer nebula of EU institutions, as an additional step towards the translation of Co-UDlabs' academic and research advances and results into valuable policy-making recommendations and guidance on urban drainage, water management, and mitigation of extreme climate-change impact.

Throughout RP3, WP10 has also been in charge of convening and coordinating the work of the Steering Committee, the executive project institution that includes all WP leaders and selected partner representatives. In RP3, the Committee met on September 24, 2024, to discuss the organisation of the 4th General Assembly, the finalisation of the RP2 process, and share updates on the status of the

⁹ All details on Co-UDlabs' governance structure are available in the project's reference documents: the Consortium Agreement (Section 6) and the Grant Agreement (Section 3.2).

TAs. The SC also informally met in person at each of the final two General Assemblies, as a dedicated session for the executive adoption of the Assembly's decisions. Steering Committee members, additionally, also informally met at the 16th International Conference on Urban Drainage (ICUD), held in June 2024 in Delft, the Netherlands, and in which Co-UDlabs partners participated with several panel presentations and dedicated networking events. The ICUD was also an opportunity for the Committee members to meet with Co-UDlabs' then-Project Advisor, Dr. Elena Garbarino, and update her on key results, issues, and planned actions of the project.

Finally, WP10 also coordinated a series of technical meetings — not unlike the Regular Meeting series that Co-UDlabs carried out during the first half of its implementation timeline — during the project's final months. The technical meetings were convened to coordinate action on final project reporting, distribute tasks, and check on short-term goals and achievements.

During RP3, it was harder for WP10 to keep a lively and constructive dialogue with the project's International Advisory Board. While the Board had been more actively involved in previous periods mostly because of the support they provided to the promotion and advertising of Co-UDlabs' TA calls, throughout RP3 there were fewer occasions in which the IAB's guidance would have helped with project implementation (let alone reporting and monitoring), and expressions of interests from the members of the Board were scarce. The General Assembly agreed that it will be essential to communicate with the Board following the end of Co-UDlabs to inform them about the results, achievements, and path-breaking guidance that the project can provide, as well as to involve them in any potential follow-up on the work of Co-UDlabs and within the network and community that it helped build.

Task 10.3. Reporting (Lead UDC)

During RP3, WP10 continued to manage both internal and external reporting processes to ensure smooth coordination and compliance with project requirements. Internally, the MST facilitated communication across Work Packages, supported the preparation and timely submission of Deliverables and Milestones, and ensured that all relevant documentation was accessible via the project's SharePoint platform.

Externally, WP10 coordinated official reporting to the European Commission. This included maintaining the Continuous Reporting section on the EC's SyGMA portal, uploading all required data and indicators, and overseeing the preparation of the 3rd Periodic Report, due by 30 June 2025. The MST collected and reviewed inputs from all partners, verified financial documentation such as Certificates of Financial Statements (CFS), and compiled Part B of the Technical Report based on contributions from WP leaders. WP10 also liaised with the Project Advisor to schedule the 3rd Project Review Meeting, set for 29 July 2025.

Task 10.4. Financial administration (Lead UDC)

As project coordinator, UDC continued to manage the financial administration of Co-UDlabs during RP3. This included overseeing the transfer of funds from the European Commission to project partners and providing ongoing support to beneficiaries regarding financial procedures and compliance with the Grant Agreement.

WP10 served as a helpdesk for financial matters, offering guidance on cost eligibility, documentation, and reporting. It also supported partners in preparing and submitting their CFS, ensuring accuracy in

cost declarations and proper use of the SyGMA portal. UDC monitored the availability of required signatures and documentation to facilitate the timely completion of the consortium’s financial reporting obligations.

Summary of Deliverables

Deliverables completed:	D10.2 – 2nd periodic report (M36) Originally scheduled on M36, D10.3 could not be submitted on time because the consortium is given two months after the end of RP3 to prepare and submit the report. It was submitted on time and as agreed with the PA office on M38.
Deliverables submitted past due date:	D10.3 – 2rd periodic report (M48) Similarly, D10.3 was not available at expected time of delivery (M48, the end of RP3) and it has been agreed that it will be delivered upon completion of the report in M50.

Summary of Milestones

Milestones completed:	MS25 – Final GA – (M48) The 4 th Co-UDlabs General Assembly was held in Gelsenkirchen in M44. A final InfoDay was organized in Brussels in M47 with a the last General Assembly of the project.
Milestones submitted past due date:	None

1.2.11 Work Package 11 - Ethics Requirements

The objective of WP11 was to ensure compliance with the ‘ethics requirements’ set out in the Grant Agreement. All requested deliverables about Protection of Personal Data (POPD) and EPQ requirements were correctly submitted to the SyGMA portal on M4 of the project, so the workplan of WP11 is considered as finalised.

1.2.12 Short description of the next steps to be performed after project ends in the different WPs

In this section the next steps of the implementation of Co-UDlabs for the coming months are presented in brief. The main tasks to the develop within Co-UDlabs Networking Activities are:

- **WP1** will focus on strengthening and expanding the UDRAIN network and the broader urban drainage research community. Key actions include the organisation of a workshop at 13th Urban Drainage Modelling congress in Innsbruck (September 2025) or the collaboration with 12th Novatech conference in Lyon (June 2026) as a platform to showcase collaborative projects and highlight the UDRAIN network; continued engagement with national and international partners through events such as conferences, training, and webinars; and leveraging the timeline for UWWTD transposition to foster collaboration between scientists, practitioners, and regulators. WP1 will support the consolidation of the Urban Drainage Research Infrastructure Community through the maintenance of the UDRAIN Atlas, with planned annual updates and meetings.

Further efforts will support stakeholder engagement and explore new EU funding opportunities under Horizon Europe. Training and capacity building will continue via doctoral networks, short courses, and staff exchanges. These activities will be supported by a

coordination unit responsible for monitoring funding opportunities and aligning strategic efforts across the research infrastructure network.

- After the end of Co-UDlabs, the **WP2** core group will continue to advance data harmonisation and support open, interoperable research in urban drainage. Future work includes developing long-term data archives using platforms like Zenodo to ensure FAIR-compliant, accessible datasets. Renku will remain a key tool for managing and sharing reproducible workflows, allowing researchers to collaborate transparently. A key activity is the [INSCRIBE](#) project lead by Eawag. The harmonised data standards, shared vocabularies, and reproducible workflows developed during the project provide a strong basis for collaborative proposals and cross-institutional research. Efforts to formalise a common, ontology-based data model for UDS open new avenues for interdisciplinary work in semantic web technologies, AI, and digital water governance. The potential to link urban water data with reasoning systems, such as large language models for domain-specific queries, creates space for novel academic and applied projects. By continuing collaboration with IWGDM and related networks, WP2 partners are well-positioned to lead in shaping the digital transition of urban drainage. Collaboration with the International IWGDM and initiatives like Water4All will help align this work with community needs. Continued standardisation of sensor data formats and naming conventions will ensure consistency across infrastructures.
- All online outputs from **WP3** (including Webinars, Courses and Workshops) have been published in the YouTube platform. These materials will reside there, being publicly available for the community. The European Junior Scientist Workshop on metrology for Urban water systems and rivers has proven a successful structure to support the research community of Urban drainage. This is a unique format for our field, in which early-stage researchers have the opportunity to share (in a detail-oriented and constructive environment) their research with peers and established scientists, attend lectures from international experts and hands-on workshops on metrology techniques, ethics in science and on data protocols. This event has occurred every 2 years, targeting to put together a substantial selection of the new PhD community in UD in Europe, and internationally and foster cross-institute collaboration networks. CoUDlabs has supported two of these events (2022-2024) and allowed giving momentum for the continuity of this event. Furthermore, links created in WP3 through the invitation of institutional representatives (industry and authorities), external academics (through the CoUDlabs Webinar Series) have contributed to strengthening the UD scientific and practice community, which we aim at further fostering in the future.
- **WP4:** Some partners are currently planning their participation in events that are taking place after the end of the project, where Co-UDlabs outputs will be presented:
 - Participation of USFD in the EWA/NWA Spring Seminar 2025: Shaping the Future of Water Management in Europe on May 28, 2025 in Oslo, Norway. USFD will present an overview of findings from D6.4 and D2.5.
 - Oral presentation of USFD at the SimHydro 2025 in June 2025 in Nice, France (abstract accepted).
 - Oral presentation of GRAIE at the Astee conference in June 2025 in Toulouse, France (abstract accepted).

- Organisation of a Co-UDlabs workshop at the 13th Urban Drainage Modelling Conference (UDM) taking place on 15-19 September 2025 in Innsbruck, Austria. The workshop on [“How a collaborative network of research infrastructure can benefit urban drainage modelers”](#) will consist of two 90-minute sessions: 1) Co-UDlabs ecosystem catalogue of open datasets of sensors and technologies. How to make data more accessible, reusable and interoperable; 2) Presentation of UDRAIN WG Atlas and next steps for consolidating RI Infrastructures.
- Also, an **online Workshop on FAIR Data Sharing** in Urban Drainage has been organised by EAWAG on May 15, 2025, as a follow-up of the webinar organised on January 28 on the same topic.

In addition, there are currently **several publications which are either in preparation or under review** and which are planned to be published in the upcoming weeks/month: 7 journal papers, 3 technical articles, 1 comment, and 2 policy briefs on RI and on PP clogging (see details in D4.4). Concerning exploitation, some of the project KERs will be uploaded on the Horizon Results Platform to maximize their visibility and valorise them among relevant stakeholders. More information is available on section 1.2.4.

- In **WP5** and **WP9** the next steps focus on ensuring long-term impact and visibility of Co-UDlabs TA program through a comprehensive knowledge dissemination strategy. This includes academic publications, conference participation, open data sharing, and strong industry engagement. Numerous User Groups are preparing high-impact journal articles and presenting at leading international conferences such as Novatech 2026, ecoSTP 2025, SPN11 and IAHR 2026. The program maintains a strong commitment to open science, with all data shared under FAIR principles via platforms like Zenodo. Looking ahead, seminars, training materials and workshops will continue through 2026 with the engagement of UDRAIN WG on Large Research Infrastructures chaired by project coordinator, ensuring that research outputs benefit academic, professional and regulatory stakeholders across Europe and beyond.
- In **WP6**, Task 6.1 generated several practical options for advancing urban drainage monitoring. Promising sensors, such as the ISA UV-Vis for ammonium and the LPICM for dilution tracking, can now be deployed in real-world pilots or Transnational Access projects. Future testing is planned in direct collaboration with innovation partners, such as SUEZ, or in co-development in future EU-projects, such as URBANM2O. The work of Task 6.2 will be continued by promoting the adoption and the use of the UDMT software tool (and/or its methods and algorithms). After the end of CO-UDLabs, a 3.5-hour training course session on UDMT has been held during the annual congress of ASTEE in Toulouse, France, on 04 June 2025. Future training courses will be proposed by INSA in collaboration with GRAIE at French level, and possibilities for more international activities will be explored with Co-UDlabs and other partners, in connection with the UDRAIN Working Group. Proposals will be submitted to disseminate the UDMT at next international conferences like SUDS 2025 in Jiashan, China, Novatech 2026 in Lyon, France and ICUD 2027 in Ningbo, China.
- In **WP7** The ML based spatial analysis of system defects and system and physical characteristics reported in RP2 was submitted to the journal Urban Water “Integrating Dynamic Features into Machine Learning Models for Predicting Sewer Network Failures: A Random Forest Approach” it has been reviewed and UFSD are completing the final requested

corrections for re-submission to the journal. The data collected in the UFSD and IKT laboratories as part of Task 7.2 was analysed at part of Master student projects at IKT and UFSD and this data and analysis are now being prepared as a journal paper for submission to *Water Science and Technology*. The development and the recorded measurement performance of the 4 camera in-pipe DIC system at UFSD and IKT, is being prepared as a journal paper for the journal *Sensors*. The data collected in the UFSD visit to IKT to measure the deformation of the installed cured in-place pipe liner is being evaluated within an international innovation project based at IKT. The code development and the simulation of the impacts of blockages and defects associated with pipe defects carried out by UFSD and EAWAG in the Schaffhausen sewer network, has been prepared into a manuscript “Sewer system performance in networks with defects and asset deterioration” for submission to the *Journal Urban Water*.

The ML based spatial analysis code, that identifies assets with high likelihoods of containing particular defects – developed earlier in CoUDLabs, and the code that links overall network performance to in-pipe defects developed and tested in RP3, will both be used in a recently started EU project *pipeon* (<https://pipeon.eu/the-project/>). This is a project to develop robots for in-sewer inspection and maintenance. The CoUDLab WP7 contributions will be used to develop path planning routines to enable robotic inspection and repair systems to be sent to areas within a sewer network where defects are most likely to occur, or locations in a system in which defects may have the highest impact on overall network performance.

- In **WP8** the work will continue the publication of pending papers related to various developments made throughout the life of the project by Co-UDlabs partners. For example, in the field of the application of imaging techniques in urban drainage, a review paper will be submitted before September in which most of the project partners are represented. In this line, a specific collaboration has also arisen between the UDC and DELTARES, which are analysing new imaging techniques to determine infiltrations in sewerage networks or to apply vision techniques to trace the transport of pollutants. Another research line that could not be completed during the duration of the project is related to the analysis of the useful life of permeable pavements. The publication of a review article coordinated by the UDC and the IKT, based on the results of WP and some TA projects, which will help to define a new procedure for the analysis of the clogging of permeable pavements, is also pending completion.

1.3 Impact

During RP3, Co-UDlabs successfully consolidated its role as a European reference community in urban drainage, completing its journey as an INFRAIA Starting Community with a strong focus on the environmental, social, and economic sustainability of cities and territories. In this final phase, efforts were completed to establish a robust, diverse, and inclusive network of scientists, academics, technicians, students, local regulators, utility operators, private sector actors, and civil society stakeholders. RP3 was particularly significant for the project’s legacy work, with special emphasis on the creation and launch of the UDRAIN Working Group. This group was designed as a permanent structure to sustain collaboration, knowledge exchange, and innovation in urban drainage beyond the

project's duration. It brought together key stakeholders from the Co-UDlabs ecosystem and laid the foundation for the long-term continuation of its strategic objectives.

The TA programme also reached full maturity during RP3, with the successful completion of the projects selected in the 2nd and 3rd TA calls. These activities enabled the implementation of innovative research across multiple facilities in the network, reinforcing the project's commitment to open, interdisciplinary, and efficient access to large-scale urban drainage research infrastructure across Europe. New experimental campaigns were carried out with broad and diverse participation from researchers and professionals across numerous countries.

Co-UDlabs also maintained its role as a platform for collaboration and training, actively participating in international events and organizing capacity-building activities targeted at both industry professionals and early-stage researchers. These efforts further strengthened its position as a European leader in knowledge dissemination and best practices in urban drainage.

Finally, RP3 saw the completion of several tasks within the JRAs, reinforcing the connections between the scientific community, the technology sector, businesses, and public regulators. These achievements significantly contributed to the project's intended impact: a more cohesive urban drainage research community, equipped with more efficient and reliable solutions to address contemporary urban environmental and infrastructure challenges. For example, the UDMT software tool may have an impact for facilitating the adoption of best practices in metrology within the UD community, for both researchers and operators. If the UDMT software tool itself may not be adopted by all potential users, it may at least encourage them to adopt its methods and tools and further develop and adapt them to local contexts. In France, the UDMT tool and practices will be promoted in the frame of the French transposition of the new recast Urban WasteWater Treatment directive, as this transposition is a good opportunity to improve metrology practices at various levels.

1.3.1 Expected impacts included in the H2020-INFRAIA-02-2020 call

Annex 1 presents a summary of the main contributions and indicators of the project as stated in the Description of Action (DoA). Table 1.4 summarizes of the impact indicators included in the DoA. At the end of RP3 (M48), Co-UDlabs has completed its full implementation timeline. While this provides a comprehensive baseline to assess the project's overall performance, it is important to note that many of the project's results —particularly those related to TA— are still yet to come. While the experimental phases of all TA projects have concluded (by the end of 2024 or beginning of 2025), a significant portion of the data generated—particularly from the second and third calls—is still being processed and analysed. As a result, some scientific outputs and impact indicators are expected to continue maturing beyond the formal end of the project.

A similar consideration applies to the JRAs and NAs. Although all planned tasks have been completed by the end of RP3, the full impact of these activities—especially in terms of scientific publications, standardisation efforts, and long-term collaborations—will continue to emerge in the post-project phase. It is therefore expected that several performance indicators related to the dissemination, exploitation, and societal uptake of Co-UDlabs' results will reach their peak after the project's formal conclusion, as user groups and partners continue to work with the data, tools, and methods developed throughout the project.

Table 1.4 Co-UDlabs contributions and indicators to measure the success of the impacts mentioned in the INFRAIA 02-2020 call.

Expected Impact	Co-UDlabs contributions from the DoA Contributions – Indicators after RP3 (Target at the end of Co-UDlabs as stated in the Grant Agreement)
<i>Wider, simplified, and more efficient access to RI.</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Co-UDlabs catalogue of RI and facilities covers the full Urban Drainage System spectrum - Two online events will stimulate the creation of multi-sectorial TA groups. Two open calls will be launched - An external independent evaluation panel will select access proposals <p><u>Contributions and Indicators after RP3</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A comprehensive guide to apply to call is available in the project website, including a description of the facilities - Co-UDlabs holds two hackathon (23-25 November 2021 and 6 September 2023) and a Market place allowing to different actors join to the call and prepare joint projects (e.g., industry+academia, experimentalists+modelers). 2 online webinar events + 2 online hackathon events (Target: 2) - Two calls plus an extraordinary call. Overall, in the 3 calls 41 user projects received and 31 accepted (Target: 29) - Involvement of 127 invited researchers were hosted in the facilities after RP3(Target: 140) - 4 papers published related with the TA projects and 15 datasets (Target: 10 and 20). These figures will increase soon as some TNA users are preparing their publications and datasets, specially those from 2nd and 3rd call.
<i>New or more advanced RI services are made available to a wider community</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Co-UDlabs will expand the capabilities European RIs ecosystem by providing a set of leading-edge complementary infrastructures for UDS research community and EU water sector. - JRA actions (WP6,7,8) will provide new services to RI users, the UD research community and EU water sector. <p><u>Contributions and Indicators after RP3</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The first and second online Industrial Workshop allowed industry and operators to share research problems and how they could benefit from Co-UDlabs TA and JRA activities. An industrial course on flow determination was also celebrated online. An industrial and water professional workshop on uncertainty assessment was celebrated in Lyon and a Course on UDS metrology course was celebrated in A Coruña. - In WP6 the Urban Drainage Metrology Toolbox (UDMT) was released on M18 and update with the Deliverable 6.3. It has 166 downloads in Zenodo (Target: 400 downloads). - The UDMT was presented in the Routine uncertainty assessment webinar (June, 2023 – 35 participants), in the Industrial and water professional workshop of UA in UD monitoring data (Marh, 2024 in France – 8 participants), and in the workshop celebrated in Angoulême (October 2023, France), in training courses in Lyon (October 2023, France), Cartagena (October 17, Spain) and in a seminar in Nanjing (October 2023, China). - The Open database of CCTV inspections from WP7 was released in July 2023 with a GitHub repository with the tools to assess CCTV images. It has 150 downloads in Zenodo (Target: 400 downloads). - New monitoring technologies and scalable hydrodynamic performance and protocols to assess pollution and stormwater ponds reports are available at Zenodo in D6.1, D8.1, D8.2 and D8.4. The total number of downloads are about 350 (Target: 400 downloads)

Expected Impact	Co-UDlabs contributions from the DoA Contributions – Indicators after RP3 (Target at the end of Co-UDlabs as stated in the Grant Agreement)
<i>TA providers develop synergies to improve their common services. Less duplication of efforts and improved used of efforts is achieved.</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The implementation of NA seeks to develop the complementary capacities of the RIs participating in the project, to lift multiple synergies and to strengthen the European research community - In addition, the coordination of the JRAs will fine-tune the synergies and highlight the complementarities of the involved RIs. <p><u>Contributions and Indicators after RP3</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Outcomes from the expected harmonisation procedure will help to share and reuse data much easier. In Deliverable 2.2 the main outcomes of this processes were released. - Mobility and training actions for Co-UDlabs staff: 2 Early-Stage Researcher course celebrated in A Coruña and Sheffield (Target: 2) and 15 capacity building mobility actions (Target: 25) - Joint open datasets related with JRA and harmonisation: 15 (Target: 8) - Number joint reports with JRA actions and data harmonisation procedures: 12 Deliverables D6.1, D6.2, D6.3, D7.1, D7.2, D7.3, D7.4, D8.1, D8.2, D8.3 and D8.4 (Target: 8) - Number joint publication related to the improvements of services provided by the JRA: 6 available related with JRA and TNA (Target 4).
<i>Innovation is fostered through a reinforced partnership of research infrastructures with industry.</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - International Advisory Board will give advice to reinforce partnerships in Co-UDlabs - Co-UDlabs hackathon will promote the participation of industry and SME - Co-UDlabs will also disseminate the project in trade fairs and national level non-academic congresses. <p><u>Contributions and Indicators in RP2</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The IAB was established from the beginning of the project. Four meetings were held during the project - Attendees to Industrial Courses (Target 40) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Workshop on Urban Drainage Practice and Research Needs: 59 attendees o Attendees to Industrial and water professional workshop of UA in UD monitoring: 8 attendees o Attendees to Industrial workshop on flow rate determination of pumping stations and hydraulic structures: 59 attendees o Attendees to uncertainty in UDS course:8 attendees o Attendees to UDS metrology course: 21 attendees o 2nd Workshop on Urban Drainage Practice and Research Needs: 50 attendees - Number of TA projects leading by non-academia: 33% (10/31) - Number of Access days from user groups leading by non-academia: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o 150 days/590 days – 25% in the first TA Call (Target 30%) o 116 days/524 days – 22 % in the second and third call (Target 30%) - Number of industrial organisations and SMEs attending to webinars promoting RI call: 20 in the presentation of the project, 28 in the Urban Drainage Practice and Research Needs, 5 in the 1st hackathon and 2 in the 2nd hackathon, 8 in the webinar to present the second call. Total: 63 (Target: 60) - Number of dissemination events in trade fairs and other technical events: 4 (Target: 3) - Creation of Co-UDlabs marketplace (not foreseen in the DoA). More than 15 proposals were presented in the marketplace in both 1st and 2nd call for access.

Expected Impact	Co-UDlabs contributions from the DoA Contributions – Indicators after RP3 (Target at the end of Co-UDlabs as stated in the Grant Agreement)
<i>A new generation of researchers is trained and educated.</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Researchers supporting Co-UDlabs are PhD students and early-stage researchers - Creation of open tools and training programme within WP3 and JRA framework <p><u>Contributions and Indicators after RP3</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Number of PhD students and early-stage researcher who attended to Co-UDlabs internal events: 8 early-stage participants in the 1st internal seminar organised and 7 in the 2nd internal seminar (target 40) - Number of PhD students and early-stage researcher who attended to Co-UDlabs external events: 22 participants in the 25th EJSW and 20 participants in the 26th EJSW, 9 in PhD course of Sewer Processes (Target 40) - Number of downloads of tutorials, visits to webinar sessions and YouTube channel – 1617 (Target 2000):
<i>Closer interactions between researchers around Co-UDlabs RIs facilitate cross-disciplinary and a wider sharing of information, knowledge and technologies, between academia and non-academic UD actors.</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Close interaction between a large number of researchers from academia and industry. - This number will be increased by the participation of researchers in training, harmonisation, JRA and TA activities. <p><u>Contributions and Indicators after RP3</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Number of joint scientific and technical publications: 5 scientific publication, 20 datasets and 0 technical articles (Target: 18) - Percentage of multi-sectorial User groups in the first and second call: 40% (35% Target)
<i>The integration of Co-UDlabs RI instruments leads to better management of the data-sets collected in the facilities</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The major RI in UDS has never developed a common data sharing framework in Europe. The results of the TA and JRA carried out in these will be available at Zenodo. - The harmonisation and data management actions will allow to define a common framework to implement FAIR principles to increase data availability for the UD community. <p><u>Contributions and Indicators after RP3</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Number of visits of data-set to Co-UDlabs Zenodo data-sets: +4500 views at the end of RP3 (3000 target) - Number of unique downloads of tutorials, webinars views and open-data sets and project reports related with JRA and data harmonisation: +3500 downloads from the dataset placed at Zenodo and +24000 from project deliverables (Target 500)
<i>Integrated and harmonised access to Co-UDlabs contributes to evidence-based policy making.</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - TA providers research groups already work together with the policy-makers in their respective countries and as international consultants. - Currently, UDS challenges include the analysis of runoff water pollution, intermittent spills from CSOs, and how new emerging strategies such SuDS can improve system performance. This is being included in the regulations, but there is a lack of technical knowledge about the real performance of these new techniques and some of the process. <p><u>Contributions and Indicators after RP3</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Water utilities and network operators participate and/or benefit from the development of “early adopters’ group” launched at SPN 10 congress (2) and IWA WWC&E congress (8) (Target 10) - Survey to understand performance of UDS data and their purpose (RP3 within WP2 Task 2.3) - Participation in national level events for non-scientific UD actors: 6 (Target: 10)

1.3.2 Other relevant impacts

The project's Description of Action in the Grant Agreement considers several impacts that are not explicitly outlined in the INFRAIA framework—such as the establishment of multi-disciplinary, multi-national user-groups accessing the partners' facilities with more competitive and transversal proposals—but which were regarded as instrumental for the definition of innovative and ambitious tasks within the project's workplan. These impacts are particularly relevant due to their potential to reach a broader audience beyond academia and to influence policy through the knowledge, technologies, and methodologies developed within Co-UDlabs.

Although the TA programme and the JRAs have now been completed, a significant portion of the data generated—especially from the second and third TA calls—is still under analysis. Therefore, while it is premature to quantify the full socio-economic, environmental, or policy-related impacts, it is already possible to identify several relevant outcomes with strong potential for long-term influence.

Several TA projects have already demonstrated significant potential for broader impact beyond their immediate scientific objectives. For instance, the **development and testing of novel monitoring tools and instrumentation**—such as the OSRAI'Level conductance-based sensor for infiltration detection (INSA-04-DRB-LE GAC), or the Plant-O-Meter for vegetation health assessment in Nature-Based Solutions (INSA-03-OTHU-Prodanovic)—are expected to support the operationalization of smart sewer systems and precision maintenance strategies. These tools, developed in collaboration with SMEs and research institutions, are already being considered for standardization and commercial deployment.

In the **regulatory and policy domain**, projects such as INSA-04-DRB-LE GAC and IKT-04-TEST-Johansen have contributed to the development of new testing protocols and national standards for stormwater management, with direct implications for procurement, certification, and performance benchmarking of decentralized treatment systems. These outcomes are aligned with the objectives of the EU Green Deal and the recast UWWTD, particularly in relation to CSO monitoring and the integration of NBS in urban drainage. This work was also complemented with the publication of two Policy Briefs, focusing on CSO management and Co-UDlabs' contribution to European Research Infrastructures area.

From an **industrial perspective**, the TA programme has facilitated the validation of innovative infrastructure components, such as the novel manhole design tested at IKT (IKT-03-TEST-Carnacina), which demonstrated significant improvements in hydraulic performance and energy dissipation. This design, developed in collaboration with a UK-based SME, has the potential to reduce installation costs and improve resilience in dense urban environments. A novel, hybrid stormwater drainage system (with a combination of permeable and impermeable pipes) was developed in USFD-04-Buried-Li was tested at a full-scale. The results have been used to calibrate a SWMM based design tool and design guidance for practising engineers is being developed. Workshops in the UK and Canada in May 2026 are planned to launch this guidance.

Moreover, the projects have fostered the **emergence of new interdisciplinary research communities**, such as the **UDRAIN working group**, which is already exploring joint funding opportunities and collaborative training initiatives. The involvement of early-career researchers and non-academic stakeholders in over 30% of the TA projects has also contributed to capacity building and knowledge transfer across sectors.

While the full extent of these impacts will only become evident in the medium to long term, the early evidence from the second and third TA calls confirms that Co-UDlabs is effectively bridging the gap between research, innovation, and implementation in urban drainage, with tangible benefits for infrastructure operators, regulators, and society at large.

1.4 Access provisions to Research Infrastructures

1.4.1 Trans-national Access Activities (TA)

In the following section we specifically pinpoint the requests from H2020 Periodic report template for Co-UDlabs TA activities developed under the WP5 – TA management and WP9 – TA provision.

Description of the publicity concerning the new opportunities for access

Not applicable in RP3

Description of the selection procedure

Not applicable in RP3

Description of the Trans-national Access activity

This section compiles brief descriptions of the work that facility providers and hosted user-groups have carried out together for the arrangement, performance, and completion of their TA projects. A summary of the projects developed during this RP3 is provided in Table 1.5. Further information (e.g., procedures, tests setup, results) can be found in Deliverable 9.2 Final report on TA provision.

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Table 1.5. Full list of projects (from any of the three TA Calls) in which costs have been incurred in RP3

<i>Host Institution</i>	<i>Name</i>	<i>TA call</i>	<i>Project objectives</i>	<i>Resources provided for project preparation and implementation</i>	<i>Days of access provided in RP3</i>
UDC	UDC-04-BLOCK-Franca	2	To investigate the onset on motion of large macroplastics by urban stormwater runoff and rainfall	YES	70
UDC	UDC-05-BLOCK-Coupe	2	To analyse the hydrological performance of different typologies of green roofs and its potential heat recovery	YES	51
UDC	UDC-06-STREET-Linnemann	2	To investigate new permeable asphalt pavement clogging and pollutant release	YES	34
UDC	UDC-07-STREET-Lutze	2	To explore a photocatalytic option to adsorb and degrade micropollutants found in building materials, preventing their emission in rainwater	YES	52
USFD	USFD-05-ABFLUME-Martins	2	To investigate the transport of particulate pollutants from sewer networks to surface flows during urban flood conditions.	YES	49
USFD	USFD-06-BURIED-Joksimovic	2	To study the use of fixed hydraulic controls to enhance infiltration via a slotted drainage pipe into a well-drained soil.	YES	35
USFD	USFD-07-RTCRIG Vanderverf	2	To investigate RTC operation of a constructed sewer model	YES	47
USFD	USFD-08-RTCRIG-Gutierrez	2	To investigate flow and volume measurements in a constructed sewer model	YES	26
DEL	DEL-01-BLOOP-Besharat	2	Generate data on the dynamics of gas pocket transport through pressurized pipe systems	YES	37
DEL	DEL-02-BLOOP-Farhadiroushan	2	Evaluate the use of Fibre-Optic Distributed Acoustic Sensing (DAS) to retrieve information on the flow of highly-concentrated slurry flows for wastewater transport.	YES	40
EAWAG	EAWAG-04-UWO-Abdelaal	2	To investigate the impact of heat recovery on mitigating the formation of H ₂ S in sewer buried structure, through computational modelling	YES	1
EAWAG	EAWAG-05-UWO-Dittmer	2	To investigate uses the UWO dataset to assess the required spatio-temporal resolution of precipitation for rainfall-runoff modelling in urban hydrology	YES	50

Co-UDlabs – 3rd Technical Periodic Report (M48)

<i>Host Institution</i>	<i>Name</i>	<i>TA call</i>	<i>Project objectives</i>	<i>Resources provided for project preparation and implementation</i>	<i>Days of access provided in RP3</i>
IKT	IKT-03-TEST-Carnacina	2	To test an innovative manhole design suitable for use in narrow streets	YES	15
IKT	IKT-04-TEST-Johansen	2	To develop a proposal for Swedish national standard for prefabricated stormwater facilities	YES	20
INSA	INSA-01-OTHU-Fuchs	1	To measure the spatial distribution of soil moisture in a swale under artificial heavy rains	YES	7
INSA	INSA-02-OTHU-Prodanovic	2	To explore the relationship between plant parameters and the water management performance of urban nature-based solutions	YES	17
INSA	INSA-03-GROOF-Förster	2	To compare experimental and modelling data of the hydrological response of green roofs across scales, sites and experimental setup	YES	24
INSA	INSA-03-OTHU DRB-Le Gac	3	Continuous monitoring of water level, conductivity and sediment thickness in a detention and settling basin using an innovative multi-parameter sensing device	YES	15
AAU	AAU-01-FREJLEV-Laanearu	3	Air-water stratified flow in a poorly ventilated sewer main	YES	11

- **UDC-04-BLOCK-Franca. Inception of transport of litter under pluvial conditions**

Plastic debris transport during urban flooding worsens infrastructure damage and environmental pollution. This study examines the water depth and flow velocity, that initiate the movement of plastic bags under rainfall. Researchers from KIT, Imperial College, Deltares, and UDC conducted over 200 tests using varied slopes (0.5%, 2.0%, 5.0%), surfaces (concrete and tile), and rainfall intensities (30, 50, 80 mm/h). Plastic bag movement was tracked using automated video and computer vision tools. Results show that bags begin to move at shallow water depths (0.26–1.39 cm) and low velocities (0.13–0.68 m/s). On steeper slopes, bags mobilize at lower depths and higher velocities. Under rain, tile surfaces require higher water depths for movement due to surface roughness and raindrop effects. Without rain, tile surfaces lead to earlier movement due to surface trenches. Rainfall also increases the bags' mass, stabilizing them and raising motion thresholds. A non-linear relationship between rainfall intensity and flow was observed on concrete. These findings were used to calibrate a Monte Carlo-based model, emphasizing the importance of including wet mass in future simulations. The model predicts plastic bags will likely move before water depths exceed 3 cm, offering insights for improving flood-related plastic transport models and mitigation strategies.

- **UDC-05-BLOCK-Coupe. Soil moisture supply and green roof plant requirements incorporating drainage and energy functions**

This research, led by Coventry University with Oviedo University and UDC, investigates innovative green and blue-green roof (GBGR) systems. The project focuses on enhancing water retention and irrigation by modifying sub-base layers to store water and improve root contact. It also pioneers the integration of geothermal heat recovery in GBGRs, marking the first use of a heat exchanger in such systems. Eight roof models—six green and two blue—were tested using standardized Thermal Response Tests (TRT) to assess thermal performance. Built in insulated lysimeter-like boxes, the models included heat flux sensors, thermocouples, and a hot water recirculation system to simulate heat pump operation. Simulated rainfall events evaluated hydrological behavior, including runoff, retention, and evapotranspiration, while effluent samples were analyzed for water quality. Sustainable materials like expanded clay, aggregate, and compost-biochar substrates were used, and lighting supported plant growth in controlled conditions. Data were categorized into thermal parameters, hydraulic performance, water quality, and vegetation/substrate behavior. This comprehensive approach enabled a detailed assessment of GBGR multifunctionality, combining renewable energy use with green infrastructure benefits.

- **UDC-06-STREET-Linnemann. Hydraulic Characterization of Permeable Pavement Bonded with a Novel Polyurethane Binder (HyPermaPave)**

The Polyurethane Bound Permeable Mixture (PBPM), developed at RWTH Aachen University, is a new pavement material with superior mechanical properties compared to traditional bitumen-based permeable asphalt. However, its hydraulic conductivity under clogging conditions had not been studied. This research fills that gap by examining PBPM's performance under different rainfall intensities, sediment sizes, concentrations, and application methods (stepwise vs. single-dose). Tests were conducted at the STREET facility (UDC) using PBPM slabs with varying pore sizes and conventional asphalt as a reference. Results show PBPM is highly sensitive to clogging: 1000 g/m² of sediment reduces conductivity by 20%, 2000 g/m² by 50%, and 4000 g/m² by over 80%. The study also compared testing methods, revealing significant differences between

Constant Head and Falling Head approaches, highlighting the need for harmonization before they can be used interchangeably. These findings support the evaluation of PBPM as a promising pavement material and contribute to the development of standardized testing methods for permeable pavements.

- **UDC-07-STREET-Lutze. Integration of Visible Light-Driven TiO₂-based Carbon Nanotubes for Enhanced Degradation of Micropollutants in Rainwater Runoff**

With water scarcity worsening due to climate change, urban rainwater runoff is becoming increasingly valuable—but it can carry micropollutants, such as pesticides from bituminous roof sheets. This study, conducted by TU Darmstadt, NTNU, and UDC, explores a photocatalytic approach to capture and degrade these pollutants on-site. The method uses Carbon Nanotubes (CNTs) and Metal Organic Frameworks (MOFs) to adsorb micropollutants during rain and degrade them under UV or visible light. Experiments at the University of A Coruña's STREET facility involved modular roofs coated with MCPA-spiked bituminous sheets. Catalysts were applied in methanol after surface heating, and rain simulations (30 mm/h for 2 minutes) were conducted under varying light conditions. Initial tests showed high MCPA emissions (~18–22 µg/L) from untreated roofs. CNT-treated roofs unexpectedly showed slightly higher emissions, suggesting limited effectiveness. MOFs, however, performed well: emissions rose in darkness but dropped significantly under UV and visible light, confirming photocatalytic activity. This project demonstrated MOFs' potential for stormwater treatment and promoted international collaboration, offering hands-on experience for early-career researchers. The findings support sustainable urban water management and lay the groundwork for future applications and scientific dissemination.

- **USFD-05-ABFLUME-Martins - Understanding the transport and fate of ejected sewer sediments during urban flood events**

This project investigated sediment transport dynamics during flood events within urban drainage systems, including the propensity of sediments to be transported from sewers to surface flows during sewer surcharge/overflow events as well as subsequent deposition on the surface. Researchers from 3 universities (from Portugal and UK) visited USFD for a total of 60 access. Detailed experiments in the Above/Below Ground Flume facility at USFD were conducted including 3D Particle Tracking Velocimetry (PTV) and overhead camera observations to provide granular insights into sediment dynamics and deposition patterns in the vicinity of urban drainage infrastructure during shallow urban floods. Experiments were completed successfully, and processing and analysis of the results is currently ongoing, including a detailed comparison of experimental data to CFD modelling approaches. This will enable robust validation of numerical modelling tools and improved scientific understanding of sediment transport and fate in drainage networks during shallow urban floods. We expect the findings to contribute to the quantification of risks posed by contaminated sediments in urban flood conditions.

- **USFD-07-RTCRIG-VANDERWERF. Measurement Uncertainty in Real Time Control and Combined Sewer Overflow quantification.**

Researchers from 2 research institutes (TU Delft, the Netherlands and INRS, Canada). Connection with local company and CFD modelling company (Aegir, France) utilised the RTC facility at USFD to consider the influence of measurement uncertainty on the efficacy of local real-time control in reducing combined sewer overflows, as well as the sensitivity of head-discharge curves to

temporary disturbances on the CSO weir. A model CSO with side weir configuration was constructed and the efficacy of an RTC system to reduce CSO spill volume under a range of hydraulic and sensor conditions was tested. Based on 40 days access, the work highlighted the need for continuous operational maintenance of RTC systems. Additionally, the research shows that temporary disturbances can have a strong influence in the ability to quantify the discharge over a side weir (typical combined sewer overflow design). Outputs are relevant to the implementation of the recast UWWTD (Article 5 & Annex 5) where CSO volumes will now need to be widely estimated and reported. These questions were answered through the combination of the unique research facility at the University of Sheffield and modelling work. We found that when sensor uncertainties beyond the normal-distributed noise are not considered within the fail-safe algorithms, a local real-time control system can deteriorate system performance compared to a non-controlled system. However, fail-safe algorithms can be designed to enhance the robustness of the RTC system. The head-discharge curve for the side weir was shown to be strongly influenced by local disturbances, if those disturbances are close to the sensor location. Quantification of these effects are still under way. Additional data analysis and modelling work is necessary to complement the unique dataset generated through the work done during this transnational access.

- **USFD-08-RTCRIG-GUTIERREZ. Evaluating level sensor methods and computational advanced modelling simulations for estimating flow in combined sewer overflows (CSO).**

This study involved researchers from The Catalan Institute for Water Research (ICRA) and Hydrens – FACSA (Spain) and involved 26 days access to the RTC facility at USFD. The study explored hydraulic behaviour in combined sewer overflow (CSO) systems using experimental tests, Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD), and Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH) simulations. For this purpose, a model CSO chamber with side weir was constructed at USFD. Key findings from experiments confirm that traditional overflow calculations utilising standard energy loss coefficients can significantly underestimate actual overflow volume in the tested configuration. Future work is needed to address uncertainties in overflow calculations under varying conditions. CFD simulations effectively captured hydraulic behaviour and trends, despite minor discrepancies in absolute values. Moreover, CFD analysis successfully highlighted backflow effects consistent with experimental observations, providing a reliable tool for modelling hydraulic phenomena in CSO systems. Conversely, SPH simulations were found unsuitable for these calculations due to excessive computational demands on GPU-based systems. With the introduction of new European regulations on CSO monitoring, this work highlights the importance of estimate uncertainty in quantifying the discharges volumes into receiving waters.

- **USFD-06-BURIED-Joksimovic. Stormwater Conveyance System Performance Enhancement with Passive Control of Flow (SPEC-FLOW)**

This project explored innovative methods for improving stormwater management by enhancing the performance of the Toronto Exfiltration System (TES). Originally developed in the 1990s, the TES aims to replicate natural hydrologic responses in urban catchments. The system was retrofitted and tested at the University of Sheffield's Full-scale Buried Cell facility, introducing Inline Flow Restrictors (IFRs) both as a standalone solution and in combination with TES (IFR-TES). These retrofits aim to enhance passive flow control, particularly under varying hydraulic load conditions. Led by Toronto Metropolitan University (TMU) in collaboration with the Universities

of Sheffield and Belgrade, and Tianjin University, the project involved extensive experimental campaigns. The facility was modified to include a weir-orifice IFR within an intermediate manhole. The experiments evaluated steady and unsteady inflows using various combinations of orifice diameters (100 mm, 150 mm) and weir heights (low, high). Measurements included water levels (via 8 wave probes) and flow velocities (via ADV probes), capturing detailed hydraulic responses upstream and downstream of the IFR. Preliminary findings indicate that the IFR-TES system, particularly in sandy soils, significantly enhances stormwater exfiltration and reduces peak inflows. Analyses by TMU and the University of Belgrade focus on hydrograph interpretation, exfiltration performance, and preparation for numerical modeling using SWMM and CFD tools. This transnational collaboration exemplifies how full-scale experimentation, supported by detailed monitoring and numerical modelling, can lead to refined stormwater infrastructure solutions. The anticipated outputs will support global urban drainage efforts in designing more effective, resilient, and nature-based stormwater systems.

- **DEL-01-BLOOP-Besharat. Dynamic Behaviour of Air Pockets in Urban Drainage Systems.**

The presence of gas pockets in pressurized lines of water and wastewater transport is detrimental for their operation as it reduces their capacity and can lead to unstable transients. This project investigated air-water interaction during unsteady flow conditions. This aims at creating a dataset on gas pocket dynamics to inform further advances in numerical modelling of the process. During this TA access, the beta loop rig at Deltares was modified to create a vertical transparent pipe bent, and equipment deployed to control and measure the formation of gas pockets. Once the structure, the data collection and measuring protocols were in place, Deltares hosted researchers from three universities (Leeds University, Honay University and University of Campinas). The group and Deltares personnel proceeded to create a comprehensive experimental matrix covering different transient conditions to describe the gas pocket behaviour. Approximately 290 tests were conducted with different boundary conditions, geometries and air-valve configurations. A dataset report was uploaded to Zenodo but remains under embargo until the team has been able to fully process all data. At the moment Deltares and Leeds university are performing detailed analyses on the dataset, and the TA consortium is working on 2 journal publications on the results.

- **DEL-02-BLOOP-Farhadiroushan. Testing Distributed Acoustic Sensing (DAS) for Efficient Wastewater Transportation.**

Distributed acoustic sensing exploits light propagation through fibre optic lines to measure vibrations and deformations. Flow properties of highly-concentrated slurry flows are still poorly understood. This project explored the use of distributed acoustic sensors (DAS) in a plastic pressurized pipeline transporting a concentrated sludge proxy (non-Newtonian clays at different concentrations). This instrumentation could be deployed in wastewater transport systems (without the requirement to modify the existing pipeline), and could retrieve information on the flow characteristics (e.g. leakages, flow velocities, solids concentrations). Deriving these processes from acoustic signatures is still an underexplored aspect. To that effect, this TA focused on creating a dataset on acoustic features of slurry flows under different flow and concentration conditions (0%, 5%, 10% clay-water mixture). Different measurement locations were deployed with two different DAS interrogators and two different fibre optics. Four zones were measured using an iDAS unit (1 m resolution) using tightly wrapped sections (2 km of fibre). Four other sections were measured using a Carina system (0.25 m resolution) using wrapped and linear

sections (260 m). The user group is currently analysing the dataset and prepare towards a scientific publication.

- **EAWAG-04-UWO-Dittmer. STARR-ING - Spatio-temporally advanced resolution of rainfall data for ingenious urban hydrological applications**

The STARR-ING project assessed the feasibility and advantages of using high-resolution precipitation data for urban hydrological modelling, focusing on rainfall-runoff simulations in sewer networks. It evaluated whether existing data sources—ground-based measurements, radar products, and AI-enhanced forecasts—meet the spatial (0.5–3 km) and temporal (1–5 min) resolution needs for catchments between 100 and 1000 hectares. Using data from MeteoSwiss, the Urban Water Observatory (UWO), and a calibrated SWMM model of the Fehraltorf catchment in Switzerland, the team tested various rainfall inputs. Multifractal downscaling techniques refined radar data to resolutions of 0.5 km and 1.25 minutes.

Results from simulations of two 2019 events showed that improved resolution enhances the accuracy of runoff predictions, particularly during early response phases. The study also found that ensemble weather forecasts, especially when refined with machine learning, hold promise for urban applications. The project concludes that combining conventional and advanced data sources can significantly improve rainfall input fidelity in urban hydrology. However, further work is needed to standardize downscaling techniques and strengthen the reliability of AI-enhanced predictions across different European settings. It is intended to submit the results for publication in a peer-reviewed journal later in 2025.

- **EAWAG-05-UWO-Abdelaal. Maximising the Benefits of Sewer Heat Recovery through Computational Optimisation and Practicality Consideration**

This project investigated sewer heat recovery as both a sustainable energy source and a potential method to reduce hydrogen sulphide (H₂S) formation in urban wastewater systems. H₂S poses risks due to its corrosiveness, odour, and health impacts. Monitoring at two sites in the UWO sewer network in Fehraltorf, Switzerland, assessed H₂S concentrations, temperature, pH, and dissolved oxygen (DO). Results showed that temperature alone did not explain H₂S variability—pH and DO were more influential. To better predict H₂S behaviour, a context-aware machine learning model was developed using high-resolution sensor data and contextual factors like time and rainfall. The study found that heat recovery alone may not sufficiently control H₂S and highlighted the value of multi-variable analysis and predictive modelling for sewer management. The results from this TA project have also been published in a peer-reviewed publication.

- **IKT-03-TEST-Carnacina. A novel manhole design improving the hydraulic performance of separate sewer systems**

This project presents an innovative manhole design suitable for use in narrow streets, particularly in hilly regions providing cost-effective and space-efficient solutions for separate urban sewer networks to improve and ameliorate the adverse environmental impacts of storm drainage systems. It addresses the challenges of disruptions to city streets and flooding events in downstream networks by mitigating the flow energy inside the storm chamber and enabling separate sewer pipes to be accommodated in one trench. The new shape of the manhole generates a new flow pattern for stormwater. It is therefore important to understand the

hydraulic properties of the newly designed stormwater manhole chamber. The structural and hydraulic properties of a physical scale model of the new design have been assessed at a lab in the UK, and the results showed that the new manhole design provided structural integrity, stability, and significant improvements in hydraulic performance compared with the conventional system. This project's target was to confirm the hydraulic performance of the new system at a full-scale demonstration facility at IKT to facilitate its wide-scale adoption and approval.

- **IKT-04-TEST-Joahnsen. Standard development for stormwater management in Sweden**

Currently, there are no Swedish national standards available for evaluating the performance of stormwater solutions with ability to treat and delay stormwater. Within this project, “Standard development for stormwater management in Sweden” of RISE – Research Institutes of Sweden, Luleå University of Technology (LTU) and Uponor in order to determine the hydraulic performance, the retention of filterable substances (TSS – Total Suspended Solids, by dosing the test substance Millisil W4) and the retention of mineral oil hydrocarbons (MOH) and other pollutants of decentralized stormwater treatment facilities at IKT - Institute of Underground Infrastructure (Germany). The results will be the basis for a standard development process together with the Swedish Institute for Standards (SIS) with the aim of a final adoption during 2025. The test is mainly comparable to the German standard, which means that results from the Swedish and the German standards could be used in both countries, with small additions. The overall purpose of the project was to enable a better competitive and transparent market for prefabricated and compact stormwater solutions, regarding both the suppliers and the procurers

- **INSA-03-GROOF-Förster. Intercomparison of the hydrological Response of Green Roofs Across Scales, sites and experimental setups (INDOOR-GRASP)**

The INDOOR-GRASP project aimed to conduct a paired green roof experiment addressing two research questions: i) how the hydrological performance of green roofs, especially evapotranspiration, may depend on the size of pilot scale roofs, and ii) how indoor controlled experimental conditions may be applied to simulate outdoor conditions in the assessment of green roof performance. The first research question work is based on comparing two similar green roofs except their size (3x3 m² vs. 1x1 m²) installed on the GROOF RI at INSA. After the two green roofs were respectively installed in September and November 2024, hydrometeorological and hydrological data have been collected with a one-minute time step over a period of five months until March 2025. First results were reviewed in February by the project team, including both initial interpretations and modelling tests. Slightly higher evapotranspiration was measured on the 1x1 m² roof. Observed differences in the water balance could be mostly attributed to differences in (micro-) meteorological conditions and small differences in constructive details rather than scaling effects related to the dimension. The TA group and the facility provider agreed on continuing the measurements even beyond the official end of the project to further analyse recordings of a full annual cycle. Therefore, it is planned to continue the measurements until autumn 2025. During the official duration of the project, all aims of the project have been achieved by 31 Mar. 2025 (including data publication). However, in order to test the hypothesis that differences in both setups are attributable through hydrological modelling, the partners need more months of measurements, including a full summer season, which is key to understand the processes in more detail. In parallel, to investigate the second research question, further measurements at IKT are being conducted with irrigation experiments for the 1x1 m² setup.

- **INSA-03-OTHU-SuDS-Prodanovic. NBS pREcision cONdition Assessment (NBS-RECON)**

This TA project involved four partners from the University of Belgrade (UoB) Institute for Multidisciplinary Research (UoB-IMSI) in Serbia, the University of Science and Technology in Norway, Luleå University of Technology in Sweden, and the Bitgear company in Serbia. Plants play a critical role in NBS performance, influencing pollutant removal, evapotranspiration and preventing system clogging. Research indicates that plant health is closely linked to overall NBS function, with plant stress serving as an early indicator of declining hydraulic and pollutant removal efficiency. In precision agriculture, plant stress is routinely monitored, yet current detection methods remain manual, expensive, and unreliable. Recent advancements in low-cost multispectral cameras and Internet of Things (IoT) technology present an opportunity to revolutionize plant-based monitoring for NBS condition assessment and provide continuous data for real-time control models. The project aimed to explore the relationship between plant parameters and the water management performance of urban NBS, incorporating novel low-cost multi-spectral plant monitoring camera (Plant-O-Meter – P-O-M, Figure below). The research identified plant traits that can be used for NBS condition assessment, triggering maintenance actions. This work utilized two existing INSA Lyon experimental facilities (A) two OTHU-SuDS vegetated biofiltration strips (one with grass vegetation (Biofilter 1), and the other with tree/shrub vegetation (Biofilter 2)), and (B) GROOF – vegetated green roof experimental setup (Figure below). Measurements with P-O-M were recorded every or every other day (excluding weekends), by positioning P-O-M on labeled locations, pointing it towards the vegetation, and capturing at least 20 recordings (i.e., for 20 seconds), between June and August 2024. In conclusion, P-O-M and wavelength (both single and multi-point) measurement proved to be a good proxy for the soil moisture of different types of NBS. It seems plausible to measure above-ground plant health parameters and link them closely with NBS water treatment performance (for both quantity and quality). Further work is needed to understand how different plants react to these changes (i.e., we have observed difference in behaviour between biofiltration and green roof plants), how system configuration (i.e., depth, size, media properties) impact above-ground plant parameters, and how different seasonal variations impact these correlations.

- **INSA-04-OTHU DRB-Le Gac. OSRAI'Level**

OSRAI'Level (**O**utils de **S**urveillance des **R**éseaux d'**A**ssainissement **I**ntelligents – Monitoring Tool for Smart Sewage Systems) is a multi-parameters sensing device using water quality and electro-conductivity analysis to measure water and sediments heights in urban drainage systems. Using all measured parameters, one of its main purposes is to characterize water inflows leading to the identification of the rainfall-induced infiltration component or flow components due to the wrong connection to the drainage system. Providing urban drainage operators with such equipment is crucial in order to optimize its hydraulic performances and to foster maintenance strategies. This device uses a series of metallic electrodes placed vertically to measure conductivity at multiple heights. Based on the collected data, the device can provide water height with a 1mm of precision and sediment height with 10mm of precision. Knowing these two parameters in addition to the pipe wet section and the mean velocity, the user is able to get the flow rate. The device therefore allows users to track water conductivity and flow rate. This smart sensor was installed at OTHU-DRB site from June 6th to November 13th 2024. Results showed that the conductivity values collected by the OSRAI sensor are reliable compared to those recorded by a standard conductivity

sensor. The tool enabled also to monitor the thickness of the sediment deposits in the detention basin and in the experimental flume.

- **AAU-01-FREJLEV-Laanerau. Air-water stratified flow in a poorly ventilated sewer main**

The TA project brought together researchers and graduate students from six universities and one water utility to investigate the interactions between air-water stratified flows and sewer gas. The experimental campaign included participants from Aalborg University (Denmark), Tallinn University of Technology (Estonia), Eindhoven University of Technology (The Netherlands), and the Tallinn Water Company (Estonia). A pilot-scale sewer reactor in Frejlev (Denmark) was reconstructed for the study to explore air-water interactions under both uni- and bi-directional flow conditions in the presence of sewer gas. The system of concrete pipes, featuring both natural and mechanical ventilation, allowed circulating air and water to simulate real-world conditions. Hydrogen sulphide (H₂S) was injected to examine its temporal behavior under these settings. Over the course of 26 experimental runs, during the TA period from February 10 to March 3 2025, researchers measured air-water interface positions, air and water fluxes, differential pressures, and levels of H₂S together with water quality parameters such as pH and dissolved oxygen. Water samples were collected before and after reactor filling and emptying to analyze concentrations of sulphate, nitrate, phosphate, and chemical oxygen demand (COD). The research conducted provided novel insights into the complex dynamics of stratified flows in Urban Drainage System (UDS) networks and will guide the creation of a new generation of models and designs to improve all stages of UDS's management – from initial planning and design to improved operational performance and extended system lifespan. The outcomes align closely with the sustainability objectives pursued by water utilities, contributing to a cleaner, safer, and more efficient urban environment.

Scientific output of the users at the facilities

In the following paragraphs the main scientific outputs expected from the different projects developed within Co-UDlabs are shown grouped by its 17 facilities:

- **UDC BLOCK:** BLOCK facility supported the development of significant scientific outputs through two advanced research projects. The **UDC-04-BLOCK-Franca** project, led by Prof. Marco Franca with international partners, has already gained visibility through invited seminar presentations at EAWAG (Switzerland) and Kyoto University (Japan). A master's thesis based on the experimental findings has been successfully defended, and a comprehensive peer-reviewed journal article, targeted for submission to the Journal of Hydraulic Engineering, is in preparation, aiming to consolidate and disseminate the project's key results. Meanwhile, the **UDC-05-BLOCK-Coupe** project is generating high-impact knowledge on the multifunctionality of blue-green roof systems, with expected contributions to major scientific forums such as the Jornadas de Ingeniería del Agua (Spain, 2025) and NOVATECH (France, 2026). Two scientific papers detailing the experimental findings and their implications are currently under development and anticipated to be published within the year.
- **UDC STREET:** The **UDC-06-STREET-Linnemann** project has produced a research paper submitted to Construction and Building Materials, presenting the first systematic study of clogging behavior in Polyurethane PBPM). The manuscript highlights the material's performance under varying rainfall intensities, sediment sizes, concentrations, and application modes, and addresses the

need for standardization of hydraulic conductivity testing methods due to observed discrepancies between permeameter techniques. In parallel, the **UDC-07-STREET-Lutze** project is advancing the understanding of micropollutant emissions from roofing materials and evaluating the potential of photocatalytic materials to mitigate these pollutants. Preliminary findings were presented at the International Workshop on Sustainable Wastewater Management in Africa and Europe, held in Darmstadt in November 2024. Moreover, three conference papers have been accepted for presentation: two at Wasser 2024 and Wasser 2025, Germany's key conferences on water quality, and one at ecoSTP 2025, the 7th IWA International Conference on Ecotechnologies for Wastewater Treatment in Stockholm. A final contribution is planned for the 9th IAHR Europe Congress in 2026.

- **USFD BURIED RIG:** The Buried facility provided two transnational visits. The work from the first visit USFD04-Buried-Li has produced a conference paper for the IAHR Congress June 2025, and an abstract has been submitted and accepted for the IWA Urban Drainage Modelling Conference in Austria, Sept 2025. Modelling and analysis are continuing with the assistance of a Post Doctoral Researcher and Masters students, the target is a journal publication in 2026. A design guide, with SWMM software tools is being developed for practitioners with a draft due December 2025, with an open launch planned for May 2026. Analysis of the data in the recently completed USFD06-Buried-Jokosimovic has just started with the support of Masters students at the University of Belgrade and Toronto Metropolitan University. During the TA, visits to the test rig were made by senior engineers from two UK water utilities, who expressed interest in the work and provided advice on the design information they would need to consider implementing the technology used in the TA – contact is being maintained with both utilities.
- **USFD A/B RIG:** The above-below ground facility provided two transnational access visits. The key output for **01-AB FLUME-MIGNOT** was a journal paper submitted to 'Journal of Hydraulic Research' (accepted pending revisions), which is linked to an Zenodo open access dataset describing the spreading of soluble contaminants in shallow urban floodwater and the testing of different experimental techniques. This work has also been disseminated at a UK workshop on flood risk modelling. **05-AB FLUME-MARTINS** considered the spread of sediments in urban drainage systems during flood events. To date this work has been recently presented at an international IAHR conference (SimHydro 2025). A number of journal papers are currently in preparation, the first of which will be based on the validation of a CFD model to describe flow structures with a scaled manhole, based on PTV data. The target date for submission is July 2025.
- **USFD RTCRIG:** The Real Time Control rig at USFD provided two transnational access opportunities investigating different methods of estimating flow volumes of a Combined Sewer Overflow (CSO) spill over a side weir, and investigating uncertainty in local data-driven real time control strategies aimed at reducing CSO spill volumes. Both transnational access visits provided a detailed dataset of water levels in a CSO chamber which can be used by Computational Fluid Dynamics model developers for testing their models. A Master thesis was completed on investigating the suitability of different side-weir equations, and default CSO weir equations in the Infoworks ICM software, which highlighted the importance of selecting suitable parameters for the weir equations in order to achieve reliable estimates of CSO spill volumes, which is of importance to the new requirements of the recast UWWTD. Regarding the experiments on uncertainty in local data-driven real time control strategies aimed at reducing CSO spill volumes, a conference abstract has been accepted

for oral presentation at the 13th Urban Drainage Modelling Conference, Sept. 2025, Innsbruck, Austria.

- **DEL-Betaloop:** The Beta loop facility at Deltares carried out two transnational accesses aiming at understanding multi-phase flow properties. TA **DEL-01-BLOOP-Besharat** is working towards two scientific publications describing the interaction of air-water flows in transient modes. This is relevant to understand overpressures in air-valve closing, aiming to better understand how to operate pressurized drainage networks with air-entrapment. TA **DEL-02-BLOOP-Farhadiroushan**, explored the potential use of a novel monitoring technique (Distributed acoustic sensing) in slurry flows (typical flows found in low-water consumption drainage solutions (vacuum transport) or sludge transport processes). A dataset has been generated and published in Zenodo. Further communication with the User group is ongoing to explore scientific exploitation of the dataset.
- **EAWAG-UWO:** Eawag's Urban Water Observatory (UWO) water-oriented living lab supported three Transnational Access projects that yielded significant scientific outputs advancing urban water system monitoring and modelling. The **EAWAG-03-UWO-DITTMER (PROBURB)** project demonstrated a hybrid modelling approach combining SWMM with machine learning (XGBoost) to improve the accuracy and computational efficiency of urban drainage simulations. Using datasets from Fehraltorf and other European cities, the project showed that hybrid models outperform traditional simulations under certain storm conditions and can be scaled across locations. This work lays the groundwork for future research into fast, generalisable urban drainage models. A peer-reviewed publication is in preparation. In contrast to flow, **EAWAG-04-UWO-Dittmer (STARR-ING)** advanced the use of high-resolution rainfall data for urban hydrological modelling. The project applied multifractal downscaling to radar datasets and tested AI-enhanced weather forecasts to meet the temporal (1–5 min) and spatial (0.5–3 km) resolution needs of urban catchments. Simulation results using a calibrated SWMM model showed that enhanced rainfall inputs improve the representation of runoff dynamics, especially during the onset of storm events. These findings highlight the value of combining traditional radar data with downscaling and AI methods to improve local hydrological predictions. The results are currently prepared for a peer-reviewed publication. **EAWAG-05-UWO-Abdelaal** produced new insights into the interactions between sewer heat recovery and hydrogen sulphide (H₂S) formation. Field data showed that temperature alone is not a reliable predictor of H₂S dynamics. Instead, pH and dissolved oxygen (DO) were found to play a stronger role. The project developed a context-aware machine learning model that integrates physical and temporal variables to improve H₂S prediction. It also demonstrated the use of SulfiLogger™ sensors for high-resolution in-sewer gas monitoring, supporting better design of energy-efficient and odour-controlled sewer systems. The results have been published in Water Research-X.
- **IKT TEST:** The results of the full-scale tests in the **IKT-03-TEST-Carnacina** validate the lab-scale results of Liverpool John Moores University (LJMU) and approve the hydraulic integrity of the new manhole design, the results show that the new manhole geometry generated high energy dissipation inside the manhole which can improve the hydraulic performance of the sewer system by mitigating the energy of flow upstream and reduce the risk of flood downstream. The successful demonstration of the new system at a full-scale facility will enable the researcher to validate the new system and facilitate its approval by the UK and EU regulatory bodies for its use by sewerage infrastructure providers to address the challenges of high costs and disruptions

associated with the traditional separate sewer systems (SSS) and improve the hydraulic integrity of sewerage systems. The User facility group from LJMU intend to publish the results in the Journal of Hydraulic Research. The impact from the **IKT-04-TEST-Johansen** is important knowledge and understanding of the test situation during the planning and performing of the tests together with the following discussions, that will be used in the following work with this Swedish standard. Based on the results it can be summarized that the Swedish standard worked very well, and only need a few small adjustments, RISE – Research Institutes of Sweden will continue the work with the key stakeholders to bring a Swedish standard fully adopted as a new National Standard by the Swedish Institute for Standards (SIS). The standard will describe a method that gives manufacturers the opportunity to test and verify the purification function of their solutions under standardized conditions and compare results with other solutions on the market, which the technology suppliers themselves indicated as very positive. This to enable a better competitive business environment for all suppliers of stormwater products and to be a fundamental contribution for the fair and transparent evaluation of prefabricate stormwater devices. The project will be presented in at least one article, as a part of the doctoral student of Luleå University of Technology from the User Facility group.

- **INSA OTHU SuDS:** Regarding the **INSA-O1-OTHU-SUDS-Fuchs**, a poster was presented during last NOVATECH 3-7 of July 2023 in Lyon. A Master report is also available. At least two additional publications are in progress. The first one is focused on data analysis and the discussion on processes behind the soil moisture evolution. The second one addresses the validation of ITWH home-made numerical tools using soil moisture spatio-temporal distribution. On the user side, a team leader, an engineer, and a MSc student were involved. The TA project reveals the leadership of the engineer. She supervised the Msc student and gained skills on infiltration modelling in SUDS under heavy rain conditions thanks to the TA program. The conducted TA work significantly impacts the commercial and scientific aspects for Itwh. Indeed, the simulation of SUDS under heavy rain is challenging. Thanks to the TA program and their preliminary background, Itwh can face this challenge. **INSA-03-OTHU-SuDS-Prodanovic.** NNBS-RECON: a communication has been submitted and accepted for the 13th Urban Drainage Modelling Conference, to be held in Innsbruck (Austria) in September 2025. The communication entitled “Fast Nature-based Solutions condition assessment through indirect plant monitoring” explores the relationship between plant parameters (measured using novel low-cost multispectral plant monitoring device (Plant-O-Meter)) and the water management performance of urban NBS (by measuring the soil moisture). The project partners also plan to submit a first communication for Novatech 2026 when the call will be open. A paper in a scientific journal is also planned regarding the same topic.
- **INSA GROOF:** On the GROOF platform, the **INSA-03-GROOF-Förster** project generated a publicly available data set (<https://zenodo.org/records/15129787>) with a one-minute time step, from September 2024 to March 2025, on two experimental green roofs (3x3 m² and 1x1 m²) including hydrometeorological and hydrological data allowing to calculate mass balances and to evaluate the performance of the two green roofs. The project partners decided to continue the data acquisition beyond the end of the TA initial deadline (31 March 2025) until November 2025 to obtain data over an entire year to include all seasons. Also after the end of the TA, one member of the TA User group (from HSWT University, Germany) stayed at INSA from April to July 2025 (with an Erasmus scholarship) to do her Bachelor thesis on the TA project (data analysis, data validation, and modelling). The project partners plan to submit a first communication for

Novatech 2026 when the entire year of data will be available. Papers in scientific journals are also planned (one on data analysis and interpretation, one on green roof models comparison by using the data set).

- **INSA OTHU DRB:** The career development and the impact of the **INSA-O4-OTHU-DRB-Le Gac** were tangible. A team leader and two engineers were involved. The TA project reveals the leadership of the two engineers. The first one has a new position in another SME thanks to his high skills regarding the development of the OSRAI equipment. The second one strengthened his skills in data handling and processing using Python. The conducted TA work significantly impacts the commercial and scientific aspects for IJINUS. Indeed, the quality of collected data makes the OSRAI sensor more reliable and enables to promote its robustness. The continuous monitoring of sediment thickness is a challenging task. Thanks to the TA program IJINUS tested the smart OSRAI equipment under real life conditions that will foster the reliability of this innovative tool.
- **AAU Frejlev:** The Frejlev facility at AAU provided a transnational access opportunity aimed at investigating the complex interactions between air-water stratified flows and sewer gas. The TA project brought together a unique consortium of researchers and graduate students from six universities and a water utility company. Sewer gas, especially hydrogen sulfide (H₂S), poses serious risks, including hazardous work environments, odor issues, and infrastructure corrosion. The project enhanced understanding of how natural and mechanical ventilation influence H₂S behavior in sewer systems, particularly under the complex dynamics of urban drainage. It also highlighted the impact of environmental and structural factors on air-water interactions. The insights gained contribute to the improved design and management of Urban Drainage Systems (UDS), supporting sustainability goals and enhancing system longevity, safety, and performance in urban environments.

User meetings

Table A2.1 in Annex 2 reports relevant user-group meetings held with facility providers during the 3rd reporting period. Meetings were held both in-person whenever possible and online. Most meetings concerned the set-up, logistics organisation, and detailed task definition of the experimental campaigns to be carried out by the research groups at their host facilities.

1.5 Resources used to provide access to Research Infrastructures

Table 1.6 shows personnel resources (in PM) reported in the partners financial statements for Transnational Access activities performed during the RP3, disaggregated by TA and with a short description of the tasks.

Table 1.6. Summary of resources to provide TA during RP3

Provider	Installation	Project	PM	Explanation of tasks
UDC	STREET	UDC-06-STREET-Linnemann	3.91	Logistical arrangements for experimental visits and final definition of UFA and UPP. Preparation and adaptation of the facility for the experiments. Development of the experiments. Follow up meetings and collaboration with data processing.
UDC	STREET	UDC-07-STREET-Lutze	2.53	Development of the experiments. Follow up meetings and collaboration with data processing.
UDC	BLOCK	UDC-04-BLOCK-Franca	4.06	Logistical arrangements for experimental visits and final definition of UFA and UPP. Preparation and adaptation of the facility for the experiments. Development of the experiments. Follow up meetings and collaboration with data processing.
UDC	BLOCK	UDC-05-BLOCK-Coupe	7.37	Logistical arrangements for experimental visits and final definition of UFA and UPP. Preparation and adaptation of the facility for the experiments. Development of the experiments. Follow up meetings and collaboration with data processing.
USFD	RTC RIG	USFD-07-RTC RIG-Vanderwerf	7.54	The RTC rig was modified by the addition of a scaled CSO chamber after discussion with the TA user. Array of water level monitors were installed and synchronised with the existing RTC system. Support/training provided during the testing period. Follow-up meetings for data processing and analysis.
USFD	RTC RIG	USFD-08-RTC RIG-Gutierrez	5.40	The RTC rig was modified by the addition of a scaled CSO chamber designed after discussion with the TA user. Instrumentation supplied by the TA user was integrated with the local data acquisition system and all instruments calibrated against known standard. Support/training provided during the testing period. Follow-up meetings for data processing and analysis.

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Provider	Installation	Project	PM	Explanation of tasks
USFD	BURIED INF.	USFD-06-BURIED-Joksimovic	6.03	Flow restrictors were manufactured and installed in a manhole in an existing full-scale buried pipe system in the large scale test box. Water level monitors were installed and calibrated. ADV probe installed. Support and instrumentation training provided during testing period. Follow-up meetings for data processing and analysis.
USFD	A/B FLUME	USFD-05-ABFLUME-Martins	7.89	Manhole rig modified with Particle Image Tomography and tracing system. Extensive instrumentation testing and modification. Cameras and pressure transducers installed. Technical and research support and training given to TA users. Post-test support with data analysis and interpretation. Follow-up meetings for data analysis and publication support.
DEL	B-LOOP	DEL-01-BLOOP-Besharat	4.86	Logistical arrangements for experimental visits. Support for definition of the final experimental plan. Modification of the infrastructure (creating of a sloped and transparent sections to monitor gas pocket dynamics), development of experiments and follow up meetings to collaborate with data processing.
DEL	B-LOOP	DEL-02-BLOOP-Farhadiroushan	5.50	Logistical arrangements for experimental visits. Support for definition of the final experimental plan. Modification of the infrastructure (creation and characterization of 2 types of clay-water slurry flows, geometrical modification of the pipe loop and support installing the fibre optic measurement system), development of experiments and follow up meetings to collaborate with data processing.
EAWAG	UWO	EAWAG-03-UWO-Dittmer	0.23	Eawag supported the PROBURB (EAWAG-03-UWO-Dittmer) project by providing access to the Urban Water Observatory (UWO) facility, supplying high-resolution monitoring data, and contributing a calibrated SWMM model of the Fehrltorf catchment, which enabled the development and validation of the hybrid SWMM–machine learning modelling approach
EAWAG	UWO	EAWAG-04-UWO-Abdelaal	0.30	Eawag supported the EAWAG-05-UWO-Abdelaal project by facilitating high-resolution monitoring of hydrogen sulphide,

Provider	Installation	Project	PM	Explanation of tasks
				temperature, and water quality parameters in the UWO sewer network, enabling the evaluation of sewer heat recovery impacts and the development of a machine learning framework for H ₂ S prediction
EAWAG	UWO	EAWAG-05-UWO-Dittmer	0.84	Eawag supported the EAWAG-03-UWO-Dittmer project by providing access to the Urban Water Observatory (UWO) facility as well as MeteoSwiss radar data and 2D rainfall simulator, contributing to the experimental design, data acquisition, and post-processing needed to evaluate high-resolution precipitation data for improving rainfall-runoff modeling in urban hydrology
IKT	IKT TEST	IKT-03-TEST-Carnacina	3.71	Logistical arrangements for experimental visits and final definition of UFA and UPP. Preparation and adaptation of the facility for the experiments. Development of the experiments. Follow up meetings and collaboration with data processing.
IKT	IKT TEST	IKT-04-TEST-Johansen	1.96	Logistical arrangements for experimental visits and final definition of UFA and UPP. Preparation and adaptation of the facility for the experiments. Development of the experiments. Follow up meetings and collaboration with data processing.
INSA	OTHU DRB	INSA-04-DRB-LE GAC	0.72	Field visits and final definition of UFA and UPP. Adaptation of OTHU monitoring flume for OSRAI implementation. Design of new equipment and material preparation for data comparison. Maintenance purposes. Data processing and results interpretation. Meetings to discussion on sediment thickness measurements.
INSA	OTHU SuDS	INSA-03-OTHU-Prodanovic	1.00	Logistical organization of experimental visits and final definition of the UFA and UPP. Preparation and adaptation of facilities for experiments. Development of experiments. Acquisition and transmission of measurements, and maintenance of the monitoring system. Follow-up meetings and collaboration on data interpretation and valorisation of results (writing of a conference paper).

<i>Provider</i>	<i>Installation</i>	<i>Project</i>	<i>PM</i>	<i>Explanation of tasks</i>
INSA	GROOF	INSA-02-GROOF-Foerster	1.50	Logistical arrangements for experimental visits and final definition of UFA and UPP. Preparation and adaptation of the facility for the experiments. Development of the experiments. Follow up meetings and collaboration with monthly data acquisition, transmission and pre-processing.
AAU	FREJLEV	AAU-01-FREJLEV-Laanearu	2.25	Logistical arrangements for experimental visits and final definition of UFA and UPP. Preparation and adaptation of the facility for the experiments. Development of the experiments. Constructing experimental setup and data acquisition. Chemical analysis of water samples. Follow-up meetings and collaborative efforts were conducted to review the collected data.

Information of other direct costs related with TA provision to users' projects in RP3 as well as internal invoicing costs from UDC-02-BLOCK-Zafra and UDC-07-STREET-Lutze project are provided periodic financial report part of RP3.

2 Update of the Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of Results (PEDR)

During RP3, it was decided together with the coordinator and the Project Officer, that an update of the PEDR (D4.2) was not necessary since the final update on communication, dissemination and exploitation have been provided in the "Final report on the project exploitation initiatives and related impacts on innovation, including dissemination and communication activities" (D4.4, M48, April 2025).

3 Update of the Data Management Plan (DMP)

During RP3, the DMP was updated at M48 (April 2025), thus including the latest project datasets. By M48, 70 datasets have been produced by the Co-UDlabs project in the framework of the NA (40), JRA (15) and TA (15) activities. All versions of the DMP are available on the project's Zenodo repository: <https://zenodo.org/records/11091173>.

Co-UDlabs partners agreed to regularly (e.g. each 6 months) the DMP to include the publications and datasets generated after the project ends.

4 Follow-up of recommendations and comments from previous review

Following the second Review in RP2, the consortium was encouraged to continuing monitoring critical risks and to deliver the deliverables postponed from RP2 to RP3 with the approval of the REA office. During RP3 implementation risks were monitored and updated in project continuous reporting and all the deliverables and project milestones were submitted on due time.

During RP3 project KPI were monitored and updated. Deliverable 4.4 Final report on the project exploitation initiatives and related impacts on innovation, including dissemination and communication activities was delivered on M48. A summary of the follow up of the KPIs and project impact is also available in this report (section 1.2.4 and Annex 1).

Regarding **Transnational Access Programme**, by the conclusion of the Co-UDlabs project, the TNA programme had successfully engaged 227 users from approximately 26 countries and 122 institutions. These included universities, research centres, SMEs, technology firms, utilities, industry stakeholders, and public regulatory bodies. Of the total users, 54 were women (24%), 67 originated from non-EU countries (29%), and 75 represented non-academic institutions (33%). The programme exceeded the initial targets set in the Grant Agreement, supporting 31 projects instead of the planned 29, and delivering 1,201 access days—an 11% increase over the proposed 1,080. This strong participation also reflected a high degree of interdisciplinary collaboration, with many user groups comprising academic-business partnerships and a mix of early-career and senior researchers. The data underscores the TNA programme's significant contribution to both academic research and market-driven innovation. It has supported the advancement of new techniques, methodologies, technologies, instruments, and standards in the field of urban drainage.

Despite these achievements, the assessment identified several areas for enhancement. These include increasing efforts to promote gender equality, expanding outreach to underrepresented regions such as Central and Eastern Europe (CEE) and Widening countries, and strengthening collaboration with industry and utility sectors. While non-academic users accounted for 33% of participants, further engagement from industrial and administrative stakeholders is needed in the future. Regarding regional participation, only two CEE countries were represented in the programme, despite targeted outreach through associations and partnerships. However, participation from Widening countries was more encouraging, with users from six such countries taking part in the TNA programme.

With regards with the **long-term implementation and sustainability** of Co-UDlabs, Deliverable 1.3 Strategy for RI Sustainability and Community Development presents the strategic vision of Co-UDlabs for ensuring the long-term sustainability and development of research infrastructures (RIs) in the field of Urban Drainage Systems (UDS) across Europe. The strategy outlined in this report builds on lessons learned throughout the project and addresses key priorities, including increasing visibility and accessibility of RIs, fostering cross-disciplinary collaboration, enhancing knowledge exchange, and identifying future funding pathways. Co-UDlabs also led the formation of the UDRAIN Working Group within the JCUD, which seeks to consolidate global efforts in UDS RIs through a dedicated atlas and shared standards and new training and collaborative funding opportunities.

By engaging with EU and national communities, building partnerships with industry and utilities, and exploring new funding mechanisms—such as ESFRI, ERIC, and Open Science initiatives—Co-UDlabs charts a path toward a resilient, inclusive, and innovation-driven network of urban drainage RIs that responds to real-world challenges in climate resilience, public health, and environmental protection.

In relation to sustainability, Co-UDlabs has developed a **Policy Brief focused on Research Infrastructures**, following the Horizon Europe project guidelines (which are not mandatory for Co-UDlabs H2020 project). This document, available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15715128>, outlines key insights and recommendations for ensuring the long-term viability of research infrastructures. One of the most compelling conclusions drawn from this work is the recognition of the critical role played by small to medium-sized, distributed infrastructures in addressing sector-specific challenges with agility and innovation. However, a major sustainability challenge persists: the lack of dedicated EU support for emerging research infrastructures that fall outside the ESFRI/ERIC frameworks. These infrastructures, despite their proven responsiveness and impact, face the risk of discontinuation without sustained access to TA funding and operational resources. Co-UDlabs strongly recommends that the European Union consider reintroducing or adapting funding mechanisms to support such communities—particularly those that have demonstrated excellence and relevance under the Starting Communities or Advanced Community models.

Lastly, and accordingly to RP2 recommendations, Co-UDlabs prepared a **Policy Brief document related with CSO spills** and the implementation of the new UWTD which was presented in the final project InfoDay. The Policy document is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15715128> and highlights the urgent need for improved CSO monitoring, data transparency, and integrated stormwater management to address the environmental and public health risks posed by intermittent sewage discharges. A dedicated policy briefing would be especially valuable to inform regulatory updates, such as those under the UWWTD, by providing evidence-based recommendations on emission standards, environmental quality targets, and the adoption of digital tools and nature-based solutions. Another Policy Brief will be prepared in relation with the assessment of permeable pavement clogging laboratory standards. This policy in brief is related with the preparation of a manuscript with the results from the activities performed within WP8 and will be submitted for its publication during the second semester of 2025.

5 Deviations from Annex 1 and Annex 2

5.1 Tasks

Work plan implementation in RP3 was generally successful and consistent with the project's expected timeline and outcomes. All 15 Deliverables planned for RP3 were submitted on time — including three Deliverables originally scheduled for RP2 and whose delivery was re-programmed for RP3. All re-scheduling requests, in these cases, were submitted to the office of the Project Advisor and accepted following due diligence and the provision of reasoned explanations. The following is a per-WP list of the main recorded deviations from the schedules, work plans, and expected outcomes of Co-UDlabs' Work Packages. Wherever available, a brief description of the measures and initiatives carried out to address and resolve these issues is included.

- **Work Package 1.** There have been no significant deviations from the workplan.
- **Work Package 2.** There have been no major deviations from the workplan. Minor deviations concern the adoption of common data formats and experimental protocols (MS04) and a joint database of CSO spill data (MS05) with the early adopter's utility group. Due to diverse RI practices and initial staffing delays, common acquisition protocols were not fully adopted. However, shared validation procedures and a harmonized data model were developed and will continue to be streamlined beyond the lifetime of the Co-UDlabs project.

This has not been problematic, as core harmonisation goals have been met and uptake continues. For MS05, a joint database could not be released due to complex governance structures and sensitivity around open CSO data. Nevertheless, a comprehensive survey was completed, even if the participation from some countries was sub-par. Work is progressing also outside of Co-UDlabs, under the revised UWWTD, ensuring continued relevance and policy alignment for content and methods developed within project activities.

- **Work Package 3.** There have been no major deviations from the workplan. An additional PhD workshop — the 26th edition of the European Junior Scientists Workshop on Monitoring Urban Drainage Systems and Rivers (EJSW26), in Saint Maurice en Valgaudemar (France), on May 26-June 1, 2024 — was organised with extensive institutional and academic support from Co-UDlabs and its partners.

The workshop was not originally included in the GA, but it was a valuable addition to the academic and dissemination work carried out by Co-UDlabs throughout RP3. This addition did not imply any additional expenditure for the project, nor any changes in the development of any other WPs' workplan or initiatives.

- **Work Package 4.** There have been no significant deviations from the workplan during RP3.
- **Work Package 5-9.** There have been no significant deviations from the workplan during RP3. Although some projects from the 2nd and 3rd calls experienced slight delays, all were completed before the end of the project and with sufficient
- **Work Package 6.** There have been no significant deviations from the workplan during RP3. This WP only required a deadline extension for Deliverable D6.2, which originally scheduled for delivery on M36 but was eventually submitted on M44 due to delays in sensors testing. The document also required an update on M48 to amend typos and finalise Section 3.8, which had to be delayed due to limited human resources available (additional information is available below in Section 5.2.2 on INSA's deviations in the use of resources). The workplan of WP6 also included a programmed update of Deliverable D6.3: the initial version was delivered on M24 as planned; a first revised version was submitted on M32; a final version was released as the UDMT User Manual v.2025a on M48.
- **Work Package 7.** There have been no major deviations from planned tasks and outputs delivered. Deliverable 7.4 was delivered at M40 instead of M36, as agreed beforehand with the Project Advisor, due to the non-availability of a laboratory facility that was being used by a TA experimental campaign (UFSD-06_BURIED-Jokosimovic).

- **Work Package 8.** There have been no major deviations from the workplan. An extension of Deliverable 8.5 to M46 was agreed with the Project Advisor.
- **Work Package 10.** There have been no major deviations from the work plan. Reporting tasks for RP3 were all completed in time, and WP10 also supported communication with the office of the Project Advisor and the Financial Officer to amend any inconsistencies in official reporting documents and data. As regards internal reporting, and as it was agreed by the consortium, WP10 has refrained from convening the ‘regular meetings’ the helped the consortium track project implementation because of how they impacted speed and quality of intra-project communication; however, a swifter version of this protocol was reinstated at the end of RP3 to improve communication and task distribution ahead of the final technical and financial reporting efforts.

In RP3, Co-UDlabs carried out two General Assemblies, even though the institution is expected to normally meet once per year. The Assemblies, however, were strategically crucial to address specific issues and milestones of project implementation. The 4th General Assembly, held at IKT in Gelsenkirchen in December 2024 was planned at the end of the 2nd and 3rd TA Calls, and was essential to assess the outcomes and impact of TA projects and progress with the achievement of all expected results of the Transnational Access programme. A short and operative General Assembly was also organised back-to-back with the project’s final InfoDay event, held in Brussels in March 2025 as a networking and dissemination event which brought Co-UDlabs achievements and results to a larger audience and within the community of EU institutions.

5.2 Use of resources

5.2.1 Deviations in partners’ structure and composition

In the following section, the report presents deviations in the structure and composition of partners’ research and administrative teams. Thus far, Co-UDlabs has not experienced any changes in the composition of partners at the consortium level. However, some partners have undergone changes in their personnel composition:

- **UDC.** During RP2, Professors Luis Cea and Jerónimo Puertas have had to reduce their participation in the project for sick leave and a new position as UDC vice-Rector respectively. Both researchers did not participate in Co-UDlabs during RP3, so their responsibilities and duties in various WPs were mostly assumed by Juan Naves and José Anta respectively. Acacia Naves, senior lecturer at UDC’s Civil Engineering School, joined the Co-UDlabs team during RP3 and contributed her expertise in hydrology and construction materials for the development of the UDC-05-BLOCK-Coupe experimental campaigns. Lastly, project manager Andrea Ciambra left UDC’s team on M46, even though he provided external support from UDC’s European project management area.
- **DELTAIRES.** As discussed in RP2, the initial project coordinator at Deltaires, Prof. François Clemens-Meyer, left the organization in November 2022. Antonio Moreno Ródenas took over coordination tasks from Prof. Clemens as project leader for Deltaires in Co-UDlabs. Due to the unique expertise and counselling provided by Prof. Clemens, Deltaires and project coordinators at UDC agreed with

the Project Advisor to involve Prof. Clemens in specific tasks as a per-service arrangement. Permission was granted. Deltares, at the request of Dr. Moreno Ródenas, has required the contribution of Prof. Clemens in several tasks during RP3. These costs, not initially foreseen in Annex 1, are duly justified in the financial statement.

- **AAU.** The composition of the AAU team remained consistent throughout the Co-UDlabs project, except for the project financial assistant: when Patty Kay Vitug left the department for another position, Frederik Asgeir Berg assumed the project’s administrative responsibilities.

The rest of partners (USFD, EAWAG, IKT, GRAIE, EURONOVIA) did not report significant changes in structure or team composition during RP3.

5.2.2 Deviations in Work Package expected use of resources

All partners were required to share information on any deviations in their workplan as for the use of person/months (PMs) and resource allocation for specific tasks. Ultimately, current figures in project-wide PMs and budget expenses remain within the limits of a reasonable use of resources and in line with the requirements of the Grant Agreement (Figure 5.1).

Figure 5.1. Percentage of PM rate spent after RP3 over the estimated PM in the GA per project WP (above) and percentage of budget spent after RP3 over the estimated budget per partner (below)

Overall, the budget execution across the Co-UDlabs project has been satisfactory, with a global implementation rate of 94%. Most partners — including UDC, USFD, Deltares, EAWAG, IKT, and GRAIE — have managed their budgets effectively, with minor deviations below 10%. The most significant deviations are observed in AAU, around 12% below the original budget, and INSA — which overall requested approximately 30% less than what was budgeted at the beginning of the proposal. In the case of AAU their FREJLEV facility met unexpected difficulties in finding research teams interested in a TA, and it was not until the 3rd Call that the facility hosted a TA campaign. This implied fewer costs especially for WP5-9. INSA reduced actual budget is mostly due to uncertainties in the estimated costs for transnational access activities and, most notably, the inability to recruit a new postdoctoral researcher following the departure of M. Lepot during RP2. This led to a significant reduction in personnel costs as INSA had to declare costs for one fewer person in a full-time position at the institution's relatively high personal rate.

Overall, the rate of expenditure of project budget throughout its lifetime has been satisfactory — especially when considering the degree of uncertainty about TA-related costs and estimations at the proposal stage.

As regards the use of resources, there has been a degree of variability in the allocation of person-months (PMs) if compared to the original proposal. Some WPs have exceeded the planned PMs, while others have used fewer. Overall, the project has consumed approximately 9% fewer PMs than initially foreseen. At the consortium level, most WPs fall within a $\pm 25\%$ range of proposed PM usage, which is considered acceptable given the complexity and evolving nature of the activities, especially TA-related ones.

The most significant deviations can be observed in:

- **Work Package 1.** WP1 used approximately 25% more PMs than originally proposed, mainly due to the increased involvement of GRAIE and UDC (approximately +50% personnel dedication each) when managing coordination and research complexity of WP1 tasks. These included drafting the project's strategic roadmaps, as well as leading the promotion and development of UDRAIN— an initiative originally not included in the GA and with very relevant repercussions on the institutional and networking legacy of Co-UDlabs as a whole.
- **Work Package 2.** Activities under this work package have been carried out in line with the Grant Agreement, using 74% of the originally planned PMs. This reduction is due to the fact that all contributing partners were ultimately required a smaller effort than originally planned, with the sole exception of EAWAG, as explained in detail in the use of resources deviations below.
- **Work Package 3.** Activities under this work package have been carried out in line with the Grant Agreement, using 71% of the originally planned PMs. This reduction is since less effort was ultimately required to complete the tasks. Generally, WP3 tasks required fewer resources than originally planned: back at the proposal stage, effort was accounted for with the possibility that more training activities could be held in person, whereas since the COVID pandemics hybrid or fully-remote options have been the predominant choice.
- **Work Package 4.** WP4 used approximately 4% more PMs than originally budgeted, mostly because of increased workload for WP leader Euronovia and, to a lesser extent, UDC. Both

institutions had to allocate more personnel resources to this WP especially to manage Co-UDlabs' presence online (given an increase in fully-remote and online training and communication activities) and ensure Co-UDlabs' presence at specific international networking and dissemination events.

- **Work Package 5.** This work package was implemented using virtually the same number of PMs as originally planned. The execution closely followed the initial estimates, with no significant deviations observed. Proposal-stage estimations already considered the opportunity for an extra TA call should potential participants have requested additional opportunities to apply, so even the set up of an extraordinary 3rd TA Call was ultimately consistent with foreseen personnel cost allocation.
- **Work Package 6.** WP6 used approximately 42% more PMs than originally planned. The deviation is primarily due to INSA and, to a lesser extent, USFD, which ultimately used around 100% and 50% more PMs respectively in WP6 than initially budgeted. These deviations can be mainly attributed to additional time and research work required for the development of the UDMT toolbox, the dissemination of the tool and its early results, and work related to Task 6.3 on distributed monitoring. Notably, this task has led to the preparation of a scientific article on the analysis of CSOs at the European level, which is currently under second-round review in the journal *Water Science and Technology*.
- **Work Package 7.** This work package has used approximately 57% more PMs than originally planned. The deviation is mainly due to the work carried out by USFD, which leads the WP and spent about 50% more resources than initially budgeted. Throughout the project, USFD has undertaken numerous activities that were essential to achieving the WP's objectives, but which required significantly more effort than originally anticipated.
- **Work Package 8.** This work package used approximately 11% more PMs than originally planned, which can be regarded as a reasonable deviation considering additional efforts made by USFD in coordinating the WP and the development of Task 8.2, which, as documented in Deliverable D8.3, proved to be particularly challenging because of the degree of accessibility, development, and technical adequacy of some of the tools involved in WP8 work.
- **Work Package 9.** The execution of this work package resulted in PM dedication approximately 10% below the original estimate. This slight underutilization is understandable given the inherent uncertainty in planning WP9, which was centered around supporting and implementing TA users projects whose scope and demands were not known at the proposal stage. Despite this, most partners managed to align closely with their allocated resources, which is commendable considering the variability in user group needs and project complexity. For some partners — notably EAWAG, INSA, and AAU — it proved more challenging to fully deploy the planned PMs, either due to the nature of the user projects assigned to them or logistical constraints in implementation. Overall, the deviation is not considered critical and reflects the flexible and adaptive nature required for managing transnational access activities.
- **Work Package 10.** This work package required approximately 57% more PMs than originally foreseen. The main reason for this deviation was the need for UDC to appoint a full-time

Project Manager to ensure effective coordination of the project. Additionally, most partners had to dedicate more PMs than initially planned, which reflects the fact that projects involving TA are inherently more complex to manage than other types of Research and Innovation Actions (RIAs).

The remainder of this section provides an analysis of budget execution deviations in RP3 with specific explanations per partner.

UDC

UDC submitted an Adjustment request for a total amount of EUR 1,898.16 in Other Goods and Services for RP2 due to costs that were incurred in RP2 but could not be declared within the reporting period because either the provider had not timely submitted the corresponding invoices or UDC had revised specific costs due to a change in procedure. This amount can be broken down as follows:

- EUR 959.82 corresponding to travel, accommodation, and allowance expenses for the visiting research group of transnational access project UDC-01-BENS-Peña on September 18-20, 2023, for the TA final meeting (late invoicing);
- EUR 504.00 corresponding to travel, accommodation, and allowance expenses for UDC project member, Juan Naves García-Rendueles, and his visit to the facilities of Aalborg University, on April 22-25, 2023, in the framework of WP2's internal mobility programme (late invoicing);
- EUR 31.34 corresponding to adjustments to allowances paid to research group members of UDC-07-STREET-Lutze, following a revision of UDC's internal procedure for allowance costs for EU-EEA residents;
- EUR 193.00 corresponding to rental service of a disposal container in the follow-up to experiments of the UDC-05-BLOCK-Coupe TA (late invoicing);
- EUR 210.00 corresponding to shipment of TA laboratory samples to the group's host institution for TA UDC-07-STREET-Lutze (late invoicing due to periodic bulk shipments that spilled over into RP3).

At the end of the project, UDC has spent its estimated budget, with no notable deviations in its WPs or its total budget. Claimed costs are slightly higher than the original budget at proposal stage, mostly because of higher resources needed for project management (WP10) — as agreed with the Project Advisor's office and reported in RP2. In addition to the work carried out under WP10, UDC has also invested additional resources in WP1 and WP4. This increased effort was driven by the need to coordinate the development of the UDRAIN Working Group within JCUD and support the extensive dissemination and communication activities undertaken throughout the project.

USFD

Alongside its RP3 financial report, USFD has also submitted two Adjustments to the financial reports of RP1 (EUR 1,111.15) and RP2 (EUR 6,540.36). The former was requested due to:

- a revision of hourly rates of part-time staff working at the time for the Co-UDlabs project, since the cost of statutory holidays is to be calculated differently for part-time staff compared with full-time staff, leading to a EUR 923.26 difference from what was originally declared in RP1;
- dismissal of a goods-and-services cost item whose receipt/invoice could not be located, for a EUR -34.34 difference from what was originally declared in RP1.

The latter was requested due to:

- adjustment of project personnel dedication due to a timesheet for an academic member of the project's USFD team which was mistakenly not considered when consolidating calculations for time dedication to Co-UDlabs;
- adjustment of project personnel dedication because a part-time administrative staff's dedication to the project was mistakenly calculated at the time of RP2. Correction of this error made their per-hour rate slightly higher than originally foreseen and the Adjustment considers the increase in the overall personnel costs incurred after this revision.

Claimed costs at USFD are higher than budgeted in the proposal, with a strong and unforeseen impact of unfavourable currency exchange between Euro and the British pound — as more PMs could have been used for project activities had the personnel cost rate been lower due to a favourable exchange rate. Work performed at USFD, however, was well within the internal expected budget against the GBP. In WP7, additional PMs were required to validate the conversion of sewer network models (from various software packages to SWMM) to enable the automated change in asset geometry. This task was carried out using lower-cost researchers rather than more senior researchers, which participated in writing the code and carrying out the analysis.

Deltares

Alongside its RP3 financial report, Deltares has also submitted two Adjustments to the financial reports of RP1 (EUR 5,306.90) and RP2 (EUR 6,017.81). The former was requested due to:

- the yearly revision of Deltares staff salaries not accounted for RP1 and RP2; leading to a EUR 3,481.50 difference from what was originally declared in RP1 and to EUR 2,949.87 in RP2.
- other direct cost items that should have been reported in the actual reporting periods, for a EUR 764.02 and EUR 1.864.38 difference from what was originally declared in RP1 and RP2, respectively.

During RP3, INSA Lyon and Deltares organised the 26th edition of the European Junior Scientist Workshop (EJWS26). While this event was not formally foreseen in the Grant Agreement, it was nonetheless considered an excellent opportunity to bridge specific gaps between Co-UDlabs' work and the UD research community (especially those at an earlier stage of their careers), while also providing a mitigating measure for accessibility or visibility risks connected to WP3 and training. The EJSW was a one-week full-time event including lectures and hands-on workshops on metrology for rivers and urban water systems. Dr. Antonio Moreno Ródenas and Prof. François Clemens were heavily involved in the organisation and execution of this task, which resulted in two unforeseen costs, as explained in detail in Deltares' financial report.

Additionally, during RP3, Deltares and UDC undertook an additional Joint Research Activity aiming to describe operational and practical aspects of monitoring with optical systems in urban drainage. Outputs from this JRA have been used to submit a scientific publication on the use of camera systems for velocimetry applications in sewer and wastewater streams (currently in preparation) and to support statements in the article "Review of optical methods in urban drainage" (in preparation). Activities related to this JRA resulted in additional workload in WP6 and additional purchases (mostly tools for the setup of three camera systems), also reported in detail in the financial statement. WP3 and WP8 also had a larger PM allocation than originally planned for Deltares, mostly because of Dr. Moreno Ródenas additional contributions in coordinating WP3 and WP8 activities (e.g., optical

monitoring in urban drainage and related scientific publications currently in preparation). PM allocation by Deltares has ultimately been slightly higher (+19%) than initially planned due to additional non-envisioned tasks. However, given that because of internal staff changes Deltares' average cost has been lower than initially planned, these changes have implied nearly no impact on total budget expenditure.

EAWAG

During RP3, EAWAG's use of resources showed notable deviations from the original estimates across four work packages. These variations reflect both evolving project demands, and strategic prioritisation of tasks aligned with Co-UDlabs' long-term goals.

In WP2, EAWAG contributed significantly beyond initial expectations. This increase was driven by intensive efforts related to Task 2.3, focusing on smart governance and public access to data. Coordinating and implementing a multi-country stakeholder survey proved more complex than anticipated, due to the need to tailor instruments to diverse national contexts and institutional structures. In addition, EAWAG led future-oriented work on data model development, engaging extensively with the wider urban drainage community—including coordination with the IWA/IAHR International Working Group on Data and Models. These activities were essential to producing Deliverable D2.5 and advancing Co-UDlabs' interoperability agenda.

By contrast, EAWAG's planned contributions to WP7 (Asset Deterioration) were reduced, as the main role during this period was to support a new use case in Schaffhausen, which required fewer person-months than originally forecast. This adjustment allowed resources to be redirected toward WP2, where engagement levels and coordination needs were higher than expected.

In WP8, EAWAG's activity remained low, as only a minor allocation was foreseen, and no substantial outputs were scheduled during the period. The limited resource use is therefore consistent with the original implementation plan.

For WP9, EAWAG's involvement was focused primarily on hosting activities at the UWO facility in RP3. While participation in meetings and coordination tasks continued, the effort required was reduced thanks to the strong foundation established in previous periods. Recurring collaboration with experienced partners (e.g., RPTU) and users—combined with standardized procedures and effective documentation—enabled efficient support of the TA process, which saved resources. Deliverable D9.2 reflects this continuity and benefits from work conducted during RP1 and RP2.

Finally, currency fluctuations needed to be compensated, because EAWAG received EU funding in Euro but spent in Swiss francs, where the stronger CHF meant a relative funding shortfall. An adaptive budget planning strategy was successful in absorbing the differences.

IKT

By the end of the project, IKT had spent its estimated budget with no significant deviations in either its work packages or its overall allocation. Although the final expenditure was slightly below the initial estimate, the difference is not considered significant and does not warrant further remark.

INSA

The consequences of deviations mentioned during the previous reporting periods still had effects during RP3. Following the resignation of a key research team member in Dr. Mathieu Lepot during RP2, INSA met increasing difficulties in hiring trained staff that could actively replace Dr. Lepot's

position from the onset without requiring additional internal training. Such difficulties coupled with the summer break in 2024 and the fact that the rest of INSA staff (Prof. Jean-Luc Bertrand-Krajewski in WP6 (finishing Tasks 6.1 and 6.2) and Richard Poncet in WP 9 for TA INSA-03-GROOF-Förster on green roof experimental work and data acquisition) had, in the meantime, provided additional efforts to fill in for the vacant post and advance significantly in most tasks that required INSA's contribution. INSA therefore managed to provide the needed effort without materially replacing the position that had become vacant, thus achieving relatively the same objective with fewer personnel resources. Considering that Dr. Lepot's was a senior research position with a relatively high-cost rate, forgoing that amount of personnel dedication for the whole of RP3 translated into significantly lower personnel costs for INSA altogether (approximately EUR 266,000 declared personnel costs vs. a preliminary proposed budget of EUR 402,000, -33.76%).

Staffing issues also affected the workplan of WPs in which INSA was active. INSA's contribution to Deliverable D6.2 on sensors testing was eventually delayed due to limited time availability of Prof. Bertrand-Krajewski and the rest of the staff (delivery postponed from M36 in RP2 to M44 in RP3). A final version update was submitted on M48.

AAU

AAU fulfilled participation in the Co-UDlabs project as planned, with only minor deviations from the budget due to a slight overall increase. Attracting relevant TA proposals at AAU's facility proved more challenging than anticipated. Despite outreach efforts, no suitable applications were received during the first two calls. However, during the third and final call, AAU did receive a suitable application, which enabled the providers to host a successful TA at FREJLEV.

GRAIE

GRAIE's participation in the Co-UDlabs project remained within the planned budget and commitments. The organisation concentrated its efforts primarily on WP1, which turned out to be more complex than initially anticipated due to its cross-cutting and interdisciplinary nature. This required the mobilisation and coordination of all project partners, making the associated interface and coordination tasks particularly time-consuming. However, the preparatory work carried out under WP1 provided valuable input for WP4, especially in terms of collecting and sharing success stories.

Euronovia

During RP3, Euronovia lacked appropriate personnel costs to cover the personnel efforts needed in the last year of the project. In fact, only EUR 4,738.54 of personnel costs were left after the end of RP2, which corresponds to less than 1 PM. Due to the intense period before the end of the project, Euronovia spent 5,08 PM in RP3, mainly for communication and dissemination of final project events, intense online communication efforts required to promote project outcomes and success stories, the delivery of three newsletters, the production of the final media press kit and the final press release, the co-organisation of the final InfoDay, the coordination of exploitation tasks, the preparation of Deliverables D4.4, D2.4, and D3.3, and the participation in several consortium and technical meetings. As a result, the personnel costs of RP3 were covered by remaining Other direct costs. A detailed explanation of underspending in this budget category can be found in the technical report of RP2 (in summary, fewer travels than planned, exhibition booths and exploitation seminar organised at no costs). All in all, the overspending in personnel costs is balanced by the underspending in the other direct costs, for Euronovia to stay within the originally assigned budget

5.3 Unforeseen subcontracting

Not applicable

5.4 Unforeseen use of in-kind contribution from third party against payment or free of charges

Not applicable

Annex 1. Co-UDlabs Key Performance Indicators analysis

Co-UDlabs Communication and dissemination plan																		
Dissemination or communication channel	Tool	When (and where, if relevant)	Target audiences						KPI	Target M48	Results M48	Evaluation - M48				Partner(s) in charge		
			Academics and researchers	Industry / Practitioners	Government / Policy-makers	EU and international networks	National technology networks	EU projects				General public/advocacy groups	High (>100%)	Good (≤ 100%)	Moderate (≤ 75%)		Low (<50%)	
Events to be organised by the project partners	2 Early-stage researchers seminars	1) June 27-28, 2022 2) September 19-20, 2024	X							Number of participants	20	1) 33 2) 7	>20	≤ 20	≤ 15	< 10	UDC, USFD	
	- 25th European Junior Scientists Workshop (EJSW) on UD monitoring	May 15-21, 2022	X							Number of participants	22	20	>22	≤ 22	≤ 16	< 11	INSA	
	PhD course on Sewer Processes	2023 --> October 7-11, 2024	X							Number of participants	40	9	>40	≤ 40	≤ 30	< 20	AAU	
	Industrial workshop on flow rate determination of pumping stations and hydraulic structures (1 day)	November 17, 2022		X			X			Number of participants	20	45	>20	≤ 20	≤ 15	< 10	DEL	
	Uncertainty assessment in UD monitoring data (2 days)	2023--> 6-7 March 2024		X			X			Number of participants	12	8	>12	≤ 12	≤ 9	< 6	INSA	
	Applied course on UD metrology (4 days)	July 16-19, 2024		X			X			Number of participants	12	21	> 12	≤ 12	≤ 9	< 6	UDC	
	2 IKT-association practice workshops (2 days)	1) November 3-4, 2021 2) March 11, 2025	X	X			X			Number of participants	20	1) 59 2) 50	> 20	≤ 20	≤ 15	< 10	IKT	
	Webinars and online lectures	2022 to 2025 1) September 21, 2022 2) May 16, 2023 3) June 12, 2023 4) March 15, 2024 5) January 10, 2025 6) January 30, 2025	X	X			X	X	X		Number of webinars	6	6	>6	≤ 6	≤ 4	< 3	IKT / all research institutions
											Number of attendees	30	1st webinar: 18 2nd webinar: 50 3rd webinar: 35 4th webinar: 25 5th webinar: 51 6th webinar: 50	>30	≤ 30	≤ 22	< 15	
	Side event at the Sewer Processes and Networks (SPN) conference	August 23, 2022 (Graz, Austria)		X		X	X			Number of participants	30	18	> 30	≤ 30	≤ 22	< 15	INSA/GRAIE	
	Side event at the NOVATECH conference	July 2023 (Lyon, France)		X		X	X			Number of participants	30	49	> 30	≤ 30	≤ 22	< 15	GRAIE	
	2 webinars and 2 hackathons	Before the TA calls the access to the research infrastructures	X	X		X	X			Number of attendees	60	1st webinar/hack: 100/61 2nd webinar/hack: 28/28	> 60	≤ 60	≤ 45	< 30	UDC	
	2 dissemination workshops on smart governance	Side events of IWA specialized working groups conferences or meetings 1) September 13, 2022 2) January 28, 2025		X	X	X	X	X		Number of participants	30	1st workshop: 40 2nd workshop: 16	> 30	≤ 30	≤ 22	< 15	EAWAG	
	3 Workshops related with results of JRAs	Side events of IWA specialized working groups conferences or meetings 1) UDMT workshop - August 23, 2022 2) UDMT workshop - October 17, 2023 3) EURO-SAM workshop	X	X		X	X	X		Number of participants	40	1) 18 2) 11 3) 25	> 40	≤ 40	≤ 30	< 20	INSA, USFD, UDC	
Final Info Day	At the end of the project	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	Number of attendees	50	37	> 50	≤ 50	≤ 37	< 25	Euronovia, UDC		

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Participation in external events and conferences	Scientific conferences	2022, 2023, 2024, 2025	X	X	X	X	X					Number of conferences	15	19	> 15	≤ 15	≤ 11	< 7	All research partners
	National technical events	2022, 2023, 2024, 2025		X			X					Number of events	10	16	> 10	≤ 10	≤ 7	< 5	All partners
	Fairs in innovation and technology related events	2022, 2023, 2024, 2025		X		X	X	X				Number of exhibitions	3	4	> 3	≤ 3	≤ 2	< 1	All partners
	Open-science events	2022, 2023, 2024, 2025							X	X		Number of events	10	7	> 10	≤ 10	≤ 7	< 5	All partners
Communication/dissemination material and activities	Project branding (logo, visual identity, communication templates, project leaflet, etc.)	At the beginning of the project	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	1	1	1	>1	≤ 0	-	-	-	Euronovia
	Communication package	M6	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	1	1	1	> 1	≤ 0	-	-	-	Euronovia	
	Flyer	M6	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	Number of flyers distributed	2000	1200	> 2000	≤ 2000	≤ 1500	< 1000	-	Euronovia	
	Brochure	M24	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	Number of brochures distributed	2000	1200	> 2000	≤ 2000	≤ 1500	< 1000	-	Euronovia	
	Newsletter	Every 6 months, starting M6	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	Number of issues	8	14	> 8	≤ 8	≤ 6	< 4	-	Euronovia	
										Number of subscribers	100	546	> 100	≤ 100	≤ 75	< 50	-	Euronovia	
	Press release	At the start and at the end of the project	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	Number of press releases	2	3	> 2	≤ 2	≤ 1	< 0	-	Euronovia	
	Articles in specialized magazines	Whole project duration	X	X		X	X			Number of articles	2	2	>2	≤ 2	≤ 1	< 0	-	All partners	
	Timeline infography	At the end of the project	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	Number of infography	1	2	> 1	≤ 1	≤ 0	-	-	Euronovia	
	1 Motion design video	September 2022	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	Number of views on Youtube	500	382	> 500	≤ 500	≤ 375	< 250	-	Euronovia	
	Website	Whole project duration	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	Number of visits	100/month	443/month	> 100	≤ 100	≤ 75	< 50	-	Euronovia	
										Number of news	1 news/month = 48	99	> 48	≤ 48	≤ 36	< 24	-	Euronovia	
	LinkedIn page	Whole project duration	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	Number of members	200	652	> 200	≤ 200	≤ 75	< 100	-	All (leader: Euronovia)	
										Number of posts	1/month = 48	182	>48	≤ 48	≤ 36	< 24	-	All (leader: Euronovia)	
	Twitter account	Whole project duration	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	Number of followers	200	217	> 200	≤ 200	≤ 75	< 100	-	All (leader: Euronovia)	
										Number of tweets	1/week= 208	315	> 208	≤ 208	≤ 156	< 104	-	Euronovia	
	Youtube channel with videos and interviews	from M12	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	Number of videos	15	26	> 15	≤ 15	≤ 11	< 7	-	All (leaders: Deltares/IKT)	
Number of views										7500	1617	> 7500	≤ 7500	≤ 5625	< 3750	-	Euronovia		
Media press kit	M24 and M48	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	Number of press kit	2	2	>2	≤ 2	≤ 1	< 0	-	Euronovia		
Public relations and media coverage	Whole project duration			X	X	X	X	X	Number of external articles in the media	15	22	>15	≤ 15	≤ 11	< 7	-	All partners		
Publications	Scientific publications (peer-reviewed research papers) and related datasets	From 2022	X	X					Nber of scientific papers	10	11	>10	≤ 10	≤ 7	< 5	-	All research partners		
									Nber of datasets	20	29	>20	≤ 20	≤ 15	< 10	-			
									Number of visits / downloads of data-sets on Zenodo	3000	6831	>3000	≤ 3000	≤ 2250	≤ 1500	-			
	Technical articles (international and national journals)	From 2022		X		X	X		Nber of technical papers	8	3	>8	≤ 8	< 6	< 4	-	All research partners		
Conference proceedings	From 2022	X	X		X	X			Nber of conference papers	15	28	>15	≤ 15	≤ 11	< 7	-	All research partners		
Tot. KPI M48											44								
													26	8	6	4			
													59%	18%	14%	9%			

Annex 2. User group meetings

Table A2.1 below lists relevant user-group meetings held by facility providers and representatives of the visiting groups in charge of Transnational Access projects. The list is not exhaustive and includes meetings held in preparation and arrangement of the experimental campaigns. For more details on user meetings and the arrangement of TAs, please see Section 1.4 above.

Table A2.1. List of relevant user-group meetings with facility providers.

Project Acronym	Date	Venue	Approx. # of attendees	Description
UDC-04-BLOCK-Franca	07/05/2024	Online	6	UFA preparation
UDC-04-BLOCK-Franca	27/06/2024	Online	6	UFA preparation
UDC-04-BLOCK-Franca	01/07/2024	In-person	4	TA starting meeting and setup
UDC-04-BLOCK-Franca	12/07/2024	In-person	6	TA follow-up
UDC-04-BLOCK-Franca	13/09/2024	In-person	4	TA follow-up
UDC-04-BLOCK-Franca	20/09/2024	In-person	4	TA follow-up
UDC-04-BLOCK-Franca	11/10/2024	In-person	4	TA follow-up
UDC-04-BLOCK-Franca	22/10/2024	In-person	4	TA follow-up
UDC-04-BLOCK-Franca	05/11/2024	In-person	4	TA final week meeting
UDC-04-BLOCK-Franca	20/12/2024	Online	6	Analysis of results after TA
UDC-04-BLOCK-Franca	10/01/2025	Online	6	Analysis of results after TA
UDC-04-BLOCK-Franca	06/02/2025	Online	6	Analysis of results after TA
UDC-05-BLOCK-Coupe	18/09/2024	Online	7	UFA preparation
UDC-05-BLOCK-Coupe	31/10/2024	Online	7	UFA preparation
UDC-05-BLOCK-Coupe	13/11/2024	Online	7	UFA preparation
UDC-05-BLOCK-Coupe	09/12/2024	In-person	7	TA starting meeting and setup
UDC-05-BLOCK-Coupe	19/12/2025	In-person	4	TA follow-up
UDC-05-BLOCK-Coupe	17/01/2025	In-person	4	TA follow-up
UDC-05-BLOCK-Coupe	23/01/2025	In-person	4	TA follow-up
UDC-05-BLOCK-Coupe	20/02/2025	In-person	4	TA follow-up
UDC-05-BLOCK-Coupe	10/03/2025	In-person	4	TA follow-up
UDC-05-BLOCK-Coupe	20/03/2025	In-person	7	TA final week meeting
UDC-05-BLOCK-Coupe	02/04/2025	Online	7	Analysis of results after TA

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<i>Project Acronym</i>	<i>Date</i>	<i>Venue</i>	<i>Approx. # of attendees</i>	<i>Description</i>
UDC-05-BLOCK-Coupe	28/04/2025	Online	7	Analysis of results after TA
UDC-06-STREET-Linnemann	14/05/2024	Online	4	UFA preparation
UDC-06-STREET-Linnemann	11/07/2024	Online	4	UFA preparation
UDC-06-STREET-Linnemann	29/07/2024	Online	4	UFA preparation
UDC-06-STREET-Linnemann	19/09/2024	In-person	4	TA starting meeting and setup
UDC-06-STREET-Linnemann	25/09/2024	In-person	4	TA follow-up
UDC-06-STREET-Linnemann	01/10/2024	In-person	4	TA follow-up
UDC-06-STREET-Linnemann	29/10/2024	In-person	4	TA follow-up
UDC-06-STREET-Linnemann	08/11/2024	In-person	4	TA final week meeting
UDC-06-STREET-Linnemann	13/12/2024	Online	3	Analysis of results after TA
UDC-06-STREET-Linnemann	11/02/2025	Online	3	Analysis of results after TA
UDC-07-STREET-Lutze	03/05/2024	In-person	8	TA follow-up
UDC-07-STREET-Lutze	24/05/2024	In-person	3	TA follow-up
UDC-07-STREET-Lutze	26/06/2024	In-person	3	TA follow-up
UDC-07-STREET-Lutze	09/09/2024	In-person	3	TA follow-up
UDC-07-STREET-Lutze	28/10/2024	Online	3	Analysis of results after TA
UDC-07-STREET-Lutze	18/12/2024	Online	4	Analysis of results after TA
UDC-07-STREET-Lutze	09/01/2025	Online	3	Analysis of results after TA
USFD- 05-AB FLUME-Martins	15/01/2024	Online	2	TNA preparations
USFD- 05-AB FLUME-Martins	20/02/2024	Online	3	TNA preparations
USFD- 05-AB FLUME-Martins	09/03/2024	Online	3	TNA preparations
USFD- 05-AB FLUME-Martins	28/03/2024	Online	4	TNA preparations
USFD-06-BURIED-Jokosimovic	14/06/2024	In-person	2	Planning meeting
USFD-06-BURIED-Jokosimovic	12/07/2025	Online	2	Planning meeting
USFD-06-BURIED-Jokosimovic	21/07/2024	In-person	4	Planning meeting
USFD-06-BURIED-Jokosimovic	01/08/2024	In-person	4	Data analysis
USFD-06-BURIED-Jokosimovic	02/08/2024	In-person	4	Data analysis
USFD-06-BURIED-Jokosimovic	05/08/2024	In-person	4	Data analysis
USFD-06-BURIED-Jokosimovic	14/08/2024	In-person	4	Data analysis
USFD-06-BURIED-Jokosimovic	14/01/2025	Online	2	Data analysis

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USFD-06-BURIED-Jokosimovic	31/01/2025	Online	3	Data analysis
USFD-06-BURIED-Jokosimovic	26/02/2025	Online	3	Planning meeting
USFD-06-BURIED-Jokosimovic	10/03/2025	Online	4	Planning meeting
USFD-06-BURIED-Jokosimovic	31/03/2025	In-person/Online	4	Data analysis
USFD-06-BURIED-Jokosimovic	07/04/2025	In-person	4	Data analysis
USFD-06-BURIED-Jokosimovic	14/04/2025	In-person	4	Data analysis
USFD-08-RTCRIG-Gutierrez	29/04/2024	Online	6	Sensor plan
USFD-07-RTCRIG-Vanderwerf	14/04/2024	Online	4	TNA preparations
USFD-08-RTCRIG-Gutierrez	21/05/2024	Online	6	Progress sensor plan and rig
USFD-07-RTCRIG-Vanderwerf	03/06/2024	Online	5	Testing plan
USFD-07-RTCRIG-Vanderwerf	26/06/2024	Online	2	Preparations for TNA start
USFD-08-RTCRIG-Gutierrez	09/08/2024	Online	2	RTC rig pump repair updates
USFD-08-RTCRIG-Gutierrez	02/08/2024	Online	4	Capacitance probes code
USFD-07-RTCRIG-Vanderwerf	09/09/2024	Online	4	Knowledge exchange
USFD-08-RTCRIG-Gutierrez	25/22/2024	Online	5	Review data collected
USFD-08-RTCRIG-Gutierrez	28/11/2024	Online	5	Draft TNA report
USFD-07-RTCRIG-Vanderwerf	29/11/2024	Online	3	Draft results
DEL-01-BLOOP-Besharat	19/09/2023	Online	3	Answering questions on TA
DEL-01-BLOOP-Besharat	09/02/2024	Online	6	Planning TA experimental plan
DEL-01-BLOOP-Besharat	29/04/2024	In-Person	7	Reception of Elias and Ruilin at Deltares
DEL-01-BLOOP-Besharat	14/05/2024	In-Person	8	Reception of Moshen Besharat at Deltares
DEL-01-BLOOP-Besharat	07/11/2024	Online	5	Data reports TA
DEL-02-BLOOP-Farhadiroushan	12/09/2023	Online	6	Answering questions on TA
DEL-02-BLOOP-Farhadiroushan	26/01/2024	Online	4	Update on TA planning
DEL-02-BLOOP-Farhadiroushan	11/04/2024	In-Person	5	Reception Silixa for planning experimental setup
DEL-02-BLOOP-Farhadiroushan	24/05/2024	In-Person	3	Beta loop access technician Silixa

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<i>Project Acronym</i>	<i>Date</i>	<i>Venue</i>	<i>Approx. # of attendees</i>	<i>Description</i>
DEL-02-BLOOP-Farhadiroushan	5/06/2024	In-person/online	5	Kick-off experiments
DEL-02-BLOOP-Farhadiroushan	23/08/2024	In-person/online	4	Discussion processing methods observations
DEL-02-BLOOP-Farhadiroushan	10/09/2024	Online	6	Final points for experimental setups discussion
DEL-02-BLOOP-Farhadiroushan	16/09/2024	In-Person	5	Installation of Fibre optic
DEL-02-BLOOP-Farhadiroushan	02/10/2024	Online	5	Experiments mixed-clay water tests
DEL-02-BLOOP-Farhadiroushan	17/04/2025	Online	4	Postprocessing and analysis of results
EAWAG-05-UWO-Abdel	12/03/2023	On site	8	Installation of Sulfilogger and field visit UWO
EAWAG-05-UWO-Abdel	05/06/2024	Online	4	Discussing final results
EAWAG-05-UWO-Abdel	28/08/2024	Online	2	Discussing maintenance of sulfilogger
EAWAG-05-UWO-Abdel	23/10/2024	Online	3	Discussing interim results
EAWAG-05-UWO-Abdel	18/12/2024	Online	4	Discussing interim results, H2S sensor problems
EAWAG-05-UWO-Abdel	30/01/2025	Online	6	Discussing final results
EAWAG-04-UWO- Dittmer	22/03/2024	Online	10	Kickoff meeting
EAWAG-04-UWO- Dittmer	20/04/2024	Online	10	Analysis of available datasets from UWO
EAWAG-04-UWO- Dittmer	17/6/2024	Online	8	Analysis of suitable methods
EAWAG-04-UWO- Dittmer	09/07/2024	Online	6	Analysis of methods
EAWAG-04-UWO- Dittmer	05/08/2024	Online	4	Analysis of results
EAWAG-04-UWO-Dittmer	08/10/2024	Online	6	Analysis of results
EAWAG-04-UWO- Dittmer	04/09/2024	In person	11	TA User group meeting at Eawag discussion of concepts, analysis of results, precipitation scaling laws, publication
EAWAG-04-UWO-Dittmer	08/10/2024	Online	6	Analysis of results
EAWAG-04-UWO- Dittmer	10/12/2024	Online	7	Analysis of results
EAWAG-04-UWO-Dittmer	13/01/2025	Online	4	Analysis of results and TA follow-up
IKT-03-TEST-Carnacina	25/10/2024	Online	4	Discussing/planning test procedure
IKT-03-TEST-Carnacina	16/01/2025	In-person	5	Discussing first observations for adjustment of test procedure
IKT-03-TEST-Carnacina	13/02/2025	Online	3	Analysis of results and TA follow-up
IKT-04-TEST-Johansen	14/05/2024	Online	4	Discussing/planning test procedure
IKT-04-TEST-Johansen	14/06/2024	Online	4	Analysis of interim results
IKT-04-TEST-Johansen	27/06/2024	Online	4	Analysis of interim results
IKT-04-TEST-Johansen	05/07/2024	Online	3	Analysis of interim results
IKT-04-TEST-Johansen	12/07/2024	Online	4	Analysis of results after TA

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<i>Project Acronym</i>	<i>Date</i>	<i>Venue</i>	<i>Approx. # of attendees</i>	<i>Description</i>
IKT-04-TEST-Johansen	02/08/2024	Online	4	TA follow-up
IKT-04-TEST-Johansen	19/08/2024	Online	4	TA follow-up
INSA-02-OTHU-Prodanovic	14/02/2024	Online	4	Planning and work methodology
INSA-02-OTHU-Prodanovic	22/03/2024	Online	10	Whole consortium meeting, detailed presentation of the Plant-O-Meter by the company. Refining the experimental procedure.
INSA-02-OTHU-Prodanovic	08/05/2024	Online	4	Final administrative details and visit planning
INSA-02-OTHU-Prodanovic	12/06/2024	In-person	8	Whole consortium meeting, modeling and data analysis
INSA-02-OTHU-Prodanovic	18/06/2024	In-person	6	TA user group meeting in Lyon to install the experient and refine the monitoring protocol on site
INSA-02-OTHU-Prodanovic	11/09/2024	Online	3	Presentation of the data analysis and preliminary results
INSA-02-OTHU-Prodanovic	07/11/2024	Online	10	Whole consortium meeting. Presentation of the consolidated results and open discussion
INSA-03-GROOF-Förster	16-17/09/2024	In-person	6	TA user group meeting in Lyon + building of the experimental green roof
INSA-03-GROOF-Förster	25-26/02/2025	In-person	6	Meeting in Lyon with TA user group + analysis and discussion of first results
INSA-04-OTHU DRB-Le Gac	06-07/06/2024	In-person	4	TA user group field visit in Lyon
INSA-04-OTHU DRB-Le Gac	08/11/2024	Online	5	Meeting on data analysis and discussion on results
AAU-01-FREJLEV-Laanerau	09/02/2025	Online	4	TA initial meeting
AAU-01-FREJLEV-Laanerau	16/04/2024	Online	13	Virtual tour of the facility
AAU-01-FREJLEV-Laanerau	12/06/2024	Online	9	Planning TA and experimental setup
AAU-01-FREJLEV-Laanerau	28/10/2024	Online	4	Status meeting on experimental setup. UFA preparation
AAU-01-FREJLEV-Laanerau	19/11/2024	In-person/online	4/8	Kick-off meeting
AAU-01-FREJLEV-Laanerau	13/12/2024	Online	3	Technical meeting. Finalizing UFA
AAU-01-FREJLEV-Laanerau	16/01/2025	Online	4	Final planning and arrangement of TA
AAU-01-FREJLEV-Laanerau	10-15/02/2025	In-person	5	TA startup and 1 st week of experimental work at the facility
AAU-01-FREJLEV-Laanerau	21/02/2025	Online	13	Review collected data from first week of experiments. Refining plan for 2 nd week of experiments
AAU-01-FREJLEV-Laanerau	24-28/02/2025	In-person	4	2 nd week of experiments at the facility
AAU-01-FREJLEV-Laanerau	11/03/2025	Online	13	Wind-up, TA-report preparation
AAU-01-FREJLEV-Laanerau	27/03/2025	Online	4	TA-report review